

Bachelor's thesis

From Jasmine through Mulan to Raya.
Representation of non-white female
Disney main characters focussing on the
dimensions “race” and “gender”

Akkon University of Human Sciences

Course of studies: Social Work B.A. (dual study)

Supervisor: Prof. Dr. Saskia Eschenbacher

Semester: summer semester 2023

Cristina Martínez Reig

Enrolment number: [REDACTED]

Address: [REDACTED]

Telephone: [REDACTED]

E-mail address: cristina.martinez@akkon-campus.de

29 September 2023

Acknowledgement

First of all, I would like to thank Professor Dr. Saskia Eschenbacher for her excellent guidance in the elaboration of this Bachelor's thesis. Her wise observations and suggestions have been an invaluable help in shaping this work into the form it now has.

A special thank you for Professor Dr. Saskia Eschenbacher, Professor Dr. Alessandra Romano and Mr. Kai Wenzke for their last-minute, lightning-fast response, which made the timely submission of this Bachelor's thesis possible.

I would also like to express my gratitude to my coworker Rocco Seiler, for asking time and time again about the progress of my work, acting as a supervisor of sorts and helping me sort out my ideas at various stages of this process.

A huge thank you to Marta Martínez Reig and Daniel López Puertollano for making the data collection possible. Without the access to Disney+ they provided me with, it would not have been possible to take the thousands of screenshots that form the basis of this Bachelor's thesis. An extra thank you to Marta Martínez Reig for her assistance in proofreading the appendices.

Finally, I would like to thank Clemens Müller and Xavier Barcons Planas for their patience, understanding and emotional support during the tumultuous weeks and months in which I lived for and by this Bachelor's thesis.

Abstract

The Walt Disney Company is a hegemonic conglomerate on its way to dominating the entertainment industry; its portrayals of race and gender have informed and continue to inform the identity formation of its usually young audiences. To analyse the representation of non-white female Disney main characters, ten Walt Disney Animation Studios films were selected: *Aladdin* (1992) with Jasmine, *Pocahontas* (1995), *The Hunchback of Notre Dame* (1996) with Esmeralda, *Mulan* (1998), *Atlantis: The Lost Empire* (2001) with Kida, *Lilo & Stitch* (2002) with Lilo, *The Princess and the Frog* (2009) with Tiana, *Moana* (2016), *Raya and the Last Dragon* (2021) with Raya and *Encanto* (2021) with Mirabel.

Following a pyramidal structure, a total of 5326 screenshots were condensed into seven in-depth analyses (which, due to time and space constraints, did not include Kida, Lilo and Mirabel); these analyses were further condensed into seven summaries, which were then comparatively examined to assess the evolution of the representation of non-white female main characters. Drawing on three of Stuart Hall's works for the "race" dimension and Judith Butler's *Gender Trouble* (1999) for the "gender" dimension, it was concluded that the analysed characters displayed a tendency towards fewer stereotypes and less sexualisation on the one hand, and an absence of heterosexual romance on the other hand. Moreover, this Bachelor's thesis identified three phases ("sexy", "no-sexy/yes-hetero" and "loves-no-man"), which do not align with the three eras suggested in the literature. In the coming years, the author speculates that Walt Disney Animation Studios might venture into LGBTQIA+, disability or non-normative beauty representation.

Table of contents

1. Introduction	1
1.1. Self-positioning	1
1.2. Subject matter: Disney’s hegemony and identity development	1
1.3. State of the art: Representation of non-white female Disney main characters	2
1.4. Research questions	3
1.5. Structure of the thesis	4
2. Theoretical and historical reflection	6
2.1. Race	6
2.1.1. <i>Race, the Floating Signifier</i> (1997a)	6
2.1.2. <i>The Spectacle of the Other</i> (1997b)	7
2.1.3. <i>The West and the Rest: Discourse and Power</i> (1992)	8
2.2. Gender	9
2.2.1. Distinction sex-gender	9
2.2.2. Heterosexual matrix	10
2.2.3. Prohibitive and generative effects of power	10
2.2.4. Performativity of gender	11
2.3. Intersectionality	12
2.4. The Walt Disney Company	14
2.4.1. The early years: Laugh-O-gram Films, Mickey Mouse and <i>Steamboat Willie</i> (1920–1928)	14
2.4.2. Renaming to Walt Disney Productions and <i>Snow White and the Seven Dwarfs</i> (1929–1949)	15
2.4.3. <i>Mary Poppins</i> , death of Walt Disney and decline of the company (1950–1989)	15
2.4.4. The Disney Renaissance and expansion (1990–present)	16
2.4.5. Current relevance of The Walt Disney Company	17
2.5. The Disney Princess	18
2.5.1. Disney princesses and “Disney Princesses”	18
2.5.2. The three eras of Disney princesses	19
3. Method	22
3.1. Formation of the analysis corpus	22
3.2. Determination of aids and appliances	26
3.3. Data collection	26
3.4. Description of the database	27
3.5. Analysis of the data	28
4. Analysis of the individual Disney characters	30
4.1. Jasmine from <i>Aladdin</i> (1992)	30

4.2. Pocahontas from <i>Pocahontas</i> (1995).....	30
4.3. Esmeralda from <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> (1996).....	32
4.4. Mulan from <i>Mulan</i> (1998).....	33
4.5. Tiana from <i>The Princess and the Frog</i> (2009).....	34
4.6. Moana from <i>Moana</i> (2016).....	36
4.7. Raya from <i>Raya and the Last Dragon</i> (2021).....	37
5. Discussion of the evolution of the representation of non-white female Disney main characters.....	38
5.1. Summary of the analyses.....	38
5.2. Representation of the “race” dimension.....	39
5.3. Representation of the “gender” dimension.....	41
5.4. Three phases in the representation of non-white female Disney main characters.....	44
5.5. Speculation on future tendencies in the representation of non-white female Disney main characters.....	45
6. Limitations	47
7. Conclusion.....	48

List of tables

Table 1. Comparison between the “film and television analysis” method by Lothar Mikos (left) and its adaption for this Bachelor’s thesis (right). Steps in bold constitute the actual method used in this Bachelor’s thesis.	22
Table 2. List of all Walt Disney Animated Studios films in chronological order, together with their release year, the reason they were included or excluded from the analysis corpus and relevant human, non-white and/or female characters. Colour code: grey for anthology films; films in blue for films with non-human protagonists; films in orange for films with white protagonists; films in yellow for films with male protagonists; green for included films.	26
Table 3. List of the ten films from the analysis corpus in chronological order, together with the number of screenshots for each film, the length of the film, the ratio between screenshots and length of the film and the timestamps of the first and last appearance. Colour code: red for ratios screenshots/length equal or lower than 5,00; orange for ratios between 5,01 and 6,00; yellow for ratios between 6,01 and 7,00; green for ratios higher than 7,01.	28
Table 4. Summary of the analysed non-white female Disney main characters including name, age (in parentheses), status, match with the race or ethnicity of the voice actor, physical appearance, psychological traits and main motivation. Sources (top to bottom): John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992; Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995; Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, The Hunchback of Notre Dame, 1996; Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998; John Musker and Ron Clements, The Princess and the Frog, 2009; John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016; Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, Raya and the Last Dragon, 2021.	39

List of figures

Figure 1. Flowchart representing the exclusion/inclusion algorithm used to build the analysis corpus.	23
Figure 2. “Original poster,” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.	xxvi
Figure 3. “Screenshots of 00:41:34 and 01:24:42 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.	xxvii
Figure 4. “Screenshots of 00:18:27, 01:10:23, 01:16:47, and 01:25:23 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.	xxvii
Figure 5. “Screenshots of 00:13:24, 00:22:27, 00:23:49, 00:41:46, 00:53:52, 00:56:57, 01:00:56, 01:05:01, 01:12:06 and 01:16:04 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.	xxviii
Figure 6. “Screenshots of 00:14:26, 00:16:41 and 00:21:50 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.	xxviii
Figure 7. “Screenshots of 00:19:24, 00:21:02, 00:57:54, 01:00:52 and 01:17:33 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.	xxix
Figure 8. “Screenshots of 00:22:34, 00:56:51, 01:00:22, 01:01:44, 01:02:03 and 01:16:48 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.	xxix
Figure 9. “Screenshots of 00:20:59, 00:23:21 and 01:18:07 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.	xxix
Figure 10. “Screenshots of 00:13:30, 00:16:46 and 00:18:21 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.	xxx

Figure 11. “Screenshots of 00:12:40, 00:16:46 and 00:12:57 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.....	xxx
Figure 12. “Screenshots of 00:13:20, 00:14:07 and 00:14:22 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.....	xxx
Figure 13. “Screenshots of 00:16:39, 00:18:39 and 00:19:13 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.....	xxx
Figure 14. “Screenshots of 00:21:54, 00:22:50 and 00:23:00 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.....	xxx
Figure 15. “Screenshots of 00:14:07 and 00:14:22 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.....	xxx
Figure 16. “Screenshots of 00:24:25, 00:24:43, 00:24:53 and 00:25:31 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.....	xxx
Figure 17. “Screenshots of 00:41:34 and 00:41:46 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.....	xxx
Figure 18. “Screenshots of 00:50:34 and 00:53:52 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.....	xxx
Figure 19. “Screenshots of 00:55:39, 00:56:57 and 00:57:45 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.....	xxx
Figure 20. “Screenshots of 00:59:00, 00:59:18, 01:00:01, 01:00:12 and 01:00:22 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.....	xxx
Figure 21. “Screenshots of 01:00:43, 01:00:52, 01:01:04 and 01:01:37 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.....	xxx
Figure 22. “Screenshots of 01:02:07, 01:02:09 and 01:02:11 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.....	xxx
Figure 23. “Screenshots of 01:04:44, 01:04:56 and 01:06:04 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.....	xxx
Figure 24. “Screenshots of 01:10:27, 01:12:41 and 01:13:24 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.....	xxx
Figure 25. “Screenshots of 01:15:41, 01:16:04, 01:16:18, 01:16:48, 01:17:52, 01:18:07, 01:18:25 and 01:21:07 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.....	xxx
Figure 26. “Screenshots of 01:24:48, 01:25:31, 01:25:35, and 01:25:42 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.....	xxx
Figure 27. “Original poster,” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.....	xxx
Figure 28. “Screenshots of 01:11:23 and 00:30:54 (left to right),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.....	xxx
Figure 29. “Screenshots of 00:08:06, 00:17:41, 00:32:28, 00:40:13, 00:40:31 and 00:40:47 (left to right, top to bottom),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.....	xxx
Figure 30. “Screenshots of 00:41:03, 00:41:39, 00:46:12, 01:06:23 and 01:07:00 (left to right, top to bottom),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.....	xxx
Figure 31. “Screenshots of 00:08:36, 00:17:41, 00:20:11, 00:29:50, 00:30:19, 00:31:41, 00:39:04, 00:54:10, 01:07:25 and 01:14:38 (left to right, top to bottom),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.....	xxx

Figure 32. “Screenshots of 00:10:59, 00:13:10, 00:14:13, 00:15:01, 00:21:11, 00:36:00 and 00:38:03 (left to right, top to bottom),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.....	xxxix
Figure 33. “Screenshots of 00:41:17, 00:46:51, 00:49:19, 00:52:21, 01:01:42 and 01:07:47 (left to right, top to bottom),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.....	xxxix
Figure 34. “Screenshots of 00:09:17 and 00:10:26 (left to right),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.....	xxxix
Figure 35. “Screenshots of 00:07:57 and 00:08:18 (left to right),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.....	xl
Figure 36. “Screenshots of 00:11:24, 00:14:26, 00:16:48 and 00:18:07 (left to right),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.....	xl
Figure 37. “Screenshots of 00:29:35, 00:30:34, 00:32:43, 00:37:02, 00:41:35 and 00:42:33 (left to right, top to bottom),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.....	xli
Figure 38. “Screenshots of 00:45:41, 00:48:58, 00:50:34 and 00:51:33 (left to right),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.....	xli
Figure 39. “Screenshots of 00:56:23, 00:58:18, 00:58:47, 00:58:49, 00:59:13 and 01:01:42 (left to right, top to bottom),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.....	xlii
Figure 40. “Screenshots of 01:02:25, 01:05:39 and 01:06:17 (left to right, top to bottom),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.....	xlii
Figure 41. “Screenshots of 01:07:12, 01:07:40 and 01:08:08 (left to right, top to bottom),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.....	xliii
Figure 42. “Screenshots of 01:11:23, 01:12:41, 01:13:34, 01:13:36, 01:15:14 and 01:15:31 (left to right, top to bottom),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.....	xliii
Figure 43. “Original poster,” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, The Hunchback of Notre Dame, 1996.....	xliv
Figure 44. “Screenshots of 00:38:25 and 0:27:05 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, The Hunchback of Notre Dame, 1996.....	xlv
Figure 45. “Screenshots of 00:18:32, 0:22:15, 00:23:47 and 01:23:07 (left to right, top to bottom),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, The Hunchback of Notre Dame, 1996.....	xlv
Figure 46. “Screenshots of 00:17:27, 00:17:35, 00:27:58, 00:28:07, 00:28:23, 00:32:04, 00:32:28, 01:09:37, 01:10:45 and 01:12:09 (left to right, top to bottom),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, The Hunchback of Notre Dame, 1996.....	xlvi
Figure 47. “Screenshots of 00:22:10, 00:22:15 and 0:27:40 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, The Hunchback of Notre Dame, 1996.....	xlvi
Figure 48. “Screenshots of 00:36:33 and 0:42:00 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, The Hunchback of Notre Dame, 1996.....	xlvii
Figure 49. “Screenshots of 00:18:32, 00:28:41, 00:28:52, 00:29:38, 00:30:07, 00:31:17, 00:43:32, 00:52:23, 00:53:54 and 01:00:05 (left to right, top to bottom),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, The Hunchback of Notre Dame, 1996.....	xlvii
Figure 50. “Screenshots of 00:17:14, 00:23:29, 00:41:36, 00:44:05, 00:59:17, 00:59:48, 01:00:34, 01:01:37, 01:10:07, 01:12:08, 01:22:35 and 01:23:47 (left to right, top to bottom),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, The Hunchback of Notre Dame, 1996.....	xlviii
Figure 51. “Screenshots of 00:17:41, 00:29:08 and 00:29:14 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, The Hunchback of Notre Dame, 1996.....	xlviii

Figure 52. “Screenshots of 00:31:50, 00:42:52, 00:44:28 and 01:21:12 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.	xlix
Figure 53. “Screenshots of 00:17:00, 00:19:48, 00:23:26, 00:23:36, 00:23:40, 00:23:45 and 00:39:54 (left to right, top to bottom),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.....	xlix
Figure 54. “Screenshots of 00:17:00, 00:17:09, 00:17:20 and 00:17:27 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.	xlix
Figure 55. “Screenshots of 00:17:33, 00:17:35, 00:17:41 and 00:17:57 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.	l
Figure 56. “Screenshots of 00:18:32 and 00:19:48 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.....	l
Figure 57. “Screenshots of 00:22:07, 00:22:13, 00:22:22 and 00:22:28 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.	l
Figure 58. “Screenshots of 00:23:13, 00:23:17, 00:23:29, 00:23:34, 00:23:38, 00:23:41, 00:23:45, and 00:23:49 (left to right, top to bottom),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.	li
Figure 59. “Screenshots of 00:24:31, 00:24:41 and 00:24:49 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.	li
Figure 60. “Screenshots of 00:27:42, 00:27:58 and 00:28:07 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.	li
Figure 61. “Screenshots of 00:28:10 and 00:28:23 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.....	lii
Figure 62. “Screenshots of 00:28:44, 00:28:45, 00:28:58, 00:29:11, 00:29:18, 00:29:39, 00:29:43 and 00:30:07 (left to right, top to bottom),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.	lii
Figure 63. “Screenshots of 00:31:17, 00:31:51, 00:32:02, 00:32:10, 00:32:29 and 00:33:00 (left to right, top to bottom),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.	liii
Figure 64. “Screenshots of 00:33:08, 00:33:19 and 00:33:34 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.	liiii
Figure 65. “Screenshots of 00:34:03, 00:34:14, 00:34:18 and 00:34:30 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.	liiii
Figure 66. “Screenshots of 00:35:01, 00:35:14, 00:35:55, 00:36:40, 00:37:31 and 00:38:13 (left to right, top to bottom),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.	liv
Figure 67. “Screenshots of 00:39:28, 00:39:50, 00:40:44, 00:41:10, 00:41:20 and 00:41:48 (left to right, top to bottom),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.	liv
Figure 68. “Screenshots of 00:43:28, 00:43:44, 00:44:05 and 00:44:09 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.	lv
Figure 69. “Screenshots of 00:49:00 and 00:50:05 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.....	lv
Figure 70. “Screenshots of 00:53:27, 00:53:53, 00:54:30 and 00:54:37 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.	lv
Figure 71. “Screenshots of 00:59:30, 00:59:54 and 01:00:20 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.	lv

Figure 72. “Screenshots of 01:00:34 and 01:01:32 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.....	lvi
Figure 73. “Screenshots of 01:09:39, 01:10:07 and 01:11:31 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.	lvi
Figure 74. “Screenshots of 01:12:09, 01:13:17, 01:14:03, 01:14:33, 01:14:41, 01:18:25 and 01:18:43 (left to right, top to bottom),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.....	lvi
Figure 75. “Screenshots of 01:19:45, 01:20:10, 01:21:18, 01:21:42 and 01:21:44 (left to right, top to bottom),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.	lvii
Figure 76. “Screenshots of 01:22:08, 01:22:35, 01:22:44, 01:22:57 and 01:24:15 (left to right, top to bottom),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, <i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i> , 1996.	lvii
Figure 77. “Original poster,” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, <i>Mulan</i> , 1998.....	lviii
Figure 78. “Screenshots of 00:03:27 and 01:14:22 (left to right),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, <i>Mulan</i> , 1998.	lix
Figure 79. “Screenshots of 00:04:32, 00:08:17, 00:18:53, 00:19:10, 00:35:13, 00:41:03, 00:44:25, 01:00:10, 01:09:30 and 01:13:05 (left to right, top to bottom),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, <i>Mulan</i> , 1998.	lix
Figure 80. “Screenshots of 00:03:18, 00:03:41, 00:07:05, 00:40:28, 00:49:01, 00:55:53, 00:58:30, 01:09:59, 01:14:10, 01:14:27 and 01:15:01 (left to right, top to bottom),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, <i>Mulan</i> , 1998.	lx
Figure 81. “Screenshots of 00:05:57, 00:07:17, 00:07:41, 00:08:43, 00:13:09, 00:27:11, 00:29:23 and 00:34:21 (left to right, top to bottom),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, <i>Mulan</i> , 1998.....	lxi
Figure 82. “Screenshots of 00:03:23, 00:35:41, 00:38:56, 00:39:22, 00:39:36 and 00:44:28 (left to right, top to bottom),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, <i>Mulan</i> , 1998.	lxii
Figure 83. “Screenshots of 00:27:28, 00:28:57, 00:33:08 and 00:36:35 (left to right),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, <i>Mulan</i> , 1998.	lxii
Figure 84. “Screenshots of 00:04:41, 00:15:22 and 00:19:08 (left to right),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, <i>Mulan</i> , 1998.	lxii
Figure 85. “Screenshots of 01:00:34 and 01:19:18 (left to right),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, <i>Mulan</i> , 1998.	lxiii
Figure 86. “Screenshots of 00:07:32, 01:05:38 and 01:12:35 (left to right),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, <i>Mulan</i> , 1998.	lxiii
Figure 87. “Screenshots of 00:13:00, 00:18:31 and 00:52:35 (left to right),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, <i>Mulan</i> , 1998.	lxiii
Figure 88. “Screenshots of 00:03:06, 00:03:10 and 00:03:23 (left to right),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, <i>Mulan</i> , 1998.	lxiv
Figure 89. “Screenshots of 00:03:41, 00:04:41 and 00:04:54 (left to right),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, <i>Mulan</i> , 1998.	lxiv
Figure 90. “Screenshots of 00:05:55, 00:06:20, 00:06:46, 00:07:17, 00:07:40 and 00:08:22 (left to right, top to bottom),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, <i>Mulan</i> , 1998.	lxiv
Figure 91. “Screenshots of 00:09:28, 00:10:38 and 00:11:04 (left to right),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, <i>Mulan</i> , 1998.	lxv

Figure 92. “Screenshots of 00:12:12, 00:13:09 and 00:13:18 (left to right),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.	lxv
Figure 93. “Screenshots of 00:13:47, 00:15:00, 00:15:22 and 00:16:17 (left to right),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.	lxv
Figure 94. “Screenshots of 00:16:58, 00:17:11, 00:17:44, 00:18:58 and 00:19:27 (left to right, top to bottom),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.	lxvi
Figure 95. “Screenshots of 00:27:11, 00:28:15 and 00:29:20 (left to right),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.	lxvi
Figure 96. “Screenshots of 00:29:29, 00:33:05, 00:33:19 and 00:34:05 (left to right),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.	lxvi
Figure 97. “Screenshots of 00:35:35, 00:36:32, 00:38:02, 00:38:43 and 00:40:03 (left to right, top to bottom),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.	lxvii
Figure 98. “Screenshots of 00:40:13, 00:40:28, 00:40:39, 00:40:47 and 00:40:54 (left to right, top to bottom),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.	lxvii
Figure 99. “Screenshots of 00:42:18, 00:43:13, 00:44:16 and 00:45:28 (left to right),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.	lxviii
Figure 100. “Screenshots of 00:48:33, 00:48:50, 00:50:29, 00:51:49 and 00:52:35 (left to right, top to bottom),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.	lxviii
Figure 101. “Screenshots of 00:53:37, 00:55:31, 00:56:17, 00:56:38, 00:57:08, 00:58:52 and 00:59:35 (left to right, top to bottom),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.	lxix
Figure 102. “Screenshots of 01:00:15, 01:00:32, 01:01:05 and 01:01:35 (left to right),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.	lxix
Figure 103. “Screenshots of 01:02:23, 01:02:56, 01:03:57, 01:04:10 and 01:05:56 (left to right, top to bottom),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.	lxix
Figure 104. “Screenshots of 01:06:46, 01:06:56 and 01:08:19 (left to right),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.	lxx
Figure 105. “Screenshots of 01:10:14, 01:11:36, 01:12:55, 01:13:07, 01:13:49, 01:14:40 and 01:14:53 (left to right, top to bottom),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.	lxx
Figure 106. “Screenshots of 01:16:35, 01:16:44, 01:17:26, 01:17:45, 01:17:58 and 01:18:12 (left to right, top to bottom),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.	lxxi
Figure 107. “Screenshots of 01:19:35, 01:19:41, 01:19:47 and 01:20:26 (left to right),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.	lxxi
Figure 108. “Screenshots of 01:21:14, 01:21:16 and 01:21:23 (left to right),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.	lxxi
Figure 109. “Original poster,” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>The Princess and the Frog</i> , 2009. .	lxxii
Figure 110. “Screenshots of 00:25:34, 01:21:16 and 00:11:22 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>The Princess and the Frog</i> , 2009.	lxxiii
Figure 111. “Screenshots of 00:02:22, 00:06:05, 00:06:43, 00:08:16, 00:12:17, 00:23:51, 01:18:16, 01:28:06, 01:28:31, 01:28:58 and 01:29:45 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>The Princess and the Frog</i> , 2009.	lxxiii

Figure 112. “Screenshots of 00:06:39, 00:07:18, 00:08:16, 00:09:48, 00:33:05, 00:36:10, 00:40:24, 00:50:20, 01:05:50 and 01:29:09 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, The Princess and the Frog, 2009.	lxxiv
Figure 113. “Screenshots of 00:07:50, 00:09:21 and 00:09:58 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, The Princess and the Frog, 2009.	lxxiv
Figure 114. “Screenshots of 00:13:37 and 00:39:44 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, The Princess and the Frog, 2009.	lxxv
Figure 115. “Screenshots of 00:13:01, 00:15:13, 00:42:58, 01:10:28 and 01:18:47 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, The Princess and the Frog, 2009.	lxxv
Figure 116. “Screenshots of 00:13:15, 00:14:01 and 00:24:50 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, The Princess and the Frog, 2009.	lxxv
Figure 117. “Screenshots of 00:26:47 and 00:29:24 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, The Princess and the Frog, 2009.	lxxvi
Figure 118. “Screenshots of 00:26:47, 00:26:47, 00:26:47, 00:26:47, 00:26:47 and 00:29:24 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, The Princess and the Frog, 2009.	lxxvi
Figure 119. “Screenshots of 00:05:00, 00:07:04 and 00:13:19 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, The Princess and the Frog, 2009.	lxxvi
Figure 120. “Screenshots of 01:04:50 and 01:20:01 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, The Princess and the Frog, 2009.	lxxvii
Figure 121. “Screenshots of 00:27:03, 00:33:02, 00:45:58, 00:51:34, 00:54:55, 00:55:45, 01:10:42 and 01:28:18 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, The Princess and the Frog, 2009.	lxxvii
Figure 122. “Screenshots of 00:24:35, 00:28:01, 00:30:05, 00:33:28, 00:46:18, 00:51:20, 01:01:33 and 01:20:28 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, The Princess and the Frog, 2009.	lxxviii
Figure 123. “Screenshots of 00:02:44, 00:11:22, 00:22:54 and 00:59:58 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, The Princess and the Frog, 2009.	lxxviii
Figure 124. “Screenshots of 00:01:31, 00:01:54 and 00:02:15 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, The Princess and the Frog, 2009.	lxxix
Figure 125. “Screenshots of 00:03:54, 00:04:24, 00:04:43, 00:05:18 and 00:06:24 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, The Princess and the Frog, 2009.	lxxix
Figure 126. “Screenshots of 00:06:39, 00:06:49 and 00:07:40 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, The Princess and the Frog, 2009.	lxxix
Figure 127. “Screenshots of 00:07:58, 00:10:03 and 00:10:22 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, The Princess and the Frog, 2009.	lxxx
Figure 128. “Screenshots of 00:10:49, 00:11:28 and 00:11:49 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, The Princess and the Frog, 2009.	lxxx
Figure 129. “Screenshots of 00:12:14, 00:12:33 and 00:12:55 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, The Princess and the Frog, 2009.	lxxx
Figure 130. “Screenshots of 00:13:41 and 00:14:07 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, The Princess and the Frog, 2009.	lxxx
Figure 131. “Screenshots of 00:22:23, 00:23:06, 00:24:43 and 00:24:57 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, The Princess and the Frog, 2009.	lxxx

Figure 132. “Screenshots of 00:26:29, 00:26:47, 00:27:14, 00:29:20 and 00:29:31 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>The Princess and the Frog</i> , 2009.....	lxxxi
Figure 133. “Screenshots of 00:29:53, 00:30:40, 00:31:06, 00:33:40, 00:34:03, 00:34:21 and 00:35:27 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>The Princess and the Frog</i> , 2009.	lxxxii
Figure 134. “Screenshots of 00:36:01, 00:40:53, 00:43:57, 00:44:26, 00:51:47, 00:52:51 and 00:54:13 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>The Princess and the Frog</i> , 2009.	lxxxii
Figure 135. “Screenshots of 00:55:03, 00:56:25, 00:59:02, 00:59:30, 00:59:51 and 00:59:58 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>The Princess and the Frog</i> , 2009.....	lxxxiii
Figure 136. “Screenshots of 01:00:56, 01:02:43 and 01:05:50 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>The Princess and the Frog</i> , 2009.	lxxxiii
Figure 137. “Screenshots of 01:07:58, 01:09:27, 01:10:15, 01:10:48, 01:12:02, 01:13:28, 01:13:57 and 01:14:59 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>The Princess and the Frog</i> , 2009.....	lxxxiv
Figure 138. “Screenshots of 01:17:14, 01:18:02, 01:19:11, 01:20:24, 01:20:32, 01:20:50 and 01:20:57 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>The Princess and the Frog</i> , 2009.	lxxxiv
Figure 139. “Screenshots of 01:23:16, 01:23:30, 01:25:21, 01:26:27, 01:26:50 and 01:26:59 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>The Princess and the Frog</i> , 2009.....	lxxxv
Figure 140. “Screenshots of 01:27:24, 01:27:48, 01:28:15, 01:28:22 and 01:28:53 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>The Princess and the Frog</i> , 2009.....	lxxxv
Figure 141. “Screenshots of 01:29:03, 01:29:11, 01:29:20, 01:30:09, 01:30:15 and 01:30:19 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>The Princess and the Frog</i> , 2009.....	lxxxvi
Figure 142. “Original poster,” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>Moana</i> , 2016.....	lxxxvii
Figure 143. “Screenshots of 01:01:50 and 01:27:50 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>Moana</i> , 2016.....	lxxxviii
Figure 144. “Screenshots of 00:05:06, 00:09:30, 00:11:33, 00:11:39, 00:13:06, 00:33:08, 00:59:47 and 01:35:58 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>Moana</i> , 2016.....	lxxxviii
Figure 145. “Screenshots of 00:12:07, 00:13:30, 00:14:26, 00:19:41, 00:41:52, 00:48:35, 00:50:18, 01:04:40, 01:13:00, 01:22:33, 01:22:36 and 01:23:37 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>Moana</i> , 2016.	lxxxix
Figure 146. “Screenshots of 00:36:33, 00:37:51, 00:43:14, 00:44:41 and 01:15:28 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>Moana</i> , 2016.	xc
Figure 147. “Screenshots of 00:16:50, 00:17:37, 00:26:07, 00:51:44, 01:20:57 and 01:21:01 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>Moana</i> , 2016.	xc
Figure 148. “Screenshots of 00:18:00, 00:18:08, 00:31:14, 00:34:19, 00:42:24, 00:46:34, 00:48:05, 00:55:42, 00:59:14, 01:05:07 and 01:24:00 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>Moana</i> , 2016.....	xc
Figure 149. “Screenshots of 00:05:17, 00:09:02 and 00:12:24 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>Moana</i> , 2016.....	xc
Figure 150. “Screenshots of 00:19:25, 00:30:12, 00:33:32, 01:10:25, 01:29:43 and 01:33:06 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, <i>Moana</i> , 2016.	xcii

Figure 151. “Screenshots of 00:03:49, 00:42:32, 00:57:28 and 01:29:31 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.	xcii
Figure 152. “Screenshots of 00:03:26 and 00:04:08 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.....	xcii
Figure 153. “Screenshots of 00:05:31 and 00:06:55 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.....	xciii
Figure 154. “Screenshots of 00:08:16, 00:08:42 and 00:10:00 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.....	xciii
Figure 155. “Screenshots of 00:10:55 and 00:11:39 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.....	xciii
Figure 156. “Screenshots of 00:12:33, 00:14:38 and 00:15:21 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.....	xciv
Figure 157. “Screenshots of 00:17:44, 00:18:35, 00:19:20 and 00:19:35 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.	xciv
Figure 158. “Screenshots of 00:20:18, 00:21:59, 00:26:07 and 00:27:12 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.	xciv
Figure 159. “Screenshots of 00:28:37, 00:29:54 and 00:31:50 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.....	xciv
Figure 160. “Screenshots of 00:33:18, 00:34:23 and 00:35:01 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.....	xcv
Figure 161. “Screenshots of 00:35:53, 00:37:59, 00:41:52 and 00:43:03 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.	xcv
Figure 162. “Screenshots of 00:44:41, 00:48:05 and 00:48:44 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.....	xcv
Figure 163. “Screenshots of 00:50:18, 00:52:10 and 00:52:42 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.....	xcv
Figure 164. “Screenshots of 00:54:05, 00:54:56 and 00:57:28 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.....	xcvi
Figure 165. “Screenshots of 00:58:13, 00:59:54, 01:04:02, 01:04:40 and 01:05:27 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.	xcvi
Figure 166. “Screenshots of 01:08:40 and 01:12:39 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.....	xcvii
Figure 167. “Screenshots of 01:14:20, 01:15:28 and 01:18:16 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.....	xcvii
Figure 168. “Screenshots of 01:18:36, 01:20:09, 01:22:02, 01:25:49 and 01:26:04 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.	xcvii
Figure 169. “Screenshots of 01:28:11, 01:29:42 and 01:30:07 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.....	xcviii
Figure 170. “Screenshots of 01:34:19, 01:34:25, 01:35:41, 01:35:48 and 01:36:11 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.	xcviii
Figure 171. “Original poster,” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, Raya and the Last Dragon, 2021.	xcix

Figure 172. “Screenshots of 01:22:49, 01:11:15 and 00:59:36 (left to right),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.c

Figure 173. “Screenshots of 00:04:57, 00:08:47 and 00:13:20 (left to right),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.c

Figure 174. “Screenshots of 00:03:27, 00:04:52, 00:06:19, 00:16:05, 00:16:37 and 00:18:30 (left to right, top to bottom),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.c

Figure 175. “Screenshots of 00:22:10, 00:30:04, 00:30:26, 00:34:37, 00:47:17, 01:00:00, 01:00:21, 01:00:44, 01:19:28 and 01:20:56 (left to right, top to bottom),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.ci

Figure 176. “Screenshots of 00:05:38, 00:06:52, 00:28:07, 00:32:43, 00:34:54 and 01:24:08 (left to right, top to bottom),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.ci

Figure 177. “Screenshots of 00:08:54, 00:10:02, 00:38:49, 00:39:20, 00:51:02, 00:54:08, 00:54:37, 01:06:27 and 01:09:40 (left to right, top to bottom),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.cii

Figure 178. “Screenshots of 00:01:03, 00:04:08, 00:06:00, 00:06:55, 00:08:37, 00:30:08, 00:35:35, 00:50:25 and 00:53:51 (left to right, top to bottom),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.cii

Figure 179. “Screenshots of 00:58:39 and 01:05:38 (left to right),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.ciii

Figure 180. “Screenshots of 00:33:30, 00:34:02, 00:37:26, 00:58:35, 00:59:29 and 00:59:39 (left to right, top to bottom),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.ciii

Figure 181. “Screenshots of 00:04:38, 00:13:41 and 00:41:34 (left to right),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.ciii

Figure 182. “Screenshots of 00:44:47, 00:47:48, 00:48:07, 00:53:36, 00:57:57, 00:58:11, 01:14:33 and 01:22:36 (left to right, top to bottom),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.civ

Figure 183. “Screenshots of 00:19:21, 00:24:17, 00:28:24, 00:54:58, 01:10:14, 01:14:52 and 01:24:19 (left to right, top to bottom),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.civ

Figure 184. “Screenshots of 00:12:49, 00:13:52, 00:30:38 and 01:16:10 (left to right),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.cv

Figure 185. “Screenshots of 00:01:03 and 00:01:08 (left to right),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.cv

Figure 186. “Screenshots of 00:03:07, 00:04:06, 00:06:04, 00:06:52 and 00:07:22 (left to right, top to bottom),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.cv

Figure 187. “Screenshots of 00:09:52 and 00:10:26 (left to right),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.cvi

Figure 188. “Screenshots of 00:11:14, 00:12:22, 00:14:53 and 00:15:26 (left to right),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.cvi

Figure 189. “Screenshots of 00:15:43, 00:16:30, 00:17:39, 00:18:35, 00:19:17 and 00:19:32 (left to right, top to bottom),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.cvi

Figure 190. “Screenshots of 00:22:25, 00:24:17, 00:24:44, 00:25:56 and 00:28:22 (left to right, top to bottom),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.cvii

Figure 191. “Screenshots of 00:31:38, 00:32:53, 00:35:45 and 00:36:54 (left to right),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021. cviii

Figure 192. “Screenshots of 00:38:44, 00:43:32, 00:44:47, 00:45:12, 00:47:35, 00:48:48 and 00:50:23 (left to right, top to bottom),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021. cviii

Figure 193. “Screenshots of 00:53:44 and 00:54:07 (left to right),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021. cviii

Figure 194. “Screenshots of 00:57:57, 00:58:58, 00:59:31, 01:00:08, 01:00:33 and 01:00:44 (left to right, top to bottom),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021. cviii

Figure 195. “Screenshots of 01:01:07 and 01:01:42 (left to right),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021. cix

Figure 196. “Screenshots of 01:03:02, 01:03:41, 01:06:39, 01:09:31 and 01:11:00 (left to right, top to bottom),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021. cix

Figure 197. “Screenshots of 01:14:46, 01:15:58, 01:17:27 and 01:17:37 (left to right),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021. cix

Figure 198. “Screenshots of 01:18:51, 01:19:24, 01:20:40, 01:21:33, 01:21:52, 01:22:16 and 01:23:03 (left to right, top to bottom),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021. cx

Figure 199. “Screenshots of 01:23:44, 01:24:37, 01:24:56, 01:27:56, 01:31:15 and 01:31:47 (left to right, top to bottom),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021. cx

Figure 200. “Screenshots of 01:33:23, 01:34:21 and 01:34:40 (left to right),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021. cxi

1. Introduction

1.1. Self-positioning

No one is exempt from biases and blind spots, which are closely related to one's upbringing, experiences and privileges. I will thus position myself so that the reader can better assess the perspective from which this Bachelor's thesis has been elaborated: the author is a cisgender woman, 27 years old, white, bisexual, native speaker of Catalan and Spanish, with Spanish nationality, university-educated and without any disabilities.

1.2. Subject matter: Disney's hegemony and identity development

Stuart Hall describes hegemony as "a form of power based on leadership by a group in many fields of activity at once, so that its ascendancy commands widespread consent and appears natural and inevitable" (1997b, p. 259). The Walt Disney Company currently holds ownership of Pixar Animation Studios, Marvel Studios, Lucasfilm, 20th Century Studios, ABC broadcast network, Disney Channel, National Geographic, Disney+, Hulu, ESPN and several theme parks, resorts and cruise lines (The Walt Disney Company, 2020) – as a hegemonic conglomerate, it is almost impossible to evade. Even if the company has its origins and headquarters in the United States, its presence and impact are undeniably international (England et al., 2011, p. 555).

It is well established in the literature that portrayals present in the media, including visual media (such as television and film), influence children's beliefs and ideas about gender, race, social behaviours and norms. Several theories, such as the Social Cognitive Theory (Bussey & Bandura, 1999) and the Identity Theory (Hogg et al., 1995) propose that environmental models (such as parents, peers or characters from films) help to transmit and teach gender norms and stereotypes to young children. The Gender Schema Theory (Graves, 1999; Martin et al., 2002), suggests that children internalize their environmental observations and experiences into cognitive frameworks or schemas, which then guide their behaviour. Cultivation theory (Gerbner et al., 2022) identifies visual media as a particularly important mechanism for the development of concepts regarding social behaviour and norms. In simple terms, consistently portrayed gender and race images may be interpreted by children as "normal and natural", which in turn informs the development of their own identities as well as the identities of others around them.

Taking into account Disney's status as a hegemonic cultural institution together with the influence that portrayals in visual media have on children's identity development, it can be stated that films by Walt Disney Animation Studios operate as an important socializing agent for children all over the world. As Jessica L. Laemle writes (2018, p. 12):

It is difficult to escape Disney's influence on society. Under the Disney business model, any culture or message can be sold if it is mass-produced and marketed properly. Since "the films Walt Disney produces are specifically targeted at young impressionable children, it is important that we continue to deconstruct the messages" (Matyas, 2010, p. 42) and "question the values that Disney teaches and hold it accountable for the ways it attempts to shape children's identities" (Wormer & Juby, 2016, p. 579).

Furthermore, at some point children mature into adults, who may occupy positions of power. If no work of deconstruction and reflection has taken place, the constructs internalized in childhood about gender and race continue to shape one's own identity as well as the schemas and scripts one has of other people. Taking the field of Social Work as an example: since social workers are in contact with marginalized communities, it is important that they have reflected on and deconstructed internalized stereotypes so as not to reproduce patterns of oppression in the interaction with their clients.

1.3. State of the art: Representation of non-white female Disney main characters

In 1937, Walt Disney Productions (forerunner of present-day Walt Disney Animation Studios) released *Snow White and the Seven Dwarfs*, featuring Disney's first female main character, Snow White. It would be 55 years and seven more white female main characters before Disney's first non-white female main character, Jasmine from *Aladdin* (1992), saw the light of the world. In the following two decades, Walt Disney Animation Studios consistently released films featuring non-white female main characters: *Pocahontas* in 1995, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame* featuring Esmeralda in 1996, *Mulan* in 1998, *Atlantis. The Lost Empire* featuring Kida in 2001, *Lilo & Stitch* featuring Lilo in 2002, *The Princess and the Frog* featuring Tiana in 2009, *Moana* in 2016, *Raya and the Last Dragon* featuring Raya in 2022 and *Encanto* featuring Mirabel also in 2022.

While the catalogue of non-white female main characters is now more diverse than ever, it is important to point out that “the mere presence of any group or person does not mean that a group or person participates equally, enjoys the same privileges, or exercise the same degree of power” (Breux, 2010, p. 400). Representation in itself is not everything – the portrayal of non-white female characters in disfiguring roles can be as damaging as its complete absence. Therefore, it is important to analyse the representation that is taking place in these films and assess if it is beneficial or actually detrimental.

Extensive research has been conducted on female Disney main characters (primarily on the so-called “Disney Princesses”¹), their portrayal and their impact on children (Muir, 2022; Rogers, 2019; Uppal, 2019; Hine et al., 2018; Koushik & Reed, 2018; Laemle, 2018; Pehlke, 2018; Coyne et al., 2016; Johnson, 2015; Davis, 2014; Baker-Sperry, 2007; Do Rozario, 2004). Fewer works address specifically the representation of non-white female Disney main characters (Hoffmann, 2019; Anjirbag, 2018; Armstrong, 2018; Perea, 2018; Dundes & Streiff, 2016; Schwob, 2013; Breux, 2010) and most of them focus on one, two or at most three characters at a time.

The author believes that analysing the representation of non-white female main characters is especially interesting because they lie at precisely the intersection between the “race” and “gender” dimensions. Moreover, it would be highly valuable to analyse each and every character, from 1937 to 2022, since this would allow us to get a complete picture and assess the evolution of the representation of such figures over a timespan of three decades.

1.4. Research questions

The main question sought to be answered in this Bachelor’s thesis is how non-white female Disney main characters are represented, focusing on the dimensions of “race” and “gender”.

The secondary questions are:

- Is there an evolution in the representation of these characters?
- If so, are there any phases or turning points in this evolution?
- What might the representation of non-white female Disney main characters look like in the coming years?

¹ See section 2.5.1. *Disney princesses and “Disney Princesses”* to clarify the difference between a Disney princess and a “Disney Princess”.

1.5. Structure of the thesis

The first section of this Bachelor's thesis is the theoretical and historical reflection. The first part is dedicated to the "racial" dimension based on three works by Stuart Hall: *Race, the Floating Signifier* (1997a), *The Spectacle of the Other* (1997b) and *The West and the Rest: Discourse and Power* (1992). The second part is dedicated to the "gender" dimension based on *Gender Trouble* (1999) by Judith Butler. The third part is dedicated to "intersectionality", using the work *Intersectionality 101* (2014) by Olena Hankivsky as the main source. The fourth part is the history and current relevance of The Walt Disney Company in the world of entertainment. The fifth and last part is dedicated to the concept of the Disney princess, its distinction from the "Disney Princess" and the eras in which they are classified according to the literature.

The second section is dedicated to the method used in this Bachelor's thesis, which is adapted from the "film and television analysis" by Lothar Mikos (2017, pp. 515–523). The first step is the formation of the analysis corpus, in which the Walt Disney Animation Studios filmography is filtered using an exclusion algorithm in order to identify all the Disney films with a non-white female main character. The second step is the determination of aids and appliances to perform the data collection. The third step is the data collection itself, in which thousands of screenshots and quotes are collected as the foundation of this thesis. The fourth step is the description of the database, in which preliminary information about the screen presence of the characters is gathered. The fifth and last step is the analysis of the data on the basis of the screenshots; due to time and space constraints, only seven characters were selected to undergo this in-depth examination.

The third section consists of the compilations of the analyses of the seven selected characters; for each character, several pages of information were condensed into a page or page and a half. These summaries include highlights of the character's physique and psychology, expand on their most relevant actions, delve into their representation from a "race" and "gender" standpoint and infer their motivation and character arc.

The fourth section is the discussion of the evolution of the representation of these characters. The seven compilations are further condensed into a single table, the representation of the "race" and "gender" dimensions is comparatively explored, the phases in the representation of non-white female Disney main characters are delineated and future trends are speculated. The last sections are the limitations and the conclusion.

Following the main body of text and completing this Bachelor's thesis, the *Appendix I* includes the detailed breakdowns of the analysed characters (including background information about the film, physical descriptions, psychological traits and a scene-by-scene analysis of the character's actions) and the *Appendix II* includes a timeline of all the white female, non-white male and non-white female main characters from Walt Disney Animation Studios, as well as the eras from the literature and the phases identified in this Bachelor's thesis.

It is important to remark that terms that are strongly racially charged, such as "~~harem~~" and "~~gypsy~~", will appear stricken. This practice was taken from the work *Racism against Rom*nja and Sinti*zze* by Isidora Randjelović (2019) and from the exhibition "zurückgeschaut | looking back. The First German Colonial Exhibition of 1896 in Berlin-Treptow" at the Museum Treptow in Berlin, Germany. The author deems this to be an appropriate way to use terms that appear in the discussed films without reproducing them unquestioningly.

2. Theoretical and historical reflection

2.1. Race

For this section on the “race” dimension, I will draw on the author Stuart Hall and his works *Race, the Floating Signifier* (1997a), *The Spectacle of the Other* (1997b) and *The West and the Rest: Discourse and Power* (1992). The first work will provide us with an introduction to the discursive approach to race; the second paper will allow us to compile a glossary of manifestations in racialized discourse, and the third paper will introduce us to key themes in the discourse of “the West and the Rest” as well as the figure of the “noble savage”.

Stuart Henry McPhail Hall was a Jamaican-British academic, writer and cultural studies pioneer. He was born in Kingston, Jamaica in 1932 and died in London, Great Britain aged 82 in 2014 (Stuart Hall Foundation, 2023). He was a Marxist sociologist, cultural theorist and political activist, as well as one of the founding figures of the school of thought that is now known as “British Cultural Studies” or the “Birmingham School of Cultural Studies” (Procter, 2004).

2.1.1. *Race, the Floating Signifier* (1997a)

In his lecture *Race, the Floating Signifier*, Stuart Hall (1997a) defines “race” as a discursive category or as “one of those major concepts, which organize the great classificatory systems of difference, which operate in human society” (p. 6). He argues that racialized behaviour and difference should be understood as a language, instead of a genetic or biological fact (p. 8):

(...) the argument that I want to make to you is that race works like a language. And signifiers refer to the systems and concepts of the classification of a culture to its making meaning practices. And those things gain their meaning, not because of what they contain in their essence, but in the shifting relations of difference, which they establish with other concepts and ideas in a signifying field. Their meaning, because it is relational, and not essential, can never be finally fixed, but is subject to the constant process of redefinition and appropriation. To the losing of old meanings, and the appropriation and collection on contracting new ones, to the endless process of being constantly re-signified, made to mean something different in different cultures, in different historical formations, at different moments of time. The meaning of a signifier can never be finally or trans-historically fixed.

To sum up the discursive concept of race: reality is diverse and there exist all kinds of differences (for example of “hair, colour and bone”); only when these differences (and the people carrying them) get organised within a language or discourse (of different social groups)

do they acquire meaning, become a factor in human culture and thus regulate conduct. One of the most poignant affirmations of this lecture is that the “body is a text” and that each and every person is a reader of it, a reader of race, a reader of social difference (p. 15).

2.1.2. *The Spectacle of the Other* (1997b)

Scattered throughout the text *The Spectacle of the Other* (Hall, 1997b) are definitions of concepts closely related to the racialised discourse: binary opposition, naturalisation, stereotyping, orientalism, fetishism and voyeurism. Below are the definitions of these concepts:

- *Binary oppositions* structure the racialised discourse: white/black, civilisation/savagery, culture/nature, racial purity/pollution. On the one hand, whiteness is linked to intellectual development: refinement, learning and knowledge, a belief in reason, the presence of developed institutions, formal government and law and a “civilized restraint” in the emotional, sexual and civil life. On the other hand, blackness is linked to instinct: the open expression of emotion and feeling rather than intellect, a lack of “civilized refinement” in sexual and social life, a reliance on custom and ritual and the lack of developed civil institutions (p. 243). These binaries do not peacefully coexist but rather exist in a violent hierarchy, one of them exerting power over the other.
- *Naturalisation* is the process through which the cultures of a group of people are reduced to nature, thus making them permanent, fixed and beyond history. This representational strategy intends to fix and secure difference, avoiding a slide of meaning that might bring about a change in discourse or ideology (p. 245).
- *Stereotyping* is defined as reducing people to a few, simple, essential characteristics, which are represented as fixed by nature. Stereotypes get hold of the few “simple, vivid, memorable, easily grasped and widely recognized” characteristics about a person, reduce everything about the person to those traits, exaggerate and simplify them, and fix them ruling out change or development (pp. 257–258). An important aspect of stereotyping is that it divides the normal and the abnormal, the acceptable and the unacceptable, and then excludes everything that does not belong. Another important aspect is that it tends to occur where there are gross inequalities of power, usually directed against the excluded group.
- *Orientalism* is a concept created by Edward Said (1978) and describes the way in which Europe constructed a stereotypical image of “the Orient”. It is the discourse “by which European culture was able to manage –and even produce– the Orient politically, sociologically, militarily, ideologically, scientifically and imaginatively during the post-

Enlightenment period”, nested in the framework of western hegemony over the Orient (p. 259).

- *Fetishism* consists in the substitution of a part for the whole, of a thing (for example an object, an organ, a portion of the body) for a subject. It is a representational practice that turns a person into an object (p. 266). Fetishism also enables *voyeurism*, or the unacknowledged search for illicit pleasure through the act of looking (p. 268).

2.1.3. *The West and the Rest: Discourse and Power (1992)*

In *The West and the Rest: Discourse and Power*, Hall (1992) identifies a series of key themes in the construction of the idea of “the West and the Rest”, with the former being regarded as developed, industrialized, urbanized, capitalist, secular and modern “western societies” (for example Western Europe, the United States and Japan), and the latter being regarded as non-industrial, rural, agricultural and under-developed “non-western societies” (for example the Middle East, the Far East, Africa, Latin America, indigenous North America and Australasia). These five key themes are (p. 300):

- 1 the Golden World; an Earthly Paradise;
- 2 the simple, innocent life;
- 3 the lack of developed social organization and civil society;
- 4 people living in a pure state of Nature;
- 5 the frank and open sexuality; the nakedness; the beauty of the women.

Moreover, Hall documents the emergence and evolution of the figure of the “noble savage” (pp. 310–311):

The famous painting of “The Different Nations of America” by Le Brun in Louis XIV's (1638-1715) Versailles Palace was dominated by a “heroic” representation of an American Indian – grave, tall, proud, independent, statuesque, and naked (see Honour, 1978, p. 118). Paintings and engravings of American Indians dressed like ancient Greeks or Romans became popular. (...) “Heroic savages” have peopled adventure stories, Westerns, and other Hollywood and television films ever since, generating an unending series of images of “the Noble Other.” The “noble savage” also acquired sociological status. In 1749, the French philosopher Rousseau produced an account of his ideal form of society: simple, unsophisticated man living in a state of Nature, unfettered by laws, government, property, or social divisions. “The savages of North America,”

he later said in *The Social Contract*, “still retain today this method of government, and they are very well governed” (Rousseau, 1968, p. 114).

With the passage of time, the “noble savage” also became “the vehicle for a wide-ranging critique of the over-refinement, religious hypocrisy, and divisions by social rank that existed in the West” (p. 311).

2.2. Gender

For this section on the “gender” dimension, I will draw on the author Judith Butler and their work *Gender Trouble* (1999). The main ideas to be highlighted are the distinction between sex and gender, the heterosexual matrix, the prohibitive and generative effects of power and the performativity of gender.

Judith Pamela Butler is an American academic and philosopher. They were born in Cleveland, Ohio, United States in 1956. They are known because of their theories of the performative nature of gender and sex, which were influential within Francocentric philosophy, cultural theory, queer theory and some schools of philosophical feminism from the late 20th century (Duignan, 2023).

2.2.1. Distinction sex-gender

Judith Butler (1999) initially presents us with the distinction between sex and gender: the former is supposed to have a biological basis and be determined, whereas the latter is thought to be a cultural construct and thus more malleable (pp. 9–10):

Originally intended to dispute the biology-is-destiny formulation, the distinction between sex and gender serves the argument that whatever biological intractability sex appears to have, gender is culturally constructed: hence, gender is neither the causal result of sex nor as seemingly fixed as sex.

However, the author makes the argument that “sex” might actually be as culturally constructed as “gender”, which would have the consequence “that the distinction between sex and gender turns out to be no distinction at all” (pp. 10–11). They deny that “sex” and “gender” are parallel to “nature” and “culture”, but rather that the concept of “gender” generates the concept of “sex” and establishes it as “prior to culture, a politically neutral surface on which culture acts” (p. 11).

2.2.2. Heterosexual matrix

Another important concept from *Gender Trouble* (Butler, 1999) is the so-called “heterosexual matrix”, an unspoken norm of sorts that poses itself as natural and original. In simple words, this framework states that humanity is divided into men and women; that men ought to be masculine and women ought to be feminine, and that men ought to be attracted to women and vice versa.

Consequently, any person that fails to fall into the binary (see intersex people), any person that does not perform their assigned gender (see trans people) or any person who fails to be attracted exclusively to the other gender (see asexual, homosexual or bisexual people) is deemed “unnatural”.

2.2.3. Prohibitive and generative effects of power

A concern in *Gender Trouble* (Butler, 1999) are the prohibitive and generative effects of power and the consequences they have for feminism. They argue that any construction, even if elaborated for emancipatory purposes, has coercive and regulatory effects (p. 7). This would be true for the construct of “woman”, which feminism elaborates as universal, unitary and stable for the purposes of liberation; however, this construct is in turn limiting and excluding, and is met with refusal by some collectives. The key idea is that every time that we are defining or representing something, we are at the same time constraining it.

The same is true in the case of repression. Every time something is forbidden, it is at the same time being created. As Judith Butler writes (p. 119):

As Foucault makes clear, the culturally contradictory enterprise of the mechanism of repression is prohibitive and generative at once and makes the problematic of “liberation” especially acute. The female body that is freed from the shackles of the paternal law may well prove to be yet another incarnation of that law, posing as subversive but operating in the service of that law’s self-amplification and proliferation. In order to avoid the emancipation of the oppressor in the name of the oppressed, it is necessary to take into account the full complexity and subtlety of the law and to cure ourselves of the illusion of a true body beyond the law. If subversion is possible, it will be a subversion from within the terms of the law, through the possibilities that emerge when the law turns against itself and spawns unexpected permutations of itself. The culturally constructed body will then be liberated, neither to its “natural” past, nor to its original pleasures, but to an open future of cultural possibilities.

In other words: we live immersed in a so-called “cis-heteropatriarchy”, a sociopolitical system of power where cis-straight men are positioned as superior and “normal” against all other forms of gender identity, gender expression and sexual orientation. If we want to free ourselves from this system, we have to be careful not to inadvertently appropriate its very mechanisms; for example, by having cis-straight women occupy positions of power while still oppressing any other gender identity, gender expression and sexual orientation, or by having women purportedly emancipate themselves by hypersexualising themselves and playing into the roles and fantasies stemming precisely from cis-heteropatriarchy.

Judith Butler defends that “power can be neither withdrawn nor refused, but only redeployed” (p. 158). What this means for the liberation of oppressed communities is that they must find strategies of subversion and parody within the current system as a means to destabilise it, instead of trying to fully transcend it and establish a completely different system of power.

2.2.4. Performativity of gender

The last and main idea from *Gender Trouble* (Butler, 1999) is the performativity of gender. Judith Butler writes: “There is no gender identity behind the expressions of gender; that identity is performatively constituted by the very “expressions” that are said to be its results” (p. 33). They describe “gender” as “the repeated stylization of the body, a set of repeated acts within a highly rigid regulatory frame that congeal over time to produce the appearance of substance, of a natural sort of being” (pp. 43–44).

In simple words: gender expression is usually interpreted as being the effect of gender identity, thus having the “inside” (identity) precede and cause the “outside” (expression). The author argues that, in reality, the “outside” is what causes the illusion that there is an “inside”: certain repeated acts and gestures, interpreted through the frame of gender, make us believe that there is an internal essence, when in fact there is nothing but these acts themselves. This illusion of gender as identification serves an important role within the heterosexual matrix (p. 178):

Discrete genders are part of what “humanizes” individuals within contemporary culture; indeed, we regularly punish those who fail to do their gender right. Because there is neither an “essence” that gender expresses or externalizes nor an objective ideal to which gender aspires, and because gender is not a fact, the various acts of gender create the idea of gender, and without those acts, there would be no gender at all. Gender is, thus, a construction that regularly conceals its genesis; the tacit collective agreement to perform, produce, and sustain discrete and polar genders as cultural fictions is obscured by the credibility of those productions— and the punishments that

attend not agreeing to believe in them; the construction “compels” our belief in its necessity and naturalness.

2.3. Intersectionality

The Disney main characters to be analysed were chosen specifically because they lie at the intersection between “race” and “gender”. The characters that form the analysis corpus are both female and non-white (concretely Arabic, Native American, Romani, Chinese, “Atlantean”, Native Hawaiian, African-American, Polynesian, Southeast Asian and Latina).

According to Olena Hankivsky (2014), the term “intersectionality” was coined in 1989 by American critical legal race scholar Kimberlé Williams Crenshaw. Nevertheless, this concept can be traced further back (p. 2):

(...) the central ideas of intersectionality have long historic roots within and beyond the United States. Black activists and feminists, as well as Latina, post-colonial, queer and Indigenous scholars have all produced work that reveals the complex factors and processes that shape human lives (Bunjun, 2010; Collins, 1990; Valdes, 1997; Van Herk, Smith, & Andrew, 2011).

Intersectionality has been defined in various ways and interpreted as a theory, a methodology, a paradigm, a lens or also a framework. However, the key idea is the following (p. 2):

Intersectionality promotes an understanding of human beings as shaped by the interaction of different social locations (e.g., ‘race’/ethnicity, Indigeneity, gender, class, sexuality, geography, age, disability/ability, migration status, religion). These interactions occur within a context of connected systems and structures of power (e.g., laws, policies, state governments and other political and economic unions, religious institutions, media). Through such processes, interdependent forms of privilege and oppression shaped by colonialism, imperialism, racism, homophobia, ableism and patriarchy are created.

In simple words, intersectionality creates the framework to become aware of the fact that inequalities do not arise from isolated, distinct and mutually exclusive factors, but from the combination of categories such as “race”, “gender”, “class”, “age” ... It is also crucial to note that the resulting oppression is more than the simple addition of the individual effects. Different authors have tried to transport this through several metaphors, such as (p. 4):

(...) a traffic intersection that depicts intersecting roads of oppression (Crenshaw, 2003), the final product resulting from blending baking ingredients that, like the factors going into lived experience, are blended together into batter (Bowleg, 2013); the rich, complex and historically shaped topography of the Grand Canyon (Crenshaw, 2010); the dynamic reflections in a kaleidoscope (Easteal, 2002); the interconnected swirls of a marble cake (Jordan-Zachery, 2007); and the unique, compound nature of a fly's eye, which is made up of thousands of individual lenses (Weber, 2007).

Intersectionality has seven principles (Hankivsky, 2014, p. 8):

1. *Intersecting categories*: as already stated, intersectionality “conceptualizes social categories as interacting with and co-constituting one another to create unique social locations that vary according to time and place” (p. 9). Single social categories are not enough to explain human experience and, as already stated, the impact of different categories is not the simple sum of their individual effects.
2. *Multi-level analysis*: inequity and its effects can be analysed on the macro-level (global and national-level institutions and policies), meso-level (provincial and regional-level institutions and policies) and micro-level (community-level, grassroots institutions and policies as well as the individual or “self”).
3. *Power*: three aspects of power are highlighted, namely that “i) power operates at discursive and structural levels to exclude some types of knowledge and experience (Foucault, 1977); ii) power shapes subject positions and categories (e.g., ‘race’) (e.g. racialization and racism); and iii) these processes operate together to shape experiences of privilege and penalty between groups and within them (Collins, 2000)” (p. 9). A person can experience both power and oppression simultaneously, depending on the context or time.
4. *Reflexivity*: researchers, policy makers and stakeholders should practice critical self-awareness, role-awareness, interrogation of power and privilege as well as question assumptions and “truths”. This helps people become aware that there exist multiple truths and a diversity of perspectives, and give extra space to voices typically marginalised or excluded from policy “expert” roles.
5. *Time and space*: our social location conditions our interpretations, senses and feelings, which in turn influence our experience of time and space. Therefore, these dimensions are not static, fixed or objective but rather fluid and changeable. In addition, privileges and oppressions also change over time and place.

6. *Diverse knowledge*: power favours certain knowledge traditions and excludes others. It is important to include the perspectives and worldviews of people who are typically marginalized in the production of knowledge, recognizing a diversity of knowledge, paradigms and theoretical perspectives, such as knowledge generated from qualitative or quantitative research, empirical or interpretive data and Indigenous knowledges.
7. *Social justice and equity*: social justice is described as being about “transforming the way resources and relationships are produced and distributed so that all can live dignified lives in a way that is ecologically sustainable” (Potts & Brown, 2005, p. 284). Equity in public policy exists when social systems are designed to equalize outcomes between more and less advantaged groups (Braveman & Gruskin, 2003). Both social justice and equity are strongly emphasised in intersectionality.

2.4. The Walt Disney Company

The Walt Disney Company (also known as The Disney Company or Walt Disney Productions, and formerly known as Walt Disney Productions) is an American corporation best known as a purveyor of family entertainment (Luebering, 2023). It is currently one of the world’s largest media conglomerates, with holdings such as ABC, ESPN, Pixar, Marvel Entertainment and 20th Century Studios. The Walt Disney Company Disney currently has its headquarters in Burbank, California.

2.4.1. The early years: Laugh-O-gram Films, Mickey Mouse and *Steamboat Willie* (1920–1928)

The company was founded by animator, film producer and entrepreneur Walt Disney. In 1920, he began his career with the Kansas City Film Ad Company in Missouri. In 1922, Disney and his friend animator Ub Iwerks founded the Laugh-O-gram Films studio in Kansas City and began producing a series of cartoons based on fables and fairytales. Their first film was the short film *Alice in Cartoonland* (1923), combining both live action and animation. Within weeks of its completion, however, Walt Disney filed for bankruptcy and left Kansas City to establish himself in Hollywood. When *Alice in Cartoonland* turned out to be a surprising sensation, Walt Disney reopened the Laugh-O-gram Films studio in Hollywood with the help of his brother Roy Disney, who became his lifelong business partner. The Laugh-O-gram Films studio created the character of Mickey Mouse and in 1928 they released *Steamboat Willie*, which was the first animated cartoon that employed the use of synchronized sound and an immediate success.

2.4.2. Renaming to Walt Disney Productions and *Snow White and the Seven Dwarfs* (1929–1949)

In 1929, the company was renamed to Walt Disney Productions and continued producing cartoons featuring Mickey Mouse (together with new characters such as Donald Duck, Pluto and Goofy) and his as well as the *Silly Symphonies* series. The most notable *Silly Symphonies* cartoons are *Flowers and Trees* (1932) and *The Three Little Pigs* (1933), both of which were awarded an Academy Award.

In 1934, Walt Disney started the production of *Snow White and the Seven Dwarfs*, a bold financial move for the company. The feature-length animated cartoon was finished in 1937 and received widespread acclaim. The studio went on to releasing *Pinocchio* (1940), *Fantasia* (1940), *Dumbo* (1941) and *Bambi* (1942). Due to an attempt at unionizing on the side of the animators, followed by months of organizing and negotiating with Walt Disney, many of the studio's top animators were fired in 1941 and hundreds of the remaining workers went on strike. Walt Disney Productions began focusing on short cartoons, nature documentaries and features that combined live action and animation such as *The Three Caballeros* (1945) and *Song of the South* (1946). Although the company also released feature-length cartoons such as *Cinderella* (1950), *Alice in Wonderland* (1951), *Peter Pan* (1953) and *Lady and the Tramp* (1955), its attention was centred on live-action features, television productions and his new theme park, Disneyland, which opened in 1955 in Anaheim, California. At that time, in order to ensure complete control over his films and their marketing, Walt Disney established the distribution company Buena Vista Productions.

2.4.3. *Mary Poppins*, death of Walt Disney and decline of the company (1950–1989)

In the 1950s and 1960s, Walt Disney Productions produced hit television shows such as *The Mickey Mouse Club*, *Zorro* and *Walt Disney Presents*, as well as animated features such as *Sleeping Beauty* (1959), *One Hundred and One Dalmatians* (1961) and *Winnie the Pooh and the Honey Tree* (1965). However, the greatest success at that time was the live-action film *Mary Poppins* (1964), which won five Academy Awards, including a best actress Oscar for Julie Andrews, and was nominated in eight additional categories.

On 15th December 1966, Walt Disney passed away from lung cancer, at a time where the studios were in a critical financial moment. Thanks to enterprises he had planned before his death, the company was able to stay afloat. The dire financial state of Walt Disney Productions can be explained with Walt Disney's approach to business and filmmaking – he is often credited with

saying: “I don’t make movies to make money, I make money so I can make more movies” (Luebering, 2023).

In 1971, and thanks to the supervision of his brother Roy Disney, the company was able to open the Walt Disney World Resort in Florida with great success. That same year, Roy Disney also passed away. In the following two decades, however, Walt Disney Productions was unable to produce successful animated features and earned most of its profits from the distribution of old films and from Disney World. In 1983, the Disney Channel was launched, intending to be a premium channel catered to children and teenagers during the day and families in the evening (Carillo et al., 2012). In 1986, Walt Disney Productions was renamed to The Walt Disney Company.

2.4.4. The Disney Renaissance and expansion (1990–present)

The landmark that initiated the so-called “Disney Renaissance” was the release of *The Little Mermaid* (1989), which was regarded as the company’s best animated feature in more than 40 years. The film was followed by more commercial hits such as *Beauty and the Beast* (1991), *Aladdin* (1992), *The Lion King* (1994), *The Hunchback of Notre Dame* (1996) and *Fantasia 2000* (1999). The successful releases of *Toy Story* (1995) and *Toy Story 2* (1999), both developed and produced together with Pixar Animation Studios, proved the potential of computerized animation. Another great success was the live-action feature *101 Dalmatians* (1996), a remake of Disney’s animated feature from 1961.

The Walt Disney Company opened new theme parks in Paris, Tokyo, Shanghai and Hong Kong. On 30th July 1998, the first ship in the Disney Cruise Line was launched, offering vacation packages to the Caribbean islands. The Walt Disney Company also expanded broadcasting interests with the ABC network, the ESPN sports cable network and Radio Disney, all of which were added to the long-running Disney Channel cable network. The Walt Disney Company also expanded into Broadway musicals: stage adaptations of the animated features *Beauty and the Beast* and *The Lion King* premiered with great success in 1994 and 1997, respectively.

Pirates of the Caribbean: The Curse of the Black Pearl (2003) increased the popularity of live-action films by The Walt Disney Company, scoring huge numbers at the box office and launching a franchise that would make great revenue worldwide. Computer animation also gained popularity and films produced in partnership with Pixar Animation Studios, such as *Finding Nemo* (2003), *Ratatouille* (2007), *WALL·E* (2008), *Up* (2009), *Toy Story 3* (2010), *Inside Out* (2015), *Coco* (2017), *Toy Story 4* (2019) and *Soul* (2020), won Academy Awards for best animated film. Computer-animated films produced solely by The Walt Disney

Company, such as *Tangled* (2010), *Wreck-It Ralph* (2012), *Frozen* (2013) and *Encanto* (2021), were also a success. To this day, The Walt Disney Company has continued producing numerous live-action films based on its animated classics, such as *Alice in Wonderland* (2010), *Cinderella* (2015), *Beauty and the Beast* (2017), *Aladdin* (2019), *Mulan* (2020), *Cruella* (2021) and *Peter Pan and Wendy* (2023).

The Walt Disney Company acquired Pixar for \$7.400 million in 2006, Marvel Entertainment (owner of the Marvel Cinematic Universe) for \$4.000 million in 2009, Lucasfilm Ltd. from film-maker George Lucas (owner of the Star Wars franchise) for approximately \$4.000 million in 2012 and most of the holdings of 21st Century Fox (including the film studio 20th Century Fox and streaming service Hulu) for approximately \$71.000 million in 2019. Also in 2019, The Walt Disney Company started Disney+, a subscription video streaming service that collected all of the company's film and television franchises on a single platform.

2.4.5. Current relevance of The Walt Disney Company

According to its website, "The Walt Disney Company, together with its subsidiaries and affiliates, is a leading diversified international family entertainment and media enterprise that includes three core business segments: Disney Entertainment, ESPN, and Disney Parks, Experiences and Products" (The Walt Disney Company, 2020).

- Disney Entertainment operates the entertainment media and content businesses and includes: The Walt Disney Studios, Walt Disney Animation Studios, Pixar Animation Studios, Marvel Studios, Lucasfilm, Disney Theatrical Group, 20th Century Studios, Searchlight Pictures, 20th Television, ABC Entertainment, ABC News, ABC Signature, ABC Owned Television Stations, Disney Branded Television, Freeform, FX Networks, Hulu Originals, National Geographic, Disney+, Hulu, Hotstar and Disney Music Group.
- ESPN includes ESPN networks, ESPN+, and the company's international sports channels.
- Disney Parks, Experiences and Products manages the theme parks and resorts, cruise and vacation experiences and consumer products (for example toys, apparel, books and video games), and includes: Disneyland Resort, Walt Disney World, Shanghai Disney Resort, Disneyland Paris, Tokyo Disney Resort, Hong Kong Disneyland, Disney Cruise Line, Disney Vacation Club, Aulani, Adventures by Disney, Walt Disney Imagineering, Disney Publishing Worldwide and Disney Store.

According to its latest annual financial report, The Walt Disney Company had an annual net income for 2022 of \$3.145 billion, an increase of 58% over 2021 (2023, p. 31).

Through a combination of careful marketing, brand acquisitions, digital positioning in the form of the Disney+ streaming service and undeniably popular content, The Walt Disney Company has achieved enormous cultural and economic relevance and might be on its way to inevitable, permanent and total Disney cultural dominance (Pitre, 2022).

2.5. The Disney Princess

2.5.1. Disney princesses and “Disney Princesses”

It is important to make a distinction between a Disney princess and a “Disney Princess”². While a Disney princess is a female character from a Disney film who is the consort of a prince or the daughter of a monarch, a “Disney Princess” is a character in the media franchise created by Disney Consumer Products President Andy Mooney in the year 2000. In an interview with Peggy Orenstein (2006), Andy Mooney described the moment in which he had the idea for the “Disney Princess” franchise, while he was in Phoenix to see his first “Disney on Ice” show:

“Standing in line in the arena, I was surrounded by little girls dressed head to toe as princesses (...) They weren’t even Disney products. They were generic princess products they’d appended to a Halloween costume. And the light bulb went off. Clearly there was latent demand here. So the next morning I said to my team, ‘O.K., let’s establish standards and a color palette and talk to licensees and get as much product out there as we possibly can that allows these girls to do what they’re doing anyway: projecting themselves into the characters from the classic movies.’”

Andy Mooney then selected the original line-up of the “Disney Princess” franchise, the so-called “Classic Princesses” or “Original Eight Princesses”: Snow White, Cinderella, Aurora, Ariel, Belle, Jasmine, Pocahontas and Mulan. It is noteworthy that the characters of Tinker Bell and Esmeralda were once part of the line-up but were later removed from it: Tinker Bell so that she could lead her own franchise as a Disney fairy, and Esmeralda due to not being marketable enough (Tyler, 2021). The franchise currently contains thirteen characters: Snow White, Cinderella, Aurora, Ariel, Belle, Jasmine, Pocahontas, Mulan, Tiana, Rapunzel, Merida, Moana and Raya. These are known as the “New Generation of Princesses”.

² To make it easier to distinguish between the two terms, one will be written with quotation marks and capitalised and the other without.

Therefore, we can see that not all “Disney Princesses” are princesses in the strict sense: Pocahontas and Moana are the daughters of a Native American and a Polynesian chief respectively, and Mulan is not royalty whether by birth nor by marriage. In addition, not all “Disney Princesses” are uniquely from Disney, since Merida from *Brave* (2012) is featured in a film by Pixar Animation Studios. We can also see that some Disney princesses, such as Princess Eilonwy from *The Black Cauldron* (1985), Kida from *Atlantis: The Lost Empire* (2001) or Anna and Elsa from *Frozen* (2013), are not actually “Disney Princesses”.

The author Megan Condis (2013, p. 27) notes that “while membership in the Disney Princess franchise has its perks, those perks are not the same for all members. On the contrary, the diversity of the line is the mechanism that allows for the differentiation of a white model of princesshood from a racialized model.” The author argues that the presence of non-white princesses like Jasmine, Pocahontas, Mulan and Tiana actually crystallise the standards that define white femininity, tracing a line between traditional (white) princesshood and “alternative” (non-white) models.

2.5.2. The three eras of Disney princesses

Several authors (Menise, 2019; Hine et al., 2018; Johnson, 2015; England et al., 2011; Davis, 2006) suggest the classification of Disney princesses in three eras: the “Classic Years” (1937–1967), the “Eisner Era” (1967–2005) and the “Modern Era” (2005–present).

2.5.2.1. The “Classic Years” (1937–1967)

The three “Classic Years” princesses are Snow White from *Snow White and the Seven Dwarfs* (1937), Cinderella from the homonymous film (1950) and Aurora from *Sleeping Beauty* (1959). According to England et al. (2011, p. 562), these princesses are “frequently affectionate, helpful, troublesome, fearful, tentative and described as pretty.” According to Johnson (2015, p. 2), they “encapsulate submissiveness, traditional female gender roles, and stereotypical beauty”, and perpetuate stereotypical gender norms by being thin, graceful, young, submissive and attractive to romantic suitors of the opposite sex. Hine et al. (2018, p. 3) point out to happiness found through marriage and passivity as core traits from the “Classic Years” princesses. Rogers (2019, p. 24) describes the traditional Disney princess as “very petite, with an hourglass figure and wide eyes. She is almost always in a nice dress, white, young, heterosexual, rich, and demure, with a naïve and reserved personality who always knows her true love as soon as she meets him. Her main goal is a happy ending with her prince, who almost always saves her from some evil in the world.”

2.5.2.1. The “Eisner Era” (1967–2005)

The main “Eisner Era” princesses are Ariel from *The Little Mermaid* (1989), Belle from *Beauty and the Beast* (1991), Jasmine from *Aladdin* (1992), Pocahontas from the homonymous film (1995) and Mulan from the homonymous film (1998)³. Less popular characters that might also be included in this era are Esmeralda from *The Hunchback of Notre Dame* (1996), Meg from *Hercules* (1997), Jane from *Tarzan* (1999) and Kida from *Atlantis. The Lost Empire* (2001).

Menise (2019, p. 536) defines these characters as being “much more active and rebellious than the protagonists from the classic era”. According to England et al. (2011, p. 563), these princesses participate “in stereotypically masculine activities, such as conducting diplomacy and war”; however, plot resolutions reflect “traditionally valued outcomes for women, such as the princess being paired with the prince and choosing to return to family life rather than pursuing novel opportunities.” The authors also point out that, although the films show a more balanced portrayal of relationship formation, “a heterosexual romance is inevitable and often a central conclusion of the movie.”

Johnson (2015, p. 3) describes the “Eisner Era” princesses as being “more egalitarian, heroic, and athletic, showing progress that they transform with the corresponding societal shifts.” However, the author notes that these characters “still possess timeless beauty and have become more sexualized”, dressing more provocatively and still finding true love in the end with a prince. Hine et al. (2018, p. 3) point out that these princesses are “more well-rounded, independent, strong-willed, determined characters, insistent on being true to themselves”, as exemplified by Ariel, Jasmine, Pocahontas and Kida. Some characters also display “strength, brashness and confidence” as some of their core attributes, as exemplified by Meg. Nevertheless, the authors also note that in these films, “women are rewarded for acting selflessly for others, and (...) women engage in a lateral move between submission to a fatherly male authority figure, and a husbandly one”, as exemplified by Belle, Mulan and Jane.

2.5.2.1. The “Modern Era” (2005–present)

The main “Modern Era” princesses are Tiana from *The Princess and the Frog* (2009), Rapunzel from *Tangled* (2010), Merida from *Brave* (2012)⁴, Elsa and Anna from *Frozen* (2013), Moana

³ As already mentioned, whether Pocahontas nor Mulan are princesses. Pocahontas is the daughter of a Native American chief and Mulan is a commoner.

⁴ Strictly considered, Merida is a Pixar princess.

from the homonymous film (2016), Raya from *Raya and the Last Dragon* (2021) and Mirabel from *Encanto* (2021)⁵.

Menise (2019, p. 536) defines these characters as being “even more independent, adventurous, skilful, funny and generally reminiscent of characters from romantic comedies.” Hine et al. (2018, p. 1) affirm that Disney is “presenting more diverse, androgynous, balanced characters to viewers” – this conclusion is reached after determining that the Disney princesses from the first decade of the 2000s exhibit “an almost equal number of masculine and feminine behaviour”, as well as engaging in equal numbers of rescue behaviours and being more likely to remain single. These authors perfectly summarise the positive reception that the films *Tangled*, *Brave*, *Frozen* and *Moana* have had, as well as the discourse surrounding them (p. 3):

These movies have also enjoyed staggering popularity amongst young girls and increasingly, in the case of *Frozen* and *Moana*, young boys worldwide (Gomez 2014; Koonikova 2014). The mainstream media has likewise responded favorably, and a number of articles have argued that these movies contain significantly more androgynous princess characters (Pulver 2016), portray a progressive rejection of typical romantic conclusions (Pulver 2016), and present increasingly self-sufficient princesses who take an active role in plot progression ([Parks] 2014). (...) Importantly, these releases have taken place against a backdrop of unprecedented political, social and economic advancement for women worldwide, as well as increasing social discourse and acceptance surrounding gender-role flexibility and fluidity (Marsh 2016).

Johnson (2015, p. 10) notes that the character of the Disney princess has evolved over the years, redefining her message with the waves of feminism; it is predicted that, as women gain a stronger voice in society, the narrative of the Disney princesses grow as well. However, as quoted from Whelan (2012, p. 10), they “will also always be tied down in some way to their predecessors” – even though they become more empowered, they will still maintain an identity tied to less empowered ideals perpetuated by the first two eras.

⁵ Again, strictly considered, whether *Moana* nor *Mirabel* are princesses. *Moana* is the daughter of a Polynesian chief and *Mirabel* is a commoner.

3. Method

The method used in this Bachelor’s thesis is based on the “film and television analysis” by Lothar Mikos (2017, pp. 515–523), having undergone some changes: some steps were performed before starting or after finishing this Bachelor thesis, and several other steps were merged and turned into other sections, as can be seen in *Table 1*. The steps that constitute the method itself are: formation of the analysis corpus, determination of aids and appliances, data collection and description of the data base.

Steps in the method by Lothar Mikos	Adaptation in this Bachelor’s thesis
1. Development of a general interest in knowledge	Previous to the elaboration of the thesis
2. Viewing of the material	
3. Theoretical and historical reflection	<i>2. Theoretical and historical reflection</i>
4. Concretization of the cognitive interest	<i>1. Introduction</i>
5. Development of the research question(s)	
6. Narrowing of the material or formation of the analysis corpus	3. Method > 3.1. Formation of the analysis corpus
7. Determination of aids and appliances	3. Method > 3.2. Determination of aids and appliances
8. Data collection	3. Method > 3.3. Data collection
9. Description of the data base	3. Method > 3.4. Description of the data base
10. Analysis of the data: Inventory of the components of the films and television programs.	<i>Appendix I. Analysis of the individual Disney characters</i>
11. Evaluation: interpretation and contextualization of the analysed data	<i>4. Analysis of the individual Disney characters</i>
12. Evaluation I: Assessment of the analysed and interpreted data	<i>5. Discussion of the evolution of the representation of non-white female Disney main characters</i>
13. Evaluation II: Assessment of own results measured against the epistemological interest and operationalization	<i>6. Limitations</i>
14. Presentation of the results	Submission of the Bachelor’s thesis

Table 1. Comparison between the “film and television analysis” method by Lothar Mikos (left) and its adaptation for this Bachelor’s thesis (right). Steps in bold constitute the actual method used in this Bachelor’s thesis.

3.1. Formation of the analysis corpus

For this Bachelor’s thesis, only films produced by Walt Disney Animation Studios were considered. This excluded films such as *Enchanted* (2007), which was produced by Walt Disney Pictures, *Brave* (2012), which was produced by Pixar Animation Studios, or live-action adaptations and remakes of Disney animated films such as *The Little Mermaid* (2023), which was produced by Walt Disney Pictures.

To date⁶, Walt Disney Animation Studios has produced 61 films. In order to build the analysis corpus, several exclusion criteria were established (Figure 1 and Table 2):

- The first exclusion criterion was if the film was an anthology film. This excluded films such as *Saludos Amigos* (1942), *The Three Caballeros* (1944), *Make Mine Music* (1946), *Fun and Fancy Free* (1947), *Melody Time* (1948) or *The Adventures of Ichabod and Mr. Toad* (1949).
- The second exclusion criterion was if the film contained non-human protagonists. This excluded films such as *Dumbo* (1941), *Bambi* (1942), *One Hundred and One Dalmatians* (1961), *The Lion King* (1994), *Dinosaur* (2000), *Bolt* (2008) and *Zootopia* (2016).
- The third exclusion criterion was if the film contained white protagonists. This excluded all the films that feature a white Disney princess or “Disney Princess”, such as *Snow White and the Seven Dwarfs* (1937), *Cinderella* (1950), *Sleeping Beauty* (1959), *The Little Mermaid* (1989), *Beauty and the Beast* (1991) and *Tangled* (2010).
- The fourth exclusion criterion was if the film contained male protagonists. This excluded films such as *The Jungle Book* (1967), *The Emperor’s New Groove* (2000), *Brother Bear* (2003) and *Big Hero 6* (2014).

Figure 1. Flowchart representing the exclusion/inclusion algorithm used to build the analysis corpus.

⁶ This Bachelor’s thesis was completed in September 2023.

Title	Year	Reason for inclusion/exclusion	Relevant characters
<i>Snow White and the Seven Dwarfs</i>	1937	The protagonists are white.	It features the white “Disney princess” Snow White.
<i>Pinocchio</i>	1940	The protagonists are white.	
<i>Fantasia</i>	1940	The film is an anthology film.	
<i>Dumbo</i>	1941	The protagonists are not human.	
<i>Bambi</i>	1942	The protagonists are not human.	
<i>Saludos Amigos</i>	1943	The film is an anthology film.	
<i>The Three Caballeros</i>	1945	The film is an anthology film.	
<i>Make Mine Music</i>	1946	The film is an anthology film.	
<i>Fun and Fancy Free</i>	1947	The film is an anthology film.	
<i>Melody Time</i>	1948	The film is an anthology film.	
<i>The Adventures of Ichabod and Mr. Toad</i>	1949	The film is an anthology film.	
<i>Cinderella</i>	1950	The protagonists are white.	It features the white “Disney Princess” Cinderella.
<i>Alice in Wonderland</i>	1951	The protagonists are white.	It features the white protagonist Alice.
<i>Peter Pan</i>	1953	The protagonists are white.	It features the white protagonist Wendy.
<i>Lady and the Tramp</i>	1955	The protagonists are not human.	
<i>Sleeping Beauty</i>	1959	The protagonists are white.	It features the white “Disney Princess” Aurora.
<i>One Hundred and One Dalmatians</i>	1961	The protagonists are not human.	
<i>The Sword in the Stone</i>	1963	The protagonists are white.	
<i>The Jungle Book</i>	1967	The protagonists are male.	It features the Indian protagonist Mowgli.
<i>The Aristocats</i>	1970	The protagonists are not human.	
<i>Robin Hood</i>	1973	The protagonists are not human.	
<i>The Many Adventures of Winnie the Pooh</i>	1977	The protagonists are not human.	
<i>The Rescuers</i>	1977	The protagonists are not human.	
<i>The Fox and the Hound</i>	1981	The protagonists are not human.	
<i>The Black Cauldron</i>	1985	The protagonists are white.	It features the white princess Eilonwy.
<i>The Great Mouse Detective</i>	1986	The protagonists are not human.	
<i>Oliver & Company</i>	1988	The protagonists are not human.	
<i>The Little Mermaid</i>	1989	The protagonists are white.	It features the white “Disney Princess” Ariel.
<i>The Rescuers Down Under</i>	1990	The protagonists are not human.	

<i>Beauty and the Beast</i>	1991	The protagonists are white.	It features the white “Disney Princess” Belle.
<i>Aladdin</i>	1992	There is a human, non-white, female protagonist.	It features the Arabic “Disney Princess” Jasmine.
<i>The Lion King</i>	1994	The protagonists are not human.	
<i>Pocahontas</i>	1995	There is a human, non-white, female protagonist.	It features the Native American “Disney Princess” Pocahontas.
<i>The Hunchback of Notre Dame</i>	1996	There is a human, non-white, female protagonist.	It features the Romani protagonist Esmeralda.
<i>Hercules</i>	1997	The protagonists are white.	It features the white protagonist Meg.
<i>Mulan</i>	1998	There is a human, non-white, female protagonist.	It features the Chinese “Disney Princess” Mulan.
<i>Tarzan</i>	1999	The protagonists are white.	It features the white protagonist Jane.
<i>Fantasia 2000</i>	1999	The film is an anthology film.	
<i>Dinosaur</i>	2000	The protagonists are not human.	
<i>The Emperor’s New Groove</i>	2000	The protagonists are male.	It features the Incan protagonist Kuzco.
<i>Atlantis: The Lost Empire</i>	2001	There is a human, non-white, female protagonist.	It features the Atlantean princess Kida.
<i>Lilo & Stitch</i>	2002	There is a human, non-white, female protagonist.	It features the Hawaiian protagonist Lilo.
<i>Treasure Planet</i>	2002	The protagonists are white.	
<i>Brother Bear</i>	2003	The protagonists are male.	It features the Inuit protagonist Kenai.
<i>Home on the Range</i>	2004	The protagonists are not human.	
<i>Chicken Little</i>	2005	The protagonists are not human.	
<i>Meet the Robinsons</i>	2007	The protagonists are white.	
<i>Bolt</i>	2008	The protagonists are not human.	
<i>The Princess and the Frog</i>	2009	There is a human, non-white, female protagonist.	It features the Black “Disney Princess” Tiana.
<i>Tangled</i>	2010	The protagonists are white.	It features the white “Disney Princess” Rapunzel.
<i>Winnie the Pooh</i>	2011	The protagonists are not human.	
<i>Wreck-It Ralph</i>	2012	The protagonists are white.	It features the white protagonist Vanellope.
<i>Frozen</i>	2013	The protagonists are white.	It features the white princesses Elsa and Anna.
<i>Big Hero 6</i>	2014	The protagonists are male.	It features the half-white, half-East Asian protagonist Hiro.
<i>Zootopia</i>	2016	The protagonists are not human.	
<i>Moana</i>	2016	There is a human, non-white, female protagonist.	It features the Polynesian “Disney Princess” Moana.
<i>Ralph Breaks the Internet</i>	2018	The protagonists are white.	It features the Disney protagonist Vanellope.
<i>Frozen II</i>	2019	The protagonists are white.	It features the Disney princesses Elsa and Anna.
<i>Raya and the Last Dragon</i>	2021	There is a human, non-white, female protagonist.	It features the Southeast Asian protagonist Raya.
<i>Encanto</i>	2021	There is a human, non-white, female protagonist.	It features the Colombian protagonist Mirabel.

<i>Strange World</i>	2022	The protagonists are male.	It features the half-white, half-Black protagonist Ethan.
----------------------	------	----------------------------	---

Table 2. List of all Walt Disney Animated Studios films in chronological order, together with their release year, the reason they were included or excluded from the analysis corpus and relevant human, non-white and/or female characters. Colour code: grey for anthology films; films in blue for films with non-human protagonists; films in orange for films with white protagonists; films in yellow for films with male protagonists; green for included films.

All films from Walt Disney Animation Studios which had a main plot and included human, non-white and female protagonists were included in the analysis corpus: *Aladdin* (1992), *Pocahontas* (1995), *The Hunchback of Notre Dame* (1996), *Mulan* (1998), *Atlantis: The Lost Empire* (2001), *Lilo & Stitch* (2002), *The Princess and the Frog* (2009), *Moana* (2016), *Raya and the Last Dragon* (2021) and *Encanto* (2021). While most of these characters (namely Jasmine, Pocahontas, Mulan, Kida, Tiana, Moana and Raya) are indeed “Disney Princesses” or Disney princesses, for the sake of accuracy, the term “non-white female protagonist” will be used from now on, as it also includes the characters of Esmeralda, Lilo and Mirabel.

A timeline of all the white female, non-white male and non-white female Disney main characters identified in this section can be viewed in the *Appendix II*.

3.2. Determination of aids and appliances

The films were streamed using the Disney+ subscription video on-demand streaming service, using a Lenovo Thinkpad T530 laptop running on the Windows 10 Pro operating system. The screenshots were taken using the internal software of the laptop and have an original resolution of 1366x768.

3.3. Data collection

A folder was created for each of the ten films from the analysis corpus. In the course of two weeks, the films were viewed in chronological order and screenshots were taken each time the author deemed that new information about the non-white female main character was being provided. This includes:

- The first time the character appears on screen.
- The first action(s) the character performs.
- The first line of dialogue spoken by the character.
- Each time the character is framed using a different angle or shot (except exclusions).
- Each time the character performs a different action (except exclusions).

- Each line of dialogue by the characters, whether the character is on-screen or not (except exclusions).
- The last line of dialogue spoken by the character.
- The last action(s) the character performs.
- The last time the character appears on screen.

Excluded were:

- Redundant lines of dialogue: for example, if the character is off-screen and asks the question “What?” followed by the question “What do you mean?”; in this case, only the second line was screenshot, since it contained information also included in the first line.
- Redundant actions: for example, if the character is fighting with someone and uses similar attacking moves; in this case, only a sample of the moves was screenshot.
- Redundant framing: for example, if the character can be seen in a close-up showing a remorseful facial expression for 10 seconds; in this case, only a sample of the shot was screenshot.

Each screenshot was saved in .png format. The file name was their correspondent timestamp in the format H.MM.SS (H being hour, M being minute and S being second).

If other characters delivered new information about the non-white female main character via dialogue while she was not on-screen, the information was written down as a quote together with the timestamp (instead of being screenshot).

3.4. Description of the database

The data collection process yielded a total of 5326 screenshots. *Table 3* shows the number of screenshots for each film, the length of the film, the ratio between screenshots and length of the film (which operates as an indicator of the screen presence of the non-white female main character within the film), as well as the timestamps of her first and last appearance.

The non-white female main character with the highest ratio screenshots/length is Moana (7,88) from the homonymous film. This can be traced back to the fact that she is the protagonist of the film, her first appearance happens to be quite early, and she barely shares screentime with other characters – all in all she is, indeed, on-screen for most of the duration of the footage. The fact that she is a highly dynamic character, which speaks a great number of lines and performs a great number of actions, increases the number of screenshots taken.

Following Moana, the next higher ratios correspond to Tiana (6,58) from *The Princess and the Frog* and Mirabel (6,06) from *Encanto*. Behind come the ratios of Lilo (5,81) from *Lilo & Stitch*, Raya (5,56) from *Raya and the Last Dragon*, Pocahontas (5,76) from the homonymous film and Mulan (5,20) from the homonymous film. Some factors that influence their lower metrics are their relatively late first appearances (in the cases of Lilo and Pocahontas) or the fact that they happen to share screentime with a relatively big cast of characters (in the cases of Mirabel and Raya).

The non-white female main characters with the lowest ratio screenshots/length are Jasmine (3,05) from *Aladdin*, Kida (3,05) from *Atlantis. The Lost Empire* and Esmeralda (4,07) from *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*. This is hardly surprising, taking into consideration that they are not the protagonists of their respective films but rather the love interests, and thus there are large portions of the films in which they are not to be seen on-screen.

Character	Number of screenshots	Film length (minutes)	Screenshots/length	First appearance (timestamp)	Last appearance (timestamp)
Jasmine	287	94	3,05	00:12:40	01:25:42
Pocahontas	507	88	5,76	00:07:57	01:15:31
Esmeralda	395	97	4,07	00:17:00	01:24:15
Mulan	499	96	5,20	00:03:06	01:21:23
Kida	290	95	3,05	00:01:22	01:29:16
Lilo	494	85	5,81	00:10:18	01:20:17
Tiana	645	98	6,58	00:01:31	01:30:19
Moana	891	113	7,88	00:03:26	01:36:11
Raya	639	115	5,56	00:01:08	01:34:40
Mirabel	679	112	6,06	00:00:47	01:30:59

Table 3. List of the ten films from the analysis corpus in chronological order, together with the number of screenshots for each film, the length of the film, the ratio between screenshots and length of the film and the timestamps of the first and last appearance. Colour code: *red* for ratios screenshots/length equal or lower than 5,00; *orange* for ratios between 5,01 and 6,00; *yellow* for ratios between 6,01 and 7,00; *green* for ratios higher than 7,01.

3.5. Analysis of the data

Due to time and space constraints, it was not possible to conduct an in-depth analyse of the ten characters identified in the analysis corpus. A subset of seven characters was selected based on their current or past status as a “Disney Princess”: Jasmine, Pocahontas, Mulan, Tiana, Moana and Raya as current ones, and Esmeralda as a former one; Kida, Lilo and Mirabel were discarded. Since being part of the “Disney Princess” franchise ensures a greater exposure and

presence in marketing and merchandising, it was considered an indicator of the cultural relevance and impact of these characters.

Prior to the analysis, the summary of the film as it appears on Disney+, as well as the original poster, are presented in order to display the tone the company intends to set for the film.

First, background information about the film is provided: who directed the film, who were the voice actors and if they were part of the represented collectives, where the inspiration for the film came from, if members of the represented collectives were involved in the production and basic trivia about the non-white female character (status, age, sidekicks...).

Second, the physical appearance of the non-white female character is described, supported with a long-shot screenshot (for the whole body) and a close-up screenshot (for the facial features). If the character has a main outfit, this is described as well. If the character is portrayed with several outfits, a screenshot (but not a description) of each is provided.

Third, the psychological traits of the non-white female character are listed, supported with relevant screenshots. Traits which are not strictly psychological but psychology-adjacent (such as talents, passions or physical abilities) are listed as well, also supported with relevant screenshots.

Fourth, the actions of the non-white female character are described in chronological order, supported by relevant screenshots when deemed necessary. This includes the first and last frames and lines of dialogue, rescuing behaviour, songs, kisses, fights...

Lastly, a compilation summarizes the background information, the physical and psychological descriptions and the actions of the character, and infers her motivations and character arc. Where relevant, concepts from the theoretical framework are explicitly named.

The background information about the films as well as the physical appearance, psychological traits and relevant actions of the non-white female characters can be found in the *Appendix I*. The summaries of the analyses of the seven characters constitute the following section.

4. Analysis of the individual Disney characters

4.1. Jasmine from *Aladdin* (1992)

The character of Jasmine is voiced by the voice actors Linda Larkin and Lea Salonga, neither of whom are of known Arabic ancestry. She is the daughter of the Sultan of Agrabah, a fictional city in the Middle East, and is allegedly 15 years old.

Jasmine is slender, lightly tanned and extremely small-waisted. Her most prominent features are her voluminous long black hair and her huge brown eyes. According to Christiane Staninger (2003, p. 76), she can be described as a dark-haired Barbie with decidedly white features. Her outfits are extremely revealing, following the orientalist trope of the ~~harem~~ woman. She has a stubborn, rebellious and confrontative personality; she can also be described as clever and flirtatious. Although agile, she is not strong.

Throughout the film, Jasmine has close physical contact with the protagonist Aladdin and the antagonist Jafar. She kisses Aladdin already mid-film and also at the end, and is close to kissing him a couple more times though the film. She, a teenager, kisses the middle-aged Jafar on the lips, a unique act among all “Disney Princesses”, Disney princesses or Disney main characters. At this point the author would like to refer back to Judith Butler’s “prohibitive and generative effects of power”: the very same resource that is supposed to empower and free Jasmine, namely her sensual behaviour, plays along the very same system that is oppressing her.

In several occasions she is portrayed as a “damsel in distress”, being pushed to the floor and needing rescuing from Aladdin. Her greatest weapons are her royal status and her sexuality; at the end of the day, neither of those are enough for her to fend for herself. Although Jasmine states that she is “not a prize to be won” (00:53:52), her portrayal in this film contradicts this. She is strongly exoticized and fetishised; due to the way she is framed in the film, the spectator is forced into a voyeuristic role towards her.

Her biggest motivation can be summarised as having freedom of choice: on the one hand, to marry for love and, on the other hand, to leave the palace. At the end of the film, she has achieved both, marrying the man of her choice and being able to travel the world. However, it cannot be said that she has a character arc, since she has not really learnt anything or changed in any way; this can be traced back to the fact that she is not the actual protagonist of the film.

4.2. Pocahontas from *Pocahontas* (1995)

It is important to remember that Pocahontas is not based on a legend or myth, as many other non-white female characters. As Michelle Anya Anjirbag (2018, p. 89) points out, Pocahontas

is “a misappropriated historical figure and the film has drawn criticism from indigenous communities for whitewashing and erasing a genocidal history.” This is especially troubling taking into account that, when children were asked what they thought about the film, “they took its story for historical fact” (Sun & Picker, 2001).

The character of Pocahontas is voiced by the voice actors Irene Bedard and Judy Kuhn; the former is of Iñupiat and Métis descent. She is the daughter of Chief Powhatan, the leader of an alliance of Native American tribes, and is allegedly 18 years old.

Pocahontas is slender, “copper-skinned” (00:42:00) and has an hourglass figure. Her similarities to an Amazon have been remarked: “(s)he is tall, has long, strong legs, and a developed bust” (Lacroix, 2004, p. 220). She has long, straight black hair, an angular face, slanted, wide-set eyes, a straight nose and full red lips. She wears a relatively revealing outfit and is barefoot. Pocahontas can be described as extremely athletic, adventurous and devoted to her love interest John Smith; she also has a mystical connection with nature.

It is remarkable how well the portrayals in the film align with the key topics listed in *The West and the Rest: Discourse and Power* (Stuart Hall, 1992): Virginia is depicted as a paradise on earth, the Native Americans lead a simple and innocent life in harmony with nature, and Pocahontas is extremely beautiful. Although she is outraged by John Smith calling her people “savages” (00:38:42), she quite perfectly fits the trope of the “noble savage”: brave, hard-working, honourable, never taking more than she actually needs and being one with nature.

It is also remarkable how much of her plot revolves about the character of John Smith. At the climax of the film, she prevents the war between the two groups only as a “side effect” of her rescuing John Smith. She is invested in the pacific coexistence of the Native American tribes and the English colonisers not out of idealism, but in order to be able to be together with her love interest.

Her motivation is ambiguous: as stated in “Just Around the Riverbend”, she wants to follow her dreams and not live a safe, steady and sheltered life; she also wants to discover her path in life. She does achieve both: she does not marry Kocoum, gets to experience a culture different than hers and literally follows her dream about a spinning arrow to rescue John Smith, discovering her path. However, at the end of the film she ends up staying with her tribe, instead of travelling the world, which results in an also ambiguous character arc where it is not very clear if she has learnt anything or changed in any way.

4.3. Esmeralda from *The Hunchback of Notre Dame* (1996)

The character of Esmeralda is voiced by the voice actors Demi Moore and Heidi Mollenhauer, neither of whom are of known Romani ancestry. Esmeralda is a Romani dancer living in Paris in 1482, and is allegedly between 19 and her early twenties.

Esmeralda is slender and brown. She has an hourglass figure with a developed bust, voluminous wavy black hair, thick black eyebrows and huge green eyes. She can be described as being fiery, caring, cunning, seductive and athletic, and she has a talent for dancing.

Fatima El-Tayeb has noted that Romani people function as “noble savages”: proud, seductive, mysterious, and dangerous (2016, p. 93) – Esmeralda fits all of these stereotypes. She is seen being able to be quite aggressive, both verbally and physically (by insulting, spitting, kicking in the face or attacking with a candleholder or a slingshot). She is also able to perform inexplicable magic tricks, such as disappearing in smoke clouds or wrapped in cloth, or reading hands, which portrays her as being exotic and intriguing. Her being barefoot and her inability to stay “between stone walls” (00:41:20) further depict her as being free-spirited, naturalising her yearning for freedom as a part of being Romani.

Esmeralda’s degree of sexualization is striking. Her usual outfit is somewhat revealing, with a tight bodice that frames her waist and hips and a top that leaves her shoulders and a varying amount of cleavage exposed. For a brief moment, as Quasimodo enters her tent, the viewer may mistakenly believe that she will be seen naked, before she manages to cover herself with a robe. Her dance outfit is so thin and clinging to the body it looks like paint on the skin. Even at her execution outfit she is made to wear a rope around her waist to accentuate her figure. All in all, Esmeralda falls victim to naturalisation, stereotyping, fetishism and voyeurism (Hall, 1997b) as well as being a “noble savage” (Hall, 1992).

In addition, Esmeralda is portrayed as being well-aware of her sex appeal. She stares teasingly at her love interest Captain Phoebus before ever having exchanged a word, she winks at the protagonist Quasimodo, teases the antagonist Judge Claude Frollo during her dance routine, and even defyingly accuses him of having lascivious thoughts for her later in the film. This fits into Judith Butler’s “prohibitive and generative effects of power” (1999): the film intends to empower Esmeralda by means of her sexuality, while playing into the very system that is actually depriving her of power.

Esmeralda is portrayed as being able to fend for herself. She does not need assistance in escaping from the soldiers even though she is outnumbered; she rescues Phoebus twice, once by preventing his execution and once by preventing his drowning in the river; she even brings him to safety and heals his wound. She does need Quasimodo’s help to escape from Notre

Dame, and is indeed rescued by him from being burnt alive on the pyre; however, moments later, it is Esmeralda's turn to save Quasimodo's life by preventing his fall into the void.

Esmeralda's greatest motivation is justice, namely social justice: she fights for her right to earn a living by dancing on the street, she defends Quasimodo from a harassing crowd and faces the consequences from Judge Claude Frollo, and keeps fighting to change society's opinion on "gypsies". In her song "God Help the Outcast", she selflessly asks for nothing for her own benefit, but rather that the outcasts (including the Romani) are protected by God. At the end of the film, although she has not really learnt anything or changed in any way, Esmeralda has played a key role in making Paris more accepting of outcasts such as Quasimodo and the Romani, and thus coming closer to her goal.

4.4. Mulan from *Mulan* (1998)

The character of Mulan is voiced by the voice actors Ming-Na Wen and Lea Salonga; the former is Cantonese American. She is a commoner living in a village in Imperial China, and is allegedly 16 years old.

Mulan has light skin and a slender figure with a relatively flat chest and narrow hips. She has straight black hair with varying length, an oval face, slanted black eyes, black arched eyebrows, a broad nose and thick lips. Her core traits are her ingenuity and intelligence, her sense of responsibility and justice, her love for her father Fa Zhou and her inability to be "typically feminine" (as well as "typically masculine"). She is portrayed in a down-to-earth and unglamorous way, sometimes being the butt of the joke.

Initially, Mulan tries to be the perfect bride and daughter by adhering to feminine stereotypes: wearing make-up and a cumbersome dress, being "quiet, graceful, polite, delicate, refined, poised and punctual" (00:03:18) and finding a spouse through the matchmaker. However, she realises that she is too outspoken and clumsy to fit the role and is thus conflicted about her identity. While in the army, she tries to adhere to masculine stereotypes: starting fights, spitting and talking about swords and "manly urges" such as "killing something, fixing things and cooking outdoors" (00:33:19) – this also does not come naturally to her. Consequently, although *Mulan* (1992) heavily thematises gender roles, it completely rejects Judith Butler's performativity of gender (1999): Mulan was assigned female at birth and, no matter how she dresses, talks, moves or acts, she does not cease to "be" a woman throughout the film. Moreover, at the same time that the film is denouncing feminine and masculine clichés by portraying them as ridiculous, it is also reinforcing precisely these binary stereotypes – a

phenomenon that can be explained through the concept of prohibitive and generative effects of power.

Mulan is not sexualised to the extent that her predecessors Jasmine, Pocahontas and Mulan are. Her character design is not curvy and she is not dressed in a revealing way. Although she is seen bathing twice and having her chest solely covered by bandages, these depictions are not framed in a voyeuristic way – the focus does not lie in Mulan’s body, but rather in the comedic tone, the awkwardness of the situation or the forwarding of the plot. She does not kiss her love interest Shang, although she is seen kissing the forehead of her sidekick dragon Mushu and also hugging several characters (including the emperor, befriended soldiers, her father and Mushu). She is also not portrayed as needing rescuing – in fact, she is the one to rescue her love interest Shang twice.

It is interesting to note that Mulan is currently the only “Disney Princess” to have ever killed another character on-screen, namely the antagonist Shan Yu. She is also the “Disney Princess” with the highest death count, since she single-handedly buries hundreds of Huns in the snow. As stated in her song “Reflection”, Mulan’s motivation is to be truly herself and have her exterior match who she is inside. She enrolls in the army as a means to save her father’s life and also to prove her self-worth. As the film advances, Mulan learns and changes: she finds creative and resourceful ways to solve problems, gains new abilities (such as fighting, firing rockets or fishing) and becomes more athletic. However, her character arc is ambiguous: although by the end of the film she has indeed saved her father and China and proven her self-worth, it is unclear if the ways in which she has learnt and changed will have a continuity. It is possible that she will not have to wear make-up or a cumbersome dress anymore, will be accepted in her outspokenness and intelligence and, in general, will not have her opportunities limited by her gender. It is also possible that, now that she has ostensibly found a match in Shang (as she intended to do with the matchmaker), she can fulfil her traditional role as a woman and successfully play the part of bride and daughter.

4.5. Tiana from *The Princess and the Frog* (2009)

The character of Tiana is voiced by the African American voice actor Anika Noni Rose. She is a 19-year-old waitress living in New Orleans in the 1920s.

Tiana is dark-skinned, slender and hourglass-shaped. She has black curly hair, an oval face with enormous brown eyes, rosy cheeks, a broad nose, thick red lips and dimples. Tiana’s main personality traits are her strict work ethic, her ambition and her determination. England, Descartes and Collier-Meek describe her as being “career-oriented, which initially prevented

her from socializing and pursuing romantic opportunities” (2011, p. 563). She has a talent for cooking and wants to own her own restaurant, a dream that her beloved father never achieved. Tiana can be humorous and fierce, and has a supportive relationship with her best friend Lottie. Unlike any “Disney Princess” before or after her, Tiana spends a majority of the film’s runtime as a frog. Walt Disney Animation Studios has a record for transforming non-white Disney protagonists into animals: the Incan Kuzco from *The Emperor’s New Groove* (2000) is transformed into a lama and the Inuit Kenai from *Brother Bear* (2003) is transformed into a bear. *The Lion King* (1994), which is first film from the studios set in Africa, also contains non-human protagonists. This aligns with the binary oppositions posited by Stuart Hall in *The Spectacle of the Other* (1997b): whiteness is equated with civilisation, culture and intellectual development, while blackness is linked with savagery, nature and instinct – in other words, animality.

A very troubling element in this film is the fact that Tiana is offered a presumably financial reward in exchange for an intimate act (namely a kiss on the lips). She is asked for this at a very vulnerable moment, right after losing his dreamed location for her restaurant for being “a little woman of her background” (00:24:40). Tiana is very obviously disgusted by the idea of kissing a frog on the lips and only agrees to perform this act out of desperation, since she sees no other way to access the financial resources to avoid losing the old mill. This situation is not framed as exploitative or reprehensible, but rather as light-hearted fun.

Throughout the film, Tiana both engages in active rescuing behaviour and is passively rescued. She manages to defeat the antagonist Dr. Facilier on her own, on the one hand thanks to her realisation that having love is more important than owning a restaurant and, on the other hand, thanks to her viscoelastic frog tongue. In defeating Dr. Facilier, she effectively saves her love interest Naveen.

Tiana’s motivation is to make her father’s dream come true and own a restaurant. However, the film makes it very clear that this is not what she needs: instead of having her own business, she needs “love” in the form of a romantic partner. Tiana’s character arc consists in realising that she should forego her restaurant in order to be able to stay with Naveen. In addition, Tiana’s way of achieving her goals, namely through hard work, proves ineffective, since she is unable to save enough money to buy the old mill despite working two jobs; her frowned-upon method of wishing upon a star, on the other hand, works in every instance, and she gets a wealthy member of the royalty who financially supports her to make her dream come true.

4.6. Moana from *Moana* (2016)

The character of Moana is voiced by the Hawaiian voice actor Auli‘i Cravalho. She is the daughter of Tui and Sina, the chiefs of the Polynesian island of Motunui, and is allegedly 16 years old.

Moana is brown, muscular and slender. She has curly black hair, big brown eyes, black thick eyebrows and a broad nose. She wears a functional and historically accurate outfit (Currie, 2016) and is barefoot. Moana can be described as resourceful, stubborn, athletic and compassionate. A core trait of hers is her love for the ocean and for her island.

Throughout the film, Moana is portrayed as capable and perseverant. Despite numerous adversities and drawbacks, she keeps finding creative and brave solutions, fighting to save her island. At her lowest point, when she believes to be inadequate to fulfil the mission, her grandmother Tala is supportive of Moana’s decision to go back home, instead of pushing her to keep going – this allows Moana to realise that the call from the sea is not extrinsic, but inside her, and take up the mission again, ultimately saving the world.

It is remarkable that Moana is the first non-white female character who does not have a love interest, even though she is at an age where this would be possible⁷. She develops a friendly and supportive relationship with the demigod Maui, the main male character of the film, without any kind of romantic involvement.

Regarding rescue behaviour, she is shown to be able to get out of difficulties alone. Indeed, she single-handedly helps Maui out of being devoured by the giant monster crab Tamatoa. At the end of the film, she does receive assistance from him so as to make it to Te Fiti’s island, but this is framed in a way that positions her as the protagonist, with Maui telling her: “Go save the world” (01:25:49, echoing the words that Moana had previously told Maui at 01:14:20).

At the beginning of the film, her main motivation is to be a good daughter and leader for her people, but this happens to be at odds with her draw to the sea. Upon learning that she descends from voyagers, embarking on a world-saving mission and recognising the intrinsic nature of the call from the sea, she is able to integrate all aspects of her identity. Thus, her character arc is focused on her personal development: she starts the film torn apart and unsure of who she is, and ends up being able to be “all of her” and lead her people into a new era of wayfinding thanks to her newly gained knowledge.

⁷ Strictly speaking, the 6-year-old Lilo from *Lilo & Stitch* (2002) is the first non-white female character without a love interest.

4.7. Raya from *Raya and the Last Dragon* (2021)

The character of Raya is voiced by the voice actor Kelly Marie Tran, who is of Vietnamese ancestry. She is a warrior princess and the daughter of Chief Benja, the leader of one of the chiefdoms in Kumandra, a fictional land inspired by Southeast Asia. She is allegedly 18 years old.

Raya is tanned, slender and has a relatively flat chest and narrow hips. Her hair is straight and back and her face is oval with big black slanted eyes, a broad nose and medium thick peach lips. She wears a Southeast Asian-inspired functional outfit. Raya can be described as being a strong, agile, athletic and brave princess warrior, as well as a quick thinker; although she can be smug and condescending, she has a caring and empathic side too.

It has been disputed if there could be a romantic involvement between Raya and the antagonist Namaari; Raya's voice actor, Kelly Marie Tran, stated in an interview that there were "some romantic feelings going on there" (Robinson, 2021). However, Walt Disney Animation Studios has not explicitly stated that the relationship between these two characters is other than platonic. In any case, just as her predecessor Moana, Raya does not have a male love interest.

Regarding her rescue behaviour, Raya is shown both helping other people out of danger (such as the character Sisu or the people from the Fang chiefdom) as well as needing assistance to free herself (such as when she is captured in the Spine chiefdom and is rescued by another character). All in all, she is portrayed as a capable character that generally does not need rescuing.

As stated several times throughout the film, the main motivation of Raya is to get her "ba" (father) back. She feels deeply sorry and guilty for having made the mistake that led to him being turned to stone, and embarks on a six-year mission to bring him back to life. However, her character arc is based on trust and distrust, as stated by Sisu: "You really got some trust issues" (00:38:48). As a child, Raya is deeply weary of other people from other chiefdoms, and this suspicion just gets exacerbated after the betrayal of the antagonist Namaari; as she makes positive experiences with strangers, gets closer to them and spends more time with the hopeful Sisu, Raya starts to see that trust is the way out of the apocalyptic state of her world. At the climax of the film, Raya decides to "make the first step" (01:24:37) and sacrifice herself, trusting that the others will do the same in order to save everyone – and she turns out to be right, bringing about the reunification of all the chiefdoms.

5. Discussion of the evolution of the representation of non-white female Disney main characters

5.1. Summary of the analyses

Table 4 summarises the main features of the seven analysed characters: their names and ages in parentheses; their statuses, including their place of origin; whether the voice actor was sensitively cast (so that their race or ethnicity would match that of the character); depictions of their physical appearance with a long and a short shot; a list of their psychological traits, and their main motivation in the film.

	Status	Voice actor match	Physical appearance		Psychological traits	Motivation
Jasmine (15)	daughter of Sultan of Agrabah (fictional Arabic city)	No		stubborn, rebellious and confrontative; clever and flirtatious	having freedom of choice	
Pocahontas (18)	daughter of leader of alliance of Native American tribes	Yes		extremely athletic, adventurous and devoted to love interest; mystical connection with nature	following her dreams and discovering her path	
Esmeralda (~20)	Romani dancer living in Paris in 1482	No		fiery, caring, cunning, seductive and athletic; talent for dancing	achieving social justice	
Mulan (16)	commoner living in village in Imperial China	Yes		ingenious and intelligent, sense of responsibility and justice, devoted to father, unable to be “typically feminine”	being true to herself	
Tiana (19)	African American waitress living in New Orleans in the 1920s	Yes		strict work ethic, ambitious and determined; humorous and fierce; talent for cooking	owning her restaurant	

Moana (16)	daughter of chiefs of Motunui (fictional Polynesian Island)	Yes		resourceful, stubborn, athletic and compassionate; love for ocean and her island	being a good daughter and leader	
Raya (18)	daughter of leader of a chieftom in Kumandra (fictional Southeast Asian land)	Yes		strong, agile, athletic and brave; quick thinker; smug and condescending; caring and empathic	bringing her father back	

Table 4. Summary of the analysed non-white female Disney main characters including name, age (in parentheses), status, match with the race or ethnicity of the voice actor, physical appearance, psychological traits and main motivation. Sources (top to bottom): John Musker and Ron Clements, *Aladdin*, 1992; Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, *Pocahontas*, 1995; Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996; Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, *Mulan*, 1998; John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009; John Musker and Ron Clements, *Moana*, 2016; Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

At first glance, only two patterns can be detected. The first is the animation style: two-dimensional for the first five characters and three-dimensional for the last two. The second is the racially sensitive casting: the only voice actors whose race or ethnicity does not match that of the character are among the first films, whereas the last characters have all been sensitively cast. Nevertheless, a closer examination of the dimensions “race” and “gender” does indeed reveal an evolution in the representation of these characters.

5.2. Representation of the “race” dimension

The first aspect to be discussed is the **discursive concept of race**. Stuart Hall argues that race works as a language or discourse, organising and giving meaning to the physical differences which can be observed – in his words: “the body is a text” (1997a, p. 15).

Thus, in order to design characters that the spectator can “read” as being Arab, Native American, Romani, Chinese, African American, Polynesian or Southeast Asian, Walt Disney Animation Studios needed to “write” them according to the expected “rules” of the races they were intending to represent: their skin tone, their face shape, their hair colour and texture, their eye colour and shape, their nose shape, their lip colour and thickness... Five of the analysed characters (*Pocahontas*, *Mulan*, *Tiana*, *Moana* and *Raya*) do indeed have the expected features of their “race”.

Jasmine and Esmeralda, however, have been criticised for having “white features”, especially in comparison to other Arab or Romani characters in their films, respectively. This should not be understood as an attempt on Walt Disney Animation Studios’ part to subvert or challenge the expected features of these characters, but rather to make them fit into their beauty standards (as evidenced by the fact that the other Arab or Roma characters, although caricatured, do possess the expected features).

The second aspect to be discussed are the **manifestations of the racialised discourse**:

- Four films show *binary oppositions* between different characters or groups: Jasmine and Aladdin (white features, accent-free, good) versus Jafar or the guards (hooked noses, strong accents, evil); Pocahontas and the Native Americans (harmonious with nature, good) versus the English colonisers (greedy, evil); Esmeralda (white features, accent-free, honest) versus the other Romani (big noses, strong accents, dishonest) as well as Esmeralda and the Romani (threatening, shady jobs) versus the gadje⁸ (innocuous, reputable jobs); Tiana and her family (lower class, hardworking, frugal) versus Charlotte and her father (upper class, idle, extravagant).
- Two characters fall victim to *naturalisation*, or having their culture reduced to nature and lack of civilisation: Pocahontas (with her mystical connection to “rocks and trees and creatures”) and Esmeralda (with her inability to “live between stonewalls”).
- Three analysed characters are portrayed *stereotypically*, depicting exaggerated, simplified and easily recognised characteristics: Jasmine (based on the ~~harem~~ woman), Pocahontas (based on the ~~Indian princess~~) and Esmeralda (based on the ~~gypsy~~ seductress).
- Two characters display *orientalist* tropes, or stereotypical ideas of “the Orient” created by Europe: Jasmine (being exotic and highly sexualised, wearing a ~~harem~~ dress and being enslaved at the end of the film) and Esmeralda (also being exotic and highly sexualised, wearing a “sexy ~~gypsy~~” outfit, practicing witchcraft and fortune-telling and being free-spirited).
- Two characters are *fetishized*, or reduced to an object and portrayed in a voyeuristic way: Jasmine (for example, when she seduces and kisses the antagonist in her slave outfit) and Esmeralda (for example, when she performs a pole dance in her extremely tight outfit).

⁸ The word “gadje” comes from the Romani “gaʒe” and means a non-Romani person.

The third and last aspect to be considered is the **discourse of “the West and the Rest”** and the figure of the **“noble savage”**. People from “the Rest” are supposed to live in paradisiac places, lead a simple and innocent life, lack developed social organization, live in a state of nature and display a frank and open sexuality (and extreme beauty in case of women) (Hall, 1999, pp. 209–210). The “noble savage” is idealised as a proud, simple, unsophisticated person living in a state of Nature and not being corrupted by European civilization (p. 218).

Pocahontas is a great example, as she embodies these ideas to the tee: she is extremely beautiful, proud, leads a simple and innocent life in a paradisiac place and lives in connection and harmony with nature. To a large extent, Esmeralda also fits into this discourse: she is also extremely beautiful and proud, lives a simple and unsophisticated life outside of European civilization and is portrayed displaying a relatively open sexuality. Moana happens to be a fringe case: although she does live in a paradisiac place and is shown to live in simplicity and harmony with nature, she is devoid of the aura of mysticism that surrounds Pocahontas and her magic connection to the natural elements, or Esmeralda and her need to lead a nomadic life. Jasmine, Mulan, Tiana and Raya have not been found to embody the ideas from “the West and the Rest”.

	“Body as text”	Manifestations of racialised discourse	“The Rest” and “noble savage”
Jasmine	white features	(4) binary opposition, stereotyping, orientalism, fetishism/voyeurism	No
Pocahontas	readable	(3) binary opposition, naturalisation, stereotyping	Yes
Esmeralda	white features	(5) binary opposition, naturalisation, stereotyping, orientalism, fetishism/voyeurism	Yes
Mulan	readable	(0)	No
Tiana	readable	(1) binary opposition	No
Moana	readable	(0)	Debatable
Raya	readable	(0)	No

Table 5. Summary of the “race” dimension including the accuracy of the character’s features within the framework of the discursive concept of race, a list of the manifestations of the racialised discourse present in the film (with the number of items in parentheses) and the presence of the discourse of “the West and the Rest” and the figure of the “noble savage” in the film. Relevant data has been marked in **bold**.

5.3. Representation of the “gender” dimension

The first aspect to be discussed is the **distinction between sex and gender**; although the former is usually understood as being based on biology and the latter as being shaped by culture, Judith Butler states that both are actually culturally constructed (1999, pp. 10–11).

There is no available information regarding chromosomes, reproductive organs or levels of sex-specific hormones of the analysed characters, but it can be inferred from their secondary sexual

characteristics (presence of breasts, wide hips, absence of facial hair and higher-pitched voice) that they are intended to be biologically female. Based on their clothing, behaviour and choice of pronouns it can be inferred that they are intended to identify as women. Therefore, all seven analysed characters have aligning sex and gender.

The second aspect to be discussed is the **heterosexual matrix**, or the assumption of binarity, cisgender identity and heterosexuality as “natural”.

As far as we know, all seven analysed characters are intended to be endosex and cisgender. Five of them (Jasmine, Pocahontas, Esmeralda, Mulan and Tiana) have a male romantic interest; since they do not display any kind of romantic interest for female characters, it can be stated that they are portrayed as being heterosexual. Moana and Raya have no official romantic interest at all (although it is disputed whether Raya might have romantic feelings for her female antagonist), leaving their sexual orientation undetermined. Consequently, none of the films portray sex, gender identity and/or sexual orientation outside the heterosexual matrix.

The third aspect to be discussed are the **prohibitive and generative effects of power**, or the idea that, paradoxically, power limits and creates at the same time. This aspect plays a role in *Aladdin* (1992), *The Hunchback of Notre Dame* (1996) and *Mulan* (1998) and it is relevant insofar as it makes us aware of the strategies that are being employed for the purported goals of “empowering women” or “denouncing gender stereotypes”.

In the first two cases, the analysed character is presumably empowered by her sexuality: Jasmine uses her sex appeal to ridicule her love interest and also to distract the antagonist as a means of assisting in her rescue; Esmeralda uses her sex appeal to publicly mock the antagonist. However, rather than being empowering, their sexuality leads to their sexualisation and objectification, which relate to their oppression and difficulty accessing power. In plain words: the power given to them to fight against an oppressive system paradoxically plays into the hands of that system.

In the third case, the film denounces feminine and masculine clichés by portraying them as ridiculous; however, at the same time, it reinforces that it is indeed feminine to wear make-up and a cumbersome dress and to be “quiet, graceful, polite, delicate, refined, poised and punctual”, and that it is indeed masculine to start fights and to spit. All in all, by trying to condemn gender stereotypes as harmful, the film is actually promoting them.

The fourth and last aspect is the **performativity of gender**, or the notion that gender identity is actually an illusion created by repeated acts and gestures interpreted through the frame of gender (Butler, 1999, pp. 43–44).

Six of the seven analysed characters (Jasmine, Pocahontas, Esmeralda, Tiana, Moana and Raya) perform their gender correctly and make it impossible to discern whether the film is asserting that the characters “are” indeed women or are women “only” insofar as they act as one. However, by “doing their gender right”, these characters do contribute to the belief that two discrete and opposed genders are necessary and natural.

The only film in which this theory can be evaluated is *Mulan* (1998). The title character intentionally takes on the role of a man for approximately half of the film’s runtime; according to the theory of gender performativity, during the time in which Mulan is “pretending” to be a man she would be, for all intents and purposes, “being” a man. However, the film rejects this idea by assigning Mulan a “female essence”: no matter how she dresses, talks, moves or acts, she does not cease to “be” a woman throughout the film. Thus, the film rejects gender performativity.

	Distinction sex-gender	Heterosexual matrix	Prohibitive and generative effects of power	Performativity of gender
Jasmine	aligning sex and gender	endosex, cisgender, heterosexual	sexuality as empowerment	non-thematised
Pocahontas	aligning sex and gender	endosex, cisgender, heterosexual	not relevant	non-thematised
Esmeralda	aligning sex and gender	endosex, cisgender, heterosexual	sexuality as empowerment	non-thematised
Mulan	aligning sex and gender	endosex, cisgender, heterosexual	gender stereotypes as harmful	rejected
Tiana	aligning sex and gender	endosex, cisgender, heterosexual	not relevant	non-thematised
Moana	aligning sex and gender	endosex, cisgender, non-specified sexual orientation	not relevant	non-thematised
Raya	aligning sex and gender	endosex, cisgender, non-specified sexual orientation (?)	not relevant	non-thematised

Table 6. Summary of the “gender” dimension including the alignment between the character’s sex and gender, their location within the heterosexual matrix, the relevance of prohibitive and generative effects of power within the film and the its stance with respect to gender performativity. Relevant data has been marked in **bold**.

5.4. Three phases in the representation of non-white female Disney main characters

According to the analysed dimensions of race and gender, it was possible to identify three different phases in the representation of non-white female Disney main characters. These three phases have been given succinct titles that summarise their hallmarks:

1. The first phase, or **“sexy” phase**, includes Jasmine from *Aladdin* (1992), Pocahontas from *Pocahontas* (1995) and Esmeralda from *The Hunchback of Notre Dame* (1996). These three characters have in common their high degrees of sexualization, exoticization, fetishism and stereotyping of their character design, as well as the fact that they are romantically involved with male characters.
2. The second phase, or **“no-sexy/yes-hetero” phase**, includes Mulan from *Mulan* (1998) and Tiana from *The Princess and the Frog* (2009). These two characters differ from those in the first phase in that they are not as stereotyped and fetishized as their predecessors, but are similar to them in that they are still pursue heterosexual romance.
3. The third phase, or **“loves-no-man” phase**, includes Moana from *Moana* (2016) and Raya from *Raya and the last Dragon* (2021). These two characters are also not as stereotyped and fetishized as those in the first phase, but differ from those in the second phase by not being portrayed as having a male love interest.

It is interesting to note that this classification does not fully coincide with most of the literature (Menise, 2019; Hine et al., 2018; Johnson, 2015; England et al., 2011; Davis, 2006)⁹. The conventional practice is to group the “Disney Princesses”, both white and non-white, in the “Classic Years” (1937–1967) including Snow White, Cinderella and Aurora; the “Eisner Era” (1967–2005) including Ariel, Belle, Jasmine, Pocahontas and Mulan, and the “Modern Era” (2005–present) including Tiana, Rapunzel, Merida, Elsa and Anna, Moana, Raya and Mirabel. However, when removing the white characters from the equation and focussing solely on the non-white characters, a new pattern emerges: the “Classic Years” disappear due to absence of representation, the “Eisner Era” mostly becomes the “sexy” phase, and the “Modern Era” mostly becomes the “loves-no-man” phase; the “no-sexy/yes-hetero” phase bridges the end of the “Eisner Era” and the start of the “Modern Era”. For a visualisation of the comparison of the two classifications see the *Appendix II*.

⁹ Also interesting is the fact that it does align with an alternative classification proposed by Juliana Garabedian (2014, p. 23): Snow White, Cinderella and Aurora belong to the era of pre-transition; Ariel, Belle, Jasmine, Pocahontas, Mulan, Tiana and Rapunzel to the era of transition; Merida and Elsa and Anna belong to the era of progression.

All in all, we can detect a tendency towards fewer stereotypes and less sexualisation, on the one hand, and to an absence of heterosexual romance, on the other hand.

The first trend can be explained by the greater involvement of the represented communities in the making of the films: for many decades, Walt Disney Animation Studios has sensitively cast its non-white female protagonists, so that the race or ethnicity of the voice actor matched that of the character; in recent years, the studio has also started consulting teams of academics, archaeologists, anthropologists, linguists, historians, dancers, musicians... from the communities, such as the Oceanic Story Trust for *Moana* (2016) or the Southeast Asia Story Trust for *Raya and the Last Dragon* (2021) (Herman, 2016; Moon, 2021). By including people from the communities in the creative process, it is less probable that the characters are going to embody caricatures or clichés, and more likely that they are going to be complex, concrete and humanized individuals.

The second trend can be explained by the influence of “fourth wave” of feminism, which started around 2010 and advocates for issues such as women’s empowerment, intersectional experiences and LGBTQ+ rights as well as trans-inclusivity and body positivity (Castanier, 2022). Also around that time, Walt Disney Animation Studios stopped treating heterosexual romance as a key element in their stories (with the film *Tangled* in 2010 as the last example of a romantic relationship between the female protagonist and her love interest) and started focusing more on their female protagonists and their relationships with other female characters.

5.5. Speculation on future tendencies in the representation of non-white female Disney main characters

The evolution of the representation of non-white female Disney main characters can be summed up as Walt Disney Animation Studios “moving with the times”. As feminism and antiracism advanced, so did who and how the studio represents. Now we have a more diverse range of races within the “Disney Princess” franchise, with sensitive casting and more involvement of the represented communities in the creative process; the female protagonists are not as passive as they used to be (like Snow White, Cinderella and Aurora), not as sexualised (like Jasmine, Pocahontas and Esmeralda) and do not always end up in a romantic relationship with a male character (as it used to be the case for each and every female protagonist “of age” until 2010). However, although progress has been made, it should not be overseen that all of the female protagonists so far (both white and non-white) are young, able-bodied, cisgender and following normative beauty standards.

If we were to speculate on the reasons behind this “moving with the times”, we could venture that it may stem from idealism, to fight discrimination and celebrate diversity; or perhaps because of economic reasons, foreseeing possible financial losses (due to backlashes or controversies) or gains (by catering to a certain audience). As Stuart Hall wrote referring to the “United Colours of Benneton” advertising series, which used “ethnic models, especially children, from many cultures and celebrate(d) images of racial and ethnic hybridity” (1997b, pp. 273–274):

Do these images evade the difficult questions, dissolving the harsh realities of racism into a liberal mish-mash of 'difference'? Do these images appropriate 'difference' into a spectacle in order to sell a product? Or are they genuinely apolitical statement about the necessity for everyone to accept and 'live with' difference, in an increasingly diverse, culturally pluralist world?

Whether it is to sell a product, whether it is to normalise difference, Walt Disney Animation Studios is effectively bringing more diversity to the big screen – and in doing so, it is contributing to the current discourse. In fact, we can hypothesise a positive feedback loop between The Walt Disney Company and society at large: Disney creates content according to the “feminist” and “antiracist” *zeitgeist*, thus increasing the amount of “feminist” and “antiracist” content available; the public is then exposed to these representations and becomes used to them, thus consolidating the “feminist” and “antiracist” *zeitgeist* even further.

If Walt Disney Animation Studios were to keep “moving with the times”, the next steps could be in LGBTQIA+ representation. To date, the studio has already dipped its toes in this field by having an openly gay protagonist, the 16-year-old Ethan Clade from *Strange World* (2022). In the future, it might be that the studio also ventures into the field of disability representation, or in the representation of less normative beauty. To date, Quasimodo from *The Hunchback of Notre Dame* (1996) is the only protagonist with a visible physical disability and who is deemed “ugly” within the film. In recent years, however, the studio has started portraying characters with slight physical disabilities as well as less “traditionally beautiful”: Mirabel, the protagonist from *Encanto* (2022), needs glasses, and her sister Luisa has an extremely muscular character design.

6. Limitations

The greatest limitation of this Bachelor's thesis stems from the fact that it was elaborated by one author. Although it was attempted to proceed as objectively as possible, the formation of the analysis corpus, the establishing of the rules for the data collection, the data collection itself, the selection of datapoints for the analysis... were stemming from one single research habitus. It would have been extremely enriching to have several authors discussing the criteria to include or exclude each film, the standards after which a screenshot would be taken, the selection of screenshots relevant to the analysis of the character, the elaboration on the motivation of the character, the assessment of the manifestations of racialised discourse... in order to increase the rigor, objectivity, precision and confidence of this Bachelor's thesis.

Another limitation is the discarding of the analysis of Kida from *Atlantis. The Lost Empire* (2001), Lilo from *Lilo & Stitch* (2002) and Mirabel from *Encanto* (2021) due to time and space constraints. With a preliminary analysis of the screenshots, it can be ventured that:

- Kida's portrayal would fit into the "sexy" phase together with Jasmine, Pocahontas and Esmeralda, although she chronologically should be part of the "no-sexy/yes-hetero" phase;
- Lilo is an outlier: on the one hand, chronologically she belongs to the "no-sexy/yes-hetero" phase, on the other hand, purely in terms of content she belongs to the "loves-no-man" phase; however, none of these categories fit her, since (unlike all the other non-white female Disney main characters) she is not at an age where a romantic relationship would be appropriate;
- Mirabel fits perfectly into the "loves-no-man" phase, both chronologically as well as in her lack of pursuit of a heterosexual relationship.

Thus, the inclusion of the analysis of these characters might have strongly influenced the outcome of this Bachelor's thesis.

Finally, it would have been extremely interesting to compare the representation of non-white female main characters with white female main characters (such as Snow White from *Snow White and the Seven Dwarfs* (1937), Ariel from *The Little Mermaid* (1989) or Elsa and Anna from *Frozen* (2013)) and non-white male main characters (such as Mowgli from *The Jungle Book* (1967), Kuzco from *The Emperor's New Groove* (2000) or Hiro from *Big Hero 6* (2014)), in order to be able to isolate the dimensions "race" and "gender".

7. Conclusion

This Bachelor's thesis has sought to analyse the representation of non-white female Disney main characters, focusing on the "race" and "gender" dimensions. The relevance of undertaking such an analysis lies in the fact that The Walt Disney Company, as a hegemonic cultural institution, also functions as a socializing agent – the portrayals of race and gender depicted in its films inform the identity formation of its (usually young and impressionable) audiences, who at some point grow up and may occupy positions of power and/or work with marginalized collectives.

Following an exclusion/inclusion algorithm, ten Walt Disney Animation Studios films featuring non-white female main characters were identified: *Aladdin* with Jasmine (1992), *Pocahontas* (1995), *The Hunchback of Notre Dame* with Esmeralda (1996), *Mulan* (1998), *Atlantis: The Lost Empire* with Kida (2001), *Lilo & Stitch* with Lilo (2002), *The Princess and the Frog* with Tiana (2009), *Moana* (2016), *Raya and the Last Dragon* with Raya (2021) and *Encanto* with Mirabel (2021).

The films were viewed in chronological order and, following a set of a pre-established criteria, a total of 5326 screenshots were taken. The ratios between the number of screenshots and the length of the film were examined as indicators of the character's screen presence within its film. Jasmine from *Aladdin*, Kida from *Atlantis: The Lost Empire* and Esmeralda from *The Hunchback of Notre Dame* happened to have the lowest ratios, which can be explained by the fact that they are actually the love interests and not the protagonists of the films. Moana had the highest ratio, since she is a highly dynamic character and appears on-screen for most of the duration of the film.

Due to time and space constraints, the characters of Kida, Lilo and Mirabel were discarded based on their lack of present or former status as a "Disney Princess" and consequent lower exposure and cultural impact. Jasmine, Pocahontas, Esmeralda, Mulan, Tiana, Moana and Raya underwent an in-depth analysis:

- Jasmine was shown to have a revealing, sexy, ~~harem~~-like character design, as well as white features. One of the most relevant aspects of her portrayal was the high degree of exoticization and fetishisation to which she is subjected: she displays flirtatious behaviour and engages in close physical contact both with the protagonist (voluntarily) and the antagonist (as a survival strategy). Her character arc was shown to be tenuous; however, she does achieve her goal of freely choosing her husband and leaving the palace by the end of the film.

- Pocahontas was described as having an adventurous, Amazon-like character design. Her level of alignment with the “noble savage” trope and her mystical connection to nature were notable features of hers. Her character arc was shown to be ambiguous, because she manages to achieve her goals of avoiding a sheltered life and discovering her path in life, but only to a limited extent.
- Esmeralda was described as having a voluptuous and heavily sexualised character design. She was shown to conform to the stereotype of Romani people as “noble savages” by embodying pride, seductiveness, mystery and danger. She was also shown to be portrayed as being able to fend for herself, as well as making progress toward her goal of achieving social justice.
- Mulan was shown to be not as sexualised as her predecessors, but rather portrayed in a down-to-earth and unglamorous manner. The fact that she spends a substantial amount of screentime pretending to be a man allowed for an extensive examination of the film’s stance on gender roles and identity. Although Mulan was shown to undergo significant character development, her character arc was deemed ambiguous, as it is unclear whether she would be able to express a more flexible and nonconformist femininity or fall into the traditional role of daughter and wife.
- Tiana was described as being extremely hard-working, ambitious and determined. Most remarkable was the fact that she spends the majority of her screentime transformed into a frog, echoing Walt Disney Animation Studios’ longstanding tradition of equating non-whiteness with animality. Tiana was found to be both actively rescuer and passively rescued. Her character arc was quite explicit: Tiana *wanted* to own her restaurant but *needed* to learn that love (in the form of a heterosexual romantic relationship) is more important than achieving her life goals.
- Moana was described as having a muscular character design, paired with a functional and historically accurate outfit. She is the first non-white female character who does not have a male love interest. She was found to be portrayed as capable, perseverant and self-sufficient. Her character arc was focussed on her personal development, with Moana going from being conflicted between her love for her people and the sea to reconciling both aspects of her identity and, in doing so, also becoming a better leader for her community.

- Raya was found to be a strong, agile, athletic and brave princess warrior, with a Southeast Asian-inspired functional outfit. Like Moana, she does not pursue a romantic relationship, although there has been some speculation about a romantic involvement between her and the female antagonist Namaari. She was found to be portrayed as a capable character with little need for rescue. Her character arc was found to revolve around trust, with Raya *wanting* to bring her father back to life but her *needing* to trust other people in order to save the world and reunite her fragmented homeland.

Focussing on the “race” dimension and drawing on three of Stuart Hall’s works, it was found that the earlier films had a noticeably higher number of manifestations of the racialised discourse, including binary opposition, naturalisation, stereotyping, orientalism and fetishism/voyeurism. It was also the earlier characters, namely Jasmine and Esmeralda, who were depicted as having white features. Finally, also the earlier characters, namely Pocahontas and Esmeralda, were found to embody the “noble savage” trope, with the latter Moana being a fringe case.

Focussing on the “gender” dimension and drawing on Judith Butler’s *Gender Trouble* (1999), it was determined that all of the analysed characters had aligning sex and gender. Only the two latest characters, namely Moana and Raya, had slightly decentred positions in the heterosexual matrix, by virtue of having a non-specified sexual orientation. Prohibitive and generative effects of power were detected in the earlier films, namely *Aladdin* (1992) and *The Hunchback of Notre Dame* (1996) with sexuality as empowerment, and *Mulan* (1998) with gender stereotypes as harmful. The only film in which gender performativity could be evaluated, and ultimately rejected, was *Mulan* (1998).

By having all non-white female characters back-to-back and focusing on the dimensions of “race” and “gender”, it was possible to determine that there has indeed been an evolution in their representation, with a tendency towards fewer stereotypes and less sexualisation on the one hand, and an absence of heterosexual romance on the other hand. Three phases were identified in this Bachelor’s thesis: the “sexy” phase (which is characterised by a high degree of sexualization, exoticization, fetishism and stereotyping), the “no-sexy/yes-hetero” phase (which is characterised by heterosexual romance while lacking the stereotypes and sexualization) and the “loves-no-man” phase (which is characterised by the lack of heterosexual romance). Interestingly, these phases differ from those suggested in the literature.

Overall, it can be said that The Walt Disney Company “moves with the times” and caters to the current feminist and antiracist discourse. However, it is important to be aware of the fact that the studio, in its representation of non-white female characters, does not conceptualise “race” and/or “gender” being historical, political and cultural constructs – rather, the studio treats them as self-evident and natural truths.

Speculating on future trends, it is highly unlikely that Walt Disney Animation Studios will reverse course and go back to portraying non-white female characters as stereotyped and sexualised as in the 1990s, or dependent on heterosexual romance as before 2010. We can venture that we might see more non-white female characters overlapping with LGBTQIA+, disability or non-normative beauty representation in the coming years.

Future research could finish the path that this Bachelor’s thesis started and analyse the representation of the lesser-known non-white female main characters Kida, Lilo and Mirabel. It would also be extremely interesting to undertake a comparative analysis of white female main characters and non-white male main characters, so as to isolate the dimensions “race” and “gender”.

As a final note, tying back to the title of this Bachelor’s thesis, it can be concluded that the representation of non-white female main characters in films by Walt Disney Animation Studios went from the “sexy” Jasmine, Pocahontas and Esmeralda, through the “no-sexy/yes-hetero” Mulan and Tiana, to finally make it to the “loves-no-man” Moana and Raya.

List of references

- Anjirbag, M. A. (2018). Mulan and Moana: Embedded Coloniality and the Search for Authenticity in Disney Animated Film. *Social Sciences*, 7(11), 230–244.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci7110230>
- Armstrong, R. (2018). Time to Face the Music: Musical Colonization and Appropriation in Disney's Moana. *Social Sciences*, 7(7), 113. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci7070113>
- Auger, S. (2020, November 17). How Old Are The Disney Princesses? *Couponing to Disney*. Retrieved September 18, 2023, from: <https://www.couponingtodisney.com/how-old-are-the-disney-princesses/>
- Baker-Sperry, L. (2007). The Production of Meaning through Peer Interaction: Children and Walt Disney's Cinderella. *Sex Roles*, 56, 717–727. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-007-9236-y>
- Bologna, C. (2018, August 17). Can We Talk About How Young The Disney Princesses Are? *HuffPost*. https://www.huffpost.com/entry/young-disney-princesses_n_5ae0b63ce4b04aa23f1e84d9
- Bowleg, L. (2013). “Once You’ve Blended the Cake, You Can’t Take the Parts Back to the Main Ingredients”: Black Gay and Bisexual Men’s Descriptions and Experiences of Intersectionality. *Sex Roles*, 68(11–12), 754–767. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11199-012-0152-4>
- Breaux, R. M. (2010). After 75 Years of Magic: Disney Answers Its Critics. Rewrites African American History, and Cashes in on Its Racist Past. *Journal of African American Studies*, 14, 398–416. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12111-010-9139-9>
- Bunjun, B. (2010). Feminist organizations and intersectionality: Contesting hegemonic feminism. *Atlantis*, 34(2), 115–126.
- Bussey, K., & Bandura, A. (1999). Social cognitive theory of gender development and differentiation. *Psychological Review*, 106, 676–713. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-295x.106.4.676>
- Butler, J. (1999). *Gender Trouble*. Routledge.
- Carillo, C. A., Crumley, J. W., Thieringer, K., & Harrison, J. S. (2012). *The Walt Disney Company: A Corporate Strategy Analysis* [Case Study, University of Richmond: Robins School of Business]. UR Scholarship Repository.
<https://scholarship.richmond.edu/robins-case-network/4/>

- Castanier, J. (2022). *Defining 4th Wave Feminism* [Project, University of Washington Tacoma]. Sociology Student Work Collection.
https://digitalcommons.tacoma.uw.edu/gender_studies/83
- Clements, R., & Musker, J. (1992). *Aladdin* [Film]. Walt Disney Pictures & Walt Disney Feature Animation.
- Collins, P. H. (1990). *Black feminist thought: Knowledge, consciousness, and the politics of empowerment*. Routledge.
- Condis, M. (2013). Applying for the Position of Princess: Race, Labor, and the Privileging of Whiteness in the Disney Princess Line. In M. Forman-Brunell & R. C. Hainsl (Eds.), *Princess cultures: mediating girls' imaginations and identities* (pp. 25–44). Peter Lang Publishing.
- Cook, B., & Bancroft, T. (1998). *Mulan* [Film]. Walt Disney Pictures & Walt Disney Feature Animation.
- courtneyl2015. (2015, August 31). Esmeralda. *The Disney Woman*. Retrieved September 18, 2023, from: <https://thedisneywoman.wordpress.com/2015/08/31/esmeralda/>
- Coyne, S. M., Linder, J. R., Rasmussen, E. E., Nelson, D. A., & Birkbeck, V. (2016). Pretty as a Princess: Longitudinal Effects of Engagement With Disney Princesses on Gender Stereotypes, Body Esteem, and Prosocial Behavior in Children. *Child development*, 87(6), 1909–1925. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.12569>
- Crenshaw, K. W. (2003). Traffic at the crossroads: multiple oppressions. In R. Morgan (Ed.), *Sisterhood is forever: The women's anthology for a new millennium* (pp. 43–57). Washington Square Press.
- Crossley, A. (2022, June 16). Raya and the Last Dragon Characters: Heights and Ages Analysis. *Fantasy Topics*. <https://fantasytopics.com/raya-and-the-last-dragon-characters-heights-ages/>
- Crowe, D. (2015, January 28). 'The Hunchback of Notre Dame' perpetuates negative gypsy stereotypes. *Greensboro News & Record*. https://greensboro.com/the-hunchback-of-notre-dame-perpetuates-negative-gypsy-stereotypes/article_524e3593-0b12-5d54-925b-3667820893c9.html
- Currie, M. (2016, November 11). Disney designer details 'Moana' costume process. *Technique*. <https://nique.net/entertainment/2016/11/11/disney-designer-details-moana-costume-process/>
- Davis, A. M. (2006). *Good Girls and Wicked Witches: Women in Disney's Feature Animation*. John Libbey Publishing.

- Davis, M. M. (2014). From Snow to Ice: A Study of the Progression of Disney Princesses from 1937 to 2014. *Film Matters*, 5, 48–52. https://doi.org/10.1386/fm.5.2.48_1
- Do Rozario, R.-A. C. (2004). The princess and the magic kingdom: Beyond nostalgia, the function of the Disney princess. *Women's Studies in Communication*, 27, 34–59. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07491409.2004.10162465>
- Duignan, B. (2023, August 29). *Judith Butler*. Encyclopædia Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/biography/Judith-Butler>
- Dundes, L., & Streiff, M. (2016). Reel Royal Diversity? The Glass Ceiling in Disney's Mulan and Princess and the Frog. *Societies*, 6(4), 35. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soc6040035>
- Dutka, E. (1995, February 9). Disney's History Lesson : 'Pocahontas' Has Its Share of Supporters, Detractors. *Los Angeles Times*. <https://www.latimes.com/archives/la-xpm-1995-02-09-ca-29997-story.html>
- Easteal, P. L. (2002). Looking through the Prevailing Kaleidoscope: Women Victims of Violence and Intersectionality. *Sister in Law, A Feminist Law Review*, 6, 48–77. <https://doi.org/10.5204/qutlr.v3i2.158>
- El-Tayeb, F. (2016). *Undeutsch. Die Konstruktion des Anderen in der postmigrantischen Gesellschaft*. transcript Verlag. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783839430743>
- England, D. E., Descartes, L., & Collier-Meek, M. A. (2011). Gender role portrayal and the Disney princesses. *Sex Roles*, 64, 555–567. <https://doi.org/10.1177/016344397019002010>
- Gabriel, M., & Goldberg, E. (1995). *Pocahontas* [Film]. Walt Disney Pictures & Walt Disney Feature Animation.
- Garabedian, J. (2014). Animating Gender Roles: How Disney is Redefining the Modern Princess. *James Madison Undergraduate Research Journal*, 2(1), 22–25. <http://commons.lib.jmu.edu/jmurj/vol2/iss1/4/>
- Gerbner, G., Gross, L., Morgan, M., Signorielli, N., & Shanahan, J. (2002). Growing up with television: Cultivation processes. In J. Bryant & D. Zillmann (Eds.), *Media effects: Advances in theory and research* (pp. 43–67). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates Publishers. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781410602428>
- Graves, S. B. (1999). Television and prejudice reduction: When does television as a vicarious experience make a difference? *Journal of Social Issues*, 55, 707–27. <https://doi.org/10.1111/0022-4537.00143>
- Hall, D., & López Estrada, C. (2021). *Raya and the Last Dragon* [Film]. Walt Disney Pictures & Walt Disney Animation Studios.

- Hall, S. (1992). The West and the Rest: Discourse and Power. In S. Hall & B. Gieben (Eds.), *Formations of modernity* (pp. 275–331). Polity Press.
- Hall, S. (1997a). *Race, The Floating Signifier*. Race, The Floating Signifier (Transcript).
<https://www.mediaed.org/transcripts/Stuart-Hall-Race-the-Floating-Signifier-Transcript.pdf>
- Hall, S. (1997b). *Representation: Cultural representations and signifying practices*. Sage Publications.
- Hankivsky, O. (2014). *Intersectionality 101*. The Institute for Intersectionality Research & Policy, SFU.
- Herbert-Pontonnier, É. (2019, October 1). “The finest girl in France” : The figure of Esmeralda, from Victor Hugo to the Disney studios. *Medium*.
<https://medium.com/@emilieherbertpontonnier/the-finest-girl-in-france-the-figure-of-esmeralda-from-victor-hugo-to-the-disney-studios-3c9b289232bf>
- Herman, D. (2016, December 2). How the Story of “Moana” and Maui Holds Up Against Cultural Truths. *Smithsonian Magazine*. <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/smithsonian-institution/how-story-moana-and-maui-holds-against-cultural-truths-180961258/>
- Hine, B., England, D., Lopreore, K., Horgan, E. S., & Hartwell, L. (2018). The Rise of the Androgynous Princess: Examining Representations of Gender in Prince and Princess Characters of Disney Movies Released 2009–2016. *Social Sciences*, 7(12), 245.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci7120245>
- Hoffmann, E. S. (2019). Diversity Dissected: Intersectional Socialization in Disney’s Aladdin, Mulan, and The Princess and the Frog. *Leviathan: Interdisciplinary Journal in English*, (5), 60–126. <https://doi.org/10.7146/lev.v0i5.115493>
- Hogg, M. A., Terry, D. J. & White, K. M. (1995). A tale of two theories: A critical comparison of identity theory with social identity theory. *Social Psychology Quarterly*, 58, 255–269. <https://doi.org/10.2307/2787127>
- Honour, H. (1976). *The New Golden Land: European Images of America*. Allen Lane.
- Johnson, R. M. (2015). *The evolution of Disney princesses and their effect on body image, gender roles, and the portrayal of love* [Master’s thesis, James Madison University]. Educational Specialist. <https://commons.lib.jmu.edu/edspec201019/6>
- Jordan. (2019). How Old are the Disney Princesses? *Mickey Project*. Retrieved September 18, 2023, from: <https://mickeyproject.com/how-old-are-the-disney-princesses/>

- Jordan-Zachery, J. S. (2007). Am I a black woman or a woman who is black? A few thoughts on the meaning of intersectionality. *Politics & Gender*, 3(2), 254–263. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1743923X07000074>
- Konnikova, M. (2014, June 25). How “Frozen” Took Over the World. *The New Yorker*. <https://www.newyorker.com/science/maria-konnikova/how-frozen-took-over-the-world>
- Koushik, K., & Reed, A. (2018). Star Wars: The Last Jedi, Beauty and the Beast, and Disney’s Commodification of Feminism: A Political Economic Analysis. *Social Sciences*, 7(11), 237. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci7110237>
- Lacroix, C. (2004). Images of Animated Others: The Orientalization of Disney’s Cartoon Heroines from The Little Mermaid to The Hunchback of Notre Dame. *Popular Communication*, 2(4), 213–229. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15405710pc0204_2
- Laemle, J. L. (2018). *Trapped in the Mouse House: How Disney has Portrayed Racism and Sexism in its Princess Films* [Student Research Paper, Gettysburg College]. Student Publications. https://cupola.gettysburg.edu/student_scholarship/692
- LiveLoveWrite18. (2023, April 20). 17 Changes Disney Made to "The Hunchback of Notre Dame". *ReelRundown*. Retrieved September 18, 2023, from: <https://reelrundown.com/animation/Where-Disney-Went-Wrong-Hunchback-of-Notre-Dame>
- Lotha, G. (2023, September 6). *The Thousand and One Nights*. Encyclopædia Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/The-Thousand-and-One-Nights>
- Luebering, J. E. (2023, July 2). *Disney Company*. Encyclopædia Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Disney-Company>
- Mansky, J. (2017, March 23). The True Story of Pocahontas. *Smithsonian Magazine*. <https://www.smithsonianmag.com/history/true-story-pocahontas-180962649/>
- Mark, J. J. (2020, September 7). Mulan: The Legend Through History. *World History Encyclopedia*. <https://www.worldhistory.org/article/1596/mulan-the-legend-through-history/>
- Marsh, S. (2016, March 23). The gender-fluid generation: young people on being male, female or non-binary. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/commentisfree/2016/mar/23/gender-fluid-generation-young-people-male-female-trans>
- Martin, C. L., Ruble, D. N., & Szkrybalo, J. (2002). Cognitive theories of early gender development. *Psychological bulletin*, 128(6), 903–933. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.128.6.903>

- Matyas, V. (2010). *Tale as old as time: A textual analysis of race and gender in Disney princess films* [Master's thesis, McMaster University]. Major Research Projects. <http://hdl.handle.net/11375/14406>
- Menise, T. (2019). Fairy tales between transformation and repetition: How audiences rethink the big romantic myth through Disney princess stories. *Sign Systems Studies*, 47(3/4), 526–551. <https://doi.org/10.12697/SSS.2019.47.3-4.08>
- Mikos, L. (2017). Film- und Fernsehanalyse. In L. Mikos & C. Wegener (Eds.), *Qualitative Medienforschung: Ein Handbuch* (pp. 515–523). UVK Verlagsgesellschaft.
- Moon, K. (2021, March 5). Raya and the Last Dragon Introduces Disney's First Southeast Asian Princess. Advocates Say Hollywood Representation Shouldn't Stop There. *Time*. <https://time.com/5944583/raya-and-the-last-dragon-southeast-asia/>
- Muir, R. (2022). 'Into the Unknown': Using facet methodology to explore the Disney Princess Phenomenon. *Methodological Innovations*, 15(2), 127–141. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20597991221090453>
- Musker, J., & Clements, R. (2009). *The Princess and the Frog* [Film]. Walt Disney Pictures & Walt Disney Animation Studios.
- Musker, J., & Clements, R. (2016). *Moana* [Film]. Walt Disney Pictures & Walt Disney Animation Studios.
- Parks, M. (2014, October 23). How Fourth-Wave Feminism is Changing Disney's Princesses. *Highbrow Magazine*. <https://www.highbrowmagazine.com/4388-how-fourth-wave-feminism-changing-disney-s-princesses>
- Peggy, O. (2006, December 24). What's Wrong with Cinderella? *The New York Times Magazine*. <http://www.nytimes.com/2006/12/24/magazine/24princess.t.html>
- Pehlke, S.-C. (2018). *Disneys neuer Geschlechtervertrag. Eine postfeministische Analyse der Prinzessinnenfigur* [Master's thesis, University of Vienna]. Universität Wien. <https://services.phaidra.univie.ac.at/api/object/o:1346850/get>
- Perea, K. (2018). Touching Queerness in Disney Films Dumbo and Lilo & Stitch. *Social Sciences*, 7(11), 225. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci7110225>
- Pitre, J. (2023). The Magical Work of Brand Futurity: The Mythmaking of Disney+. *Television & New Media*, 24(6), 712–729. <https://doi.org/10.1177/15274764221128923>
- Procter, J. (2004). *Stuart Hall*. Routledge.
- Pulver, A. (2016, May 26). How Disney's princesses got tough. *The Guardian*. <https://www.theguardian.com/film/2016/may/26/has-disney-finally-given-up-on-princesses>

- Randjelović, I. (2019). *Rassismus gegen Rom*nja und Sinti*zze*. Vielfalt-Mediathek.
https://www.vielfalt-mediathek.de/material/rassismus-gegen-romnja-und-sintizze/rassismus-gegen-rom_nja-und-sinti_zze
- Robinson, J. (2021, March 5). Raya and the Last Dragon’s Kelly Marie Tran Thinks Her Disney Princess Is Gay. *Vanity Fair*.
<https://www.vanityfair.com/hollywood/2021/03/raya-and-the-last-dragon-kelly-marie-tran-gay-namaari-raya>
- Rogers, A. S. (2019). Are Disney Characters ‘Frozen’ in Stereotypes? An Intersectional Analysis of Frozen. *Education Sciences & Society*, 10(2), 23–41.
<https://doi.org/10.3280/ess2-2019oa8427>
- Rousseau, J.-J. (1968). *The Social Contract*. Penguin.
- Said, E. W. (1978). *Orientalism*. Pantheon Books.
- Schilling, V. (2018, September 13). The True Story of Pocahontas: Historical Myths Versus Sad Reality. *Indian Country Today*. <https://ictnews.org/archive/true-story-pocahontas-historical-myths-versus-sad-reality>
- Schwob, M. (2013). *Genderkonstruktionen in Walt Disney’s Filmen nach 1990. Mediale Inszenierungen von Gender, Class, Race und Bodies in Aladdin, Pocahontas, Küsst den Frosch und Rapunzel – Neu verhöhnt* [Diploma thesis, University of Vienna]. Universität Wien. <https://services.phaidra.univie.ac.at/api/object/o:1298473/get>
- Staninger, C. (2003). Disney's Magic Carpet Ride: Aladdin and Women in Islam. In B. Ayres (Ed.), *The Emperor's Old Groove. Decolonizing Disney's Magic Kingdom* (pp. 65 –78). Peter Lang Publishing.
- Stuart Hall Foundation. (2023). *Stuart Hall*. Stuart Hall Foundation.
<https://www.stuarthallfoundation.org/stuart-hall/>
- Sun, C. F. (Writer), & Picker, M. (Director). (2001). *Mickey Mouse Monopoly: Disney, Childhood & Corporate Power* [Video]. Media Education Foundation.
- The Walt Disney Company (2020, March 2). *Disney - Leadership, History, Corporate Social Responsibility*. The Walt Disney Company.
<https://thewaltdisneycompany.com/about/#our-businesses>
- The Walt Disney Company. (2023). *FISCAL YEAR 2022 ANNUAL FINANCIAL REPORT*.
<https://thewaltdisneycompany.com/app/uploads/2023/02/2022-Annual-Report.pdf>
- Trousdale, G., & Wise, K. (1996). *The Hunchback of Notre Dame* [Film]. Walt Disney Pictures & Walt Disney Feature Animation.

- Tyler, A. (2021, March 21). All Former Disney Princesses Explained (& Why They No Longer Count). *Screen Rant*. <https://screenrant.com/disney-princesses-former-tinker-bell-esmeralda-removed-reasons/>
- Uppal, C. (2019). Over Time and Beyond Disney—Visualizing Princesses through a Comparative Study in India, Fiji, and Sweden. *Social Sciences*, 8(4), 105. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci8040105>
- Valdes, F. (1997). Foreword: Poised at the Cusp: LatCrit Theory Outsider Jurisprudence and Latina/o Self-Empowerment. *Harvard Latino Law Review*, 2, 1.
- Van Herk, K. A., Smith, D., & Andrew, C. (2011). Identity matters: Aboriginal mothers' experiences of accessing health care. *Contemporary Nurse*, 37(1), 57–68. <https://doi.org/10.5172/conu.2011.37.1.057>
- Weber, L. (2007). *Through a Fly's Eyes: Addressing Diversity in our Creative, Research, and Scholarly Endeavors*. Keynote, University-Wide Student Creativity, Research, and Scholarship Symposium, SUNY-Geneseo, April, 2007. Published by SUNY Geneseo Office of Research.
- Whelan, B. (2012). *Third Wave Princess: Reconstructing and Redefining the Traditional Princess Narrative* [PhD thesis, University of Louisiana at Lafayette]. University of Louisiana at Lafayette. <https://www.proquest.com/openview/1cd955833c331100a45b6ca2532eb0e5/1.pdf?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750>
- Wingfield, M., & Karaman, B. (1995). Arab stereotypes and American educators. *Social studies and the Young Learner*, 7(4), 7–10.
- Wormer, K. V., & Juby C. (2016). Cultural representations in Walt Disney films: Implications for social work education. *Journal of Social Work*, 16(5), 578–594. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468017315583173>

Statement of independent work

I certify that I have written the submitted Bachelor's thesis independently and without outside help, that I have not used any sources other than those indicated, and that I have identified the passages taken from the sources used as such. This Bachelor's thesis has not been submitted or published in this or a similar form in any other module.

A handwritten signature in black ink, consisting of stylized, cursive letters that appear to be 'MR'.

29 September 2023, Berlin

Appendix I. Analysis of the individual Disney characters

1. Jasmine from *Aladdin* (1992)

“Street-smart Aladdin and Princess Jasmine join forces to save the kingdom from the evil sorcerer Jafar. Along the way, Aladdin learns to believe in himself with help from a hilarious Genie... and three wishes that can change everything” (Disney+, 2023).

1.1. Background information about *Aladdin* (1992) and Jasmine

Aladdin (1992) was directed by John Musker and Ron Clements. It stars Scott Weinger as the protagonist Aladdin (with a singing voice provided by Brad Kane), Robin Williams as the Genie, Linda Larkin as the love interest Jasmine (with a singing voice provided by Lea Salonga) and Jonathan Freeman as the antagonist Jafar. None of these voice actors are of known Arab ancestry.

The film is based on the Arabic folktale “Aladdin and the Magical Lamp” from the *One Thousand and One Nights*, a collection of largely Middle Eastern and Indian stories of uncertain date and authorship¹⁰ (Lotha, 2023). *Aladdin* (1992)

was criticised by Arab Americans including American-Arab Anti-Discrimination Committee for its “light-skinned lead characters (with) Anglicized features and Anglo-American accents” and its stereotypical portrayal of Arab characters (Wingfield & Karaman, 1995).

Jasmine is the daughter of the Sultan of Agrabah, a fictional city in the Middle East. She is half orphaned, as the film implies that her mother is deceased. Informal sources (Auger, 2020; Jordan, 2019; Bologna, 2018) attribute to her the age of 15 years. She has a Bengal tiger named Raja as a sidekick.

1.2. Physical appearance of Jasmine

Jasmine is slender and lightly tanned. She has an extremely low waist-to-hip ratio of 0.4, as well as small hands and feet. She has voluminous black hair, long to her waist. She has an oval face, large almond-shaped brown eyes with curved eyelashes, black eyebrows, delicate and

Figure 1. “Original poster,” John Musker and Ron Clements, *Aladdin*, 1992.

¹⁰ It is noteworthy that the tales of Aladdin, Ali Baba, and Sindbad the Sailor have almost become part of Western folklore, though these were added to the collection only in the 18th century in European adaptations.

slightly curved nose and medium thick red lips. Her teeth are white and straight. Her ears are not visible.

For most of the film she wears a light blue two-piece suit. The top is an off-shoulder bandeau that covers her chest, leaving her shoulders and belly bare. The bottom is ankle-length wide pants, with a V-shaped waistband. The shoes are pointy brown slippers. She wears a light blue headband with a large blue gem, as well as large golden triangular earrings and a golden necklace. She usually wears her hair in a low ponytail with two equidistant blue headbands.

Figure 3. "Screenshots of 00:41:34 and 01:24:42 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

Jasmine is also seen in several more outfits, including a disguise as a commoner, a wedding announcement gown and a slave outfit.

Figure 4. "Screenshots of 00:18:27, 01:10:23, 01:16:47, and 01:25:23 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

1.3. Psychological traits of Jasmine

Jasmine is stubborn, rebellious and confrontative. She complains several times in the film about circumstances that she deems unfair (such as the law that forces her to marry a prince before her birthday, or her lack of autonomy living inside the palace). She also faces other characters, usually the antagonist Jafar.

Figure 5. "Screenshots of 00:13:24, 00:22:27, 00:23:49, 00:41:46, 00:53:52, 00:56:57, 01:00:56, 01:05:01, 01:12:06 and 01:16:04 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

She has a great desire for freedom and independence, expressing her wish to make her own choices and live her life for herself.

Figure 6. "Screenshots of 00:14:26, 00:16:41 and 00:21:50 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

She is also a fast learner (as stated by herself) and a fast thinker. Twice in the film, she quickly understands Aladdin's plans and plays along: the first time pretending to be mentally ill, so that she can avoid getting her hand cut off for stealing, and the second time pretending that she is in love with Jafar so as to distract him while Aladdin recovers the lamp. Moreover, while Aladdin is disguised as Prince Ali, she easily recalls his phrase "Do you trust me?" and later tricks him into revealing his true identity.

Figure 7. "Screenshots of 00:19:24, 00:21:02, 00:57:54, 01:00:52 and 01:17:33 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

Jasmine is flirty, sometimes sincerely and sometimes as a weapon (to ridicule Aladdin as Prince Ali or to distract Jafar).

Figure 8. "Screenshots of 00:22:34, 00:56:51, 01:00:22, 01:01:44, 01:02:03 and 01:16:48 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

She is also agile, although not physically strong.

Figure 9. "Screenshots of 00:20:59, 00:23:21 and 01:18:07 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

Moreover, she is kind to animals (such as birds and her pet tiger Rajah) and empathic (as shown by the fact that she offers an apple to a hungry child).

Figure 10. "Screenshots of 00:13:30, 00:16:46 and 00:18:21 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

1.4. Relevant actions of Jasmine

The first time Jasmine appears on film, she can be seen from far away, sitting next to a luxurious fountain in the gardens of the palace, accompanied by her pet tiger Rajah. It is understood that she has turned down yet another suitor to her hand, and is then being confronted by the Sultan. Her first line of dialogue is "Oh, Father! Rajah was just playing with him. Weren't you, Rajah?", followed by "You were just playing with that overdressed, self-absorbed Prince Achmed, weren't you?" in a playful tone. This establishes her as a casual character that does not abide by rules or etiquette and rejects egocentric people.

Figure 11. "Screenshots of 00:12:40, 00:16:46 and 00:12:57 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

She spends the rest of the scene complaining about the "wrong" law that forces her to marry a prince before her next birthday and stating: "If I do marry, I want it to be for love." She then complains that she has never left the palace, thus never doing anything on her own or having real friends, and protests that she maybe does not want to be a princess anymore. She proceeds to free a stock of birds from a cage, a metaphor for her desire for freedom.

Figure 12. "Screenshots of 00:13:20, 00:14:07 and 00:14:22 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

Jasmine disguises herself as a commoner and escapes the palace at night by climbing a tree and jumping the wall. While visiting the marketplace, she offers an apple to a hungry child, oblivious to the fact that she needs money to pay for that item. She is about to have her hand cut off as penalty for stealing when Aladdin rescues her, claiming that she is her sister and is “a little crazy”; she quickly understands his plan and plays along, escaping the situation.

Figure 13. “Screenshots of 00:16:39, 00:18:39 and 00:19:13 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

Aladdin brings Jasmine to the place where he lives. There she complains about the lack of freedom in the palace and coincides with Aladdin that they both feel trapped in their respective lives. They get physically close, but the guards interrupt them and they have to flee, Jasmine having to decide whether to trust Aladdin.

Figure 14. “Screenshots of 00:21:54, 00:22:50 and 00:23:00 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

The guards apprehend Aladdin; Jasmine’s attempt to free him by force ends with her being pushed to the floor. She then uses her status as a princess to try to have Aladdin released, but is referred to Jafar.

Figure 15. “Screenshots of 00:14:07 and 00:14:22 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

Back in the palace, Jasmine confronts Jafar and learns that Aladdin is allegedly being executed for kidnapping the princess. She is devastated and leaves weeping, feeling guilty for Aladdin’s alleged death.

Figure 16. "Screenshots of 00:24:25, 00:24:43, 00:24:53 and 00:25:31 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

After explaining the situation to the Sultan, he forces Jasmine and Jafar to make peace; she proceeds to threaten Jafar with her "getting rid of him" when she is married and queen, and storms out.

Figure 17. "Screenshots of 00:41:34 and 00:41:46 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

Aladdin has disguised himself as Prince Ali and parades in front of the palace, but Jasmine is not impressed. When she overhears the Sultan, Jafar and Aladdin discussing whether Prince Ali is worthy of marrying Jasmine, she is outraged for being treated as "a prize to be won".

Figure 18. "Screenshots of 00:50:34 and 00:53:52 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

At night, Aladdin uses his flying magic carpet to land on Jasmine's balcony. After initially rejecting him, ridiculing him and telling him to jump off, she is convinced to be taken on a ride after recognising Aladdin from his choice of words ("Do you trust me?").

Figure 19. "Screenshots of 00:55:39, 00:56:57 and 00:57:45 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

Jasmine and Aladdin fly over several countries, singing “A Whole New World” and admiring the wonders of the world. By the end of the song, both are emotionally and physically close.

Figure 20. “Screenshots of 00:59:00, 00:59:18, 01:00:01, 01:00:12 and 01:00:22 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

Admiring fireworks from a rooftop, Jasmine tricks Aladdin into revealing this identity to her and becomes angry with him, demanding that he tell her the truth. When Aladdin lies to her again and pretends to be a royal who has escaped from the palace, just like her, she gets physically close to him again.

Figure 21. “Screenshots of 01:00:43, 01:00:52, 01:01:04 and 01:01:37 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

Aladdin brings Jasmine back to the palace and they say goodbye. The flying magic carpet makes them kiss; although initially surprised, they both quickly give in and Jasmine goes back to her room smiling.

Figure 22. "Screenshots of 01:02:07, 01:02:09 and 01:02:11 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

Jasmine is ecstatic after her time with Aladdin. However, she becomes horrified when the hypnotised Sultan announces that she will marry Jafar. After Aladdin frees the Sultan from Jafar's hypnotic control and he is arrested, Jasmine and Aladdin are close to kissing again. Jasmine announces to the Sultan that she has chosen Prince Ali as a suitor.

Figure 23. "Screenshots of 01:04:44, 01:04:56 and 01:06:04 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

At the wedding announcement, Jasmine kisses Aladdin good luck on his nose. The event is interrupted by Jafar, who forces the Sultan and Jasmine to magically bow to him. He then reveals Aladdin's true identity to Jasmine while groping her.

Figure 24. "Screenshots of 01:10:27, 01:12:41 and 01:13:24 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

Jasmine is turned into Jafar's slave: she wears an extremely revealing outfit, is shackled and serves him fresh fruit on a plate. He proposes marriage to her, but she declines while throwing wine on him; she is pushed to the floor. She hears horrified how Jafar wishes to the Genie for her to be madly in love with him. Although this does not work, Jasmine plays along and flirts with Jafar in order to help Aladdin rescue her: she compliments him and approaches him seductively. As a last distracting resort, Jasmine kisses Jafar on the lips, being visibly disgusted.

Nevertheless, Jafar notices Aladdin's presence; Jasmine tries to physically stop Jafar, but is thrown to the floor again. She runs for the magical lamp, but he imprisons her inside a giant hourglass. Jasmine almost drowns in sand; Aladdin breaks the glass just in time.

Figure 25. "Screenshots of 01:15:41, 01:16:04, 01:16:18, 01:16:48, 01:17:52, 01:18:07, 01:18:25 and 01:21:07 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

After Jafar is defeated and everything reverts back to normal (including Jasmine's outfit), Jasmine professes her love for Aladdin. The Sultan changes the law on the spot, making it so that the princess can marry "whomever she deems worthy". Jasmine's last spoken words are: "I chose you, Aladdin". They are about to kiss, but are interrupted by the Genie. In the last scene, Jasmine and Aladdin sing in unison "A whole new world / For you and me" before kissing and flying off to the moon on the magic carpet.

Figure 26. "Screenshots of 01:24:48, 01:25:31, 01:25:35, and 01:25:42 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Aladdin, 1992.

2. Pocahontas from *Pocahontas* (1995)

“Inspired by a real-life Native American legend, free-spirited Pocahontas must “listen with her heart” to help her choose which path to follow” (Disney+, 2023).

2.1. Background information about *Pocahontas* (1995) and Pocahontas

Pocahontas (1995) was directed by Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg. It stars Irene Bedard as the protagonist Pocahontas (with a singing voice provided by Judy Kuhn), Mel Gibson as the love interest John Smith, David Ogden Stiers as the antagonist Governor Ratcliffe and Russell Means as Chief Powhatan (with a singing voice provided by Jim Cummings). Two voice actors are of Native American ancestry: Irene Bedard is of Iñupiat and Métis descent and Russell Means is of Oglala Lakota descent.

The film is set in 1607 in Virginia and based on the life of the

historical figure of Pocahontas, a Powhatan woman famous for her association with the colonial settlement at Jamestown. To ensure the accuracy of the film, Walt Disney Animation Studios consulted with historians and the primary Native American organization in Virginia (Dutka, 1995). However, the plot in the film is quite different from reality; throughout this section, footnotes will provide historical information to contrast with the depictions in the film.

In the film, Pocahontas¹¹ is the daughter of Chief Powhatan, a Native American leader¹². She is half orphaned, as the film implies that her mother is deceased. Informal sources (Auger, 2020; Jordan, 2019; Bologna, 2018) attribute to her the age of 18 years¹³. She has a raccoon called Meeko and a hummingbird called Flit as sidekicks.

2.2. Physical appearance of Pocahontas

Pocahontas is slender and “copper-skinned” (as the song “Colors of the Wind” states at 00:42:00). She has an hourglass figure with a developed bust and a waist-to-hip ratio of 0.5. She has straight black hair, long to her waist. Her face is angular and she has slanted, black and

Figure 2. “Original poster,” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, *Pocahontas*, 1995.

¹¹ In reality, Pocahontas was the nickname of Amonute or Matoaka (Mansky, 2017).

¹² In reality, Chief Powhatan was the leader of an alliance of more than 30 Algonquian-speaking Native Americans living in the eastern region of Virginia (Mansky, 2017).

¹³ In reality, Pocahontas was around 11 years old when the colonisers arrived (Schilling, 2018).

wide-set eyes, brown eyebrows, a straight nose and extremely full red lips. Her teeth are white and straight and her ears are small.

She wears a light brown tight-fitting dress with a strapless shoulder, long to the thighs, with a brown belt at the waist. She is barefoot and wears her hair loose. She has a red tattoo or bodypainting in the shape of a circle with spikes in her upper right arm. For most of the film, she wears her mother's necklace, a piece of jewellery made mostly of blue stones.

Figure 28. "Screenshots of 01:11:23 and 00:30:54 (left to right)," Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.

2.3. Psychological traits of Pocahontas

One of the most remarkable traits of Pocahontas is her mysticism, especially in connection with nature. The words that introduce her, spoken by the shaman of the tribe, are: "She has her mother's spirit. She goes wherever the wind takes her." She can "listen with her heart" to foresee the future or communicate in other languages, knows that "every rock and tree and creature / Has a life, has a spirit, has a name." She is portrayed close to animals at several points in the film.

Figure 29. "Screenshots of 00:08:06, 00:17:41, 00:32:28, 00:40:13, 00:40:31 and 00:40:47 (left to right, top to bottom)," Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.

Figure 30. "Screenshots of 00:41:03, 00:41:39, 00:46:12, 01:06:23 and 01:07:00 (left to right, top to bottom)," Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.

She is also extremely athletic, agile and physically active. She can be seen jumping off cliffs into the water, climbing trees, crawling close to the floor, jumping from rock to rock and, above all, running in the forest.

Figure 31. "Screenshots of 00:08:36, 00:17:41, 00:20:11, 00:29:50, 00:30:19, 00:31:41, 00:39:04, 00:54:10, 01:07:25 and 01:14:38 (left to right, top to bottom)," Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.

She is adventurous: excited about novelty, looking forward to what life has to offer her and rejecting the steady path. She is also very curious and interested in the way of life of John Smith.

Figure 32. "Screenshots of 00:10:59, 00:13:10, 00:14:13, 00:15:01, 00:21:11, 00:36:00 and 00:38:03 (left to right, top to bottom)," Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.

She is also madly in love with John Smith. She very quickly becomes physically close to him. Having seen each other once, she is already willing to meet him secretly behind her people's back. When the member of her tribe Kocoum is accidentally murdered in front of her, her biggest worry is that she is never going to see John Smith again. Lastly, she is willing to risk her life in order to save his after having seen each other four times in total.

Figure 33. "Screenshots of 00:41:17, 00:46:51, 00:49:19, 00:52:21, 01:01:42 and 01:07:47 (left to right, top to bottom)," Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.

Lastly, she is depicted as playful and light-hearted, especially at the beginning of the film.

Figure 34. "Screenshots of 00:09:17 and 00:10:26 (left to right)," Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.

2.4. Relevant actions of Pocahontas

As already mentioned, the first time Pocahontas is seen in the film happens after she has been linked with the wind. A breeze of leaves leads the camera to Pocahontas, who is standing on top of a cliff. The wind and the camera turn around her, showing her from every angle. Her first line of dialogue is: “He’s back, Flit.” directed at her pet hummingbird and referring to her father, who has recently come back from war. This establishes her as a character who is free-spirited and independent, but also with a strong connection with her family and tribe.

Figure 35. “Screenshots of 00:07:57 and 00:08:18 (left to right),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.

We quickly learn that her father Chief Powhatan wants her to marry the warrior Kocoum, but she finds him too “serious”¹⁴; she sings “Just Around the Riverbend” and states that instead of a smooth and steady life with Kocoum, she dreams of the novelty, the excitement and the adventure. She goes to visit Grandmother Willow, a sentient tree and Pocahontas’ advisor; she tells her about a dream she has been having, involving a spinning arrow, and asks what her path is. Grandmother Willow instructs her to “listen with her heart” and Pocahontas hears from the wind that “strange clouds” are coming; this premonition is immediately confirmed, as the clouds are the sails of the ships of the colonisers.

Figure 36. “Screenshots of 00:11:24, 00:14:26, 00:16:48 and 00:18:07 (left to right),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.

Pocahontas runs to see them, encounters John Smith and follows him on the sly until he discovers her. She runs away but he convinces her to stay; although they are initially unable to communicate, thanks to “listening with her heart” Pocahontas is immediately able to speak in English with John Smith. They speak about their respective cultures, Pocahontas being really

¹⁴ In reality, Pocahontas did marry Kocoum when she was around 14 years old, became pregnant soon and gave birth to a baby called little Kocoum (Schilling, 2018).

interested in what John Smith has to tell. However, when he implies that Pocahontas' people need to be taught by the colonisers how to live and openly calls them savages, she is enraged. Singing “Colors of the Wind”, she teaches him to appreciate nature and to realise that “we are all connected to each other”; at the end of the song, both are physically close. After hearing drumming, Pocahontas leaves running.

Figure 37. “Screenshots of 00:29:35, 00:30:34, 00:32:43, 00:37:02, 00:41:35 and 00:42:33 (left to right, top to bottom),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.

Pocahontas is collecting corn with her friend Nakoma when John Smith appears, looking for her. She is happy to see him again, asks Nakoma to keep the secret and takes him to visit Grandmother Willow. Pocahontas is clearly fond of John Smith: she is disappointed to learn that he might leave, is relieved that Grandmother Willow approves of him and wants to see him again; she wonders if he is the one her dream was pointing to. Back in the tribe, Pocahontas learns that several tribes have united to fight the colonisers. She unsuccessfully tries to convince Chief Powhatan to speak with them instead.

Figure 38. “Screenshots of 00:45:41, 00:48:58, 00:50:34 and 00:51:33 (left to right),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.

At night, she escapes to meet with John Smith; when Nakoma discovers her and tries to stop her, Pocahontas states that she is “trying to help her people”. Pocahontas and John Smith meet next to Grandmother Willow and she asks him to talk with her father to avoid fighting. When he agrees, she hugs him and they kiss. Kocoum was spying on them and, in a fit of jealousy, tries to kill John Smith; Pocahontas tries to separate them but is thrown to the floor. Thomas, a

colleague of John Smith, shoots and kills Kocoum to save John Smith¹⁵; Kocoum breaks Pocahontas' necklace, symbolising the breaking of understanding between their respective worlds. Pocahontas feels guilty for Kocoum's death and is worried that she will never see John Smith again.

Figure 39. “Screenshots of 00:56:23, 00:58:18, 00:58:47, 00:58:49, 00:59:13 and 01:01:42 (left to right, top to bottom),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.

Nakoma manages to get Pocahontas into the tent where John Smith is held captive, so that she can see him once more; she does not want to leave him, but he tells her: “No matter what happens to me, I’ll always be with you. Forever”. Desolated, Pocahontas visits Grandmother Willow, where she admits feeling lost; however, her racoon pet Meeko brings her John Smith’s compass, she recognises the spinning arrow from her dream and realises that it was pointing to him as her path to follow.

Figure 40. “Screenshots of 01:02:25, 01:05:39 and 01:06:17 (left to right, top to bottom),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.

She runs back and makes it just on time, throwing herself on John Smith and avoiding his execution on the hands of Chief Powhatan¹⁶. She declares her love for him and denounces the path of hatred; stating that she “speaks with a wisdom beyond her years” and praising her “courage and understanding”, Chief Powhatan’s releases John Smith and stops the impending

¹⁵ In reality, Kocoum was killed by the colonists briefly after Pocahontas was taken to England (Schilling, 2018).

¹⁶ In reality, the story about John Smith being rescued by Pocahontas from being executed by her father was written by himself. It is possible that he misinterpreted a ritual ceremony or even made this story up completely (Mansky, 2017).

war between the tribes and the colonisers. However, the antagonist Governor Ratcliffe tries to shoot Chief Powhatan and John Smith wounded when he intercepts the bullet.

Figure 41. “Screenshots of 01:07:12, 01:07:40 and 01:08:08 (left to right, top to bottom),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.

Pocahontas and her tribe bring presents to the colonisers and she bids farewell to an injured John Smith, who needs to go back home to survive. Pocahontas gets her mother’s necklace back, a metaphor for the repaired understanding between cultures. Pocahontas’ last words are “No matter what happens, I’ll always be with you... forever”, echoing those of John Smith; she kisses him and he sails back to England. Pocahontas runs to the cliff to wave him goodbye; the last frame turns into a framed drawing, mirroring the first frame of the film and lending the film an air of historical accuracy¹⁷.

Figure 42. “Screenshots of 01:11:23, 01:12:41, 01:13:34, 01:13:36, 01:15:14 and 01:15:31 (left to right, top to bottom),” Mike Gabriel and Eric Goldberg, Pocahontas, 1995.

¹⁷ In reality, when Pocahontas was around 15 or 16 years old, an English colonist called Captain Samuel Argall went to her village and threatened to attack it unless Pocahontas went “temporarily” with him; she had to leave her child behind and was never allowed to return. She was raped, became pregnant and had another son, Thomas. She was converted to Christianity and given the name Rebecca. She then married merchant John Rolfe (it is unclear whether for love or for his benefit) and was brought to England, where she was paraded to the English elites as a sign of friendship between colonists and Native Americans. She died at the age of 20, possibly from poisoning, before she could return to America (Schilling, 2018).

3. Esmeralda from *The Hunchback of Notre Dame* (1996)

“At the urging of his gargoyle pals, Quasimodo leaves the solitary safety of his Notre Dame tower and ventures out to find his first true friend, the gypsy beauty Esmeralda, who entrusts him with a secret. When the secret is discovered, Quasi fights to save the people and the city he loves. They, in turn, begin to see people for who they are, rather than how they appear” (Disney+, 2023).

3.1. Background information about *The Hunchback of Notre Dame* (1996) and Esmeralda

The Hunchback of Notre Dame (1996) was directed by Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise. It stars Tom Hulce as the protagonist Quasimodo, Demi Moore as the love interest Esmeralda (with a singing voice provided by Heidi Mollenhauer), Tony Jay as the antagonist Judge Claude Frollo, Kevin Kline as Esmeralda’s love interest Captain Phoebus and Paul Kandel as the narrator Clopin Trouillefou. None of these actors are of known Romani ancestry.

The film is set in Paris in 1482 and is based on the novel *The Hunchback of Notre-Dame*, written in 1831 by the French writer Victor Hugo. There are no records of Walt Disney Animation Studios consulting experts in Romani culture to ensure an accurate and sensitive representation; although there was not a big controversy at the time of release, some authors from inside and outside of the Romani community have criticised the caricaturised portrayal of Romani in the film (Herbert-Pontonnier, 2019; Crowe, 2015).

In the film, Esmeralda is a Romani dancer living in Paris. She has no known family. Informal sources (LiveLoveWrite18, 2023; courtney12015, 2015) attribute to her ages ranging from 19 to early twenties. She has the goat Djali as sidekick.

3.2. Physical appearance of Esmeralda

Esmeralda is slender and brown. She has an hourglass figure with a hip-to-waist ratio of 0.62 and a developed bust. She has voluminous wavy black hair, long to the middle of her back. She has an oval face with a broad chin, thick black eyebrows, huge green eyes with thick and short eyelashes, a narrow nose and medium thick peach lips. Her teeth are white and straight and her ears cannot completely be seen.

Figure 3. “Original poster,” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

She wears a white top with loose sleeves to her elbows and bare shoulders, a blue and gold bodice, a purple skirt long to her ankles with a darker layer decorated with golden circles. She is barefoot and often wears her hair tied with a purple ribbon as a headband. She also wears a golden hoop earring on one ear and golden bracelets or rings on her both wrists and one ankle.

Figure 44. "Screenshots of 00:38:25 and 0:27:05 (left to right)," Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

Esmeralda is also seen in several more outfits, including a disguise as a beggar, a changing robe and an execution gown.

Figure 45. "Screenshots of 00:18:32, 0:22:15, 00:23:47 and 01:23:07 (left to right, top to bottom)," Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

3.3. Psychological traits of Esmeralda

Esmeralda has a fiery, defiant and combative personality, both verbally as well as physically. She calls out injustice where she sees it. At the beginning of the film, when two soldiers try to seize her money on account of it being stolen, she protests and even kicks one in the face. She frees the protagonist Quasimodo when he is being harassed by the crowd, and publicly

denounces his unjust treatment. She almost insults her love interest Captain Phoebus, calling him a “son of a ...” before being interrupted, and then attacks him using a metal candleholder. She stops the execution of Quasimodo and Phoebus by screaming in the crowd. Briefly after, she insults the antagonist Judge Claude Frollo by calling him a liar. At her execution, Esmeralda rejects the advances of Judge Claude Frollo by spitting on his face.

Figure 46. “Screenshots of 00:17:27, 00:17:35, 00:27:58, 00:28:07, 00:28:23, 00:32:04, 00:32:28, 01:09:37, 01:10:45 and 01:12:09 (left to right, top to bottom),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

However, Esmeralda also has a caring and empathetic side, especially for those less fortunate. When Quasimodo walks in on her changing by mistake, she is more concerned with his well-being than her modesty. She tends to him when he is being harassed, and tries to change his self-image by stating that he has no “monster lines” on his hand. Her only song, “God Help the Outcast”, is a cry for God to show mercy on the outcasts, such as the Romani people.

Figure 47. “Screenshots of 00:22:10, 00:22:15 and 0:27:40 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

Figure 48. "Screenshots of 00:36:33 and 0:42:00 (left to right)," Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

Esmeralda is also cunning, smart and resourceful. She manages to go unnoticed three times in the film by disguising herself (and her goat Djali) as an old person. Seeing that ten soldiers are going to seize her, she pretends to be about to cry and then disappears in a puff of smoke, reappearing on the other end of the square with her head on a pumpkin basket. She uses the long pants of a stilt walker to stop a soldier from chasing her; not long after, she disappears by wrapping herself in a huge cloth. To avoid being seen by soldiers, she pretends to be a statue on the walls of Notre Dame. She is also seen using a slingshot and sewing up a wound on Captain Phoebus.

Figure 49. "Screenshots of 00:18:32, 00:28:41, 00:28:52, 00:29:38, 00:30:07, 00:31:17, 00:43:32, 00:52:23, 00:53:54 and 01:00:05 (left to right, top to bottom)," Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

Several times throughout the film, Esmeralda is shown being seductive and eager to establish body contact. In her first appearance, she stares at her love interest Captain Phoebus, teasingly raising an eyebrow. She sits on the chair arm of the antagonist Judge Claude Frollo, wraps his neck with a handkerchief, pulls him close, kisses him on the nose and then pulls his hat down

and goes away. She also places a hand on the protagonist Quasimodo's back and cheek, kisses him on the cheek to convince him of letting her see him again and hugs him twice. She puts a finger on Phoebus' lips to make him quiet, hugs him twice and kisses him twice.

Figure 50. "Screenshots of 00:17:14, 00:23:29, 00:41:36, 00:44:05, 00:59:17, 00:59:48, 01:00:34, 01:01:37, 01:10:07, 01:12:08, 01:22:35 and 01:23:47 (left to right, top to bottom)," Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, The Hunchback of Notre Dame, 1996.

Esmeralda is shown to be athletic, agile and physically strong. She is seen running away, swinging from and balancing on cages, pulling her love interest Captain Phoebus to the floor, holding her goat Djali both as she is being held by the protagonist Quasimodo as well as when she is descending with a rope. Lastly, she manages to hold on to Quasimodo and prevent him from falling into the void.

Figure 51. "Screenshots of 00:17:41, 00:29:08 and 00:29:14 (left to right)," Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, The Hunchback of Notre Dame, 1996.

Figure 52. “Screenshots of 00:31:50, 00:42:52, 00:44:28 and 01:21:12 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

Lastly, Esmeralda has a talent for dancing. As seen early in the film, she makes a living by dancing on the street. At the Festival of Fools, she displays incredible agility and flexibility. However, it is not her vocation – as she herself states, she would not be found “dancing in the streets for coins” if she had an alternative.

Figure 53. “Screenshots of 00:17:00, 00:19:48, 00:23:26, 00:23:36, 00:23:40, 00:23:45 and 00:39:54 (left to right, top to bottom),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

3.4. Relevant actions of Esmeralda

The first time Esmeralda is seen in the film, she is dancing on the street with a tambourine, accompanied by a man playing a wind instrument and her goat Djali; a passerby instructs her son to “stay away”, as they are “gypsies” and they are going to “steal (them) blind”. She is then seen from the perspective of her love interest and Captain of the Guard Phoebus: she spins around and looks at him teasingly. Esmeralda is alerted and she tries to run, but her money falls to the floor and the soldiers interrogate her on its source – that is when she speaks her first line of dialogue: “I earned it”, while pulling on the hat containing the coins. This establishes her as an attractive woman, aware of her attractiveness and willing to make use of it, who earns her living on the fringes of society and is ready to fend for herself.

Figure 54. “Screenshots of 00:17:00, 00:17:09, 00:17:20 and 00:17:27 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

She accuses the soldiers of stealing, resists and kicks one on the face. Her goat helps her out and she is able to run away; she looks amused as Phoebus embarrasses the soldiers.

Figure 55. "Screenshots of 00:17:33, 00:17:35, 00:17:41 and 00:17:57 (left to right)," Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

She manages to go unnoticed by disguising herself as an old beggar. Later, as Judge Claude Frollo comments on how gypsies "live outside the normal order", Esmeralda is seen dancing on the street with a tambourine together with the man playing a wind instrument and her goat Djali.

Figure 56. "Screenshots of 00:18:32 and 00:19:48 (left to right)," Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

Esmeralda is changing clothes in her tent as the protagonist Quasimodo falls inside and rips the curtain. Esmeralda manages to cover herself with a robe just in time and immediately asks him if he is alright. She guides him out of the tent in a friendly way and compliments him on (what she thinks is) his mask.

Figure 57. "Screenshots of 00:22:07, 00:22:13, 00:22:22 and 00:22:28 (left to right)," Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

In the Festival of Fools, Esmeralda appears in a cloud of smoke with an extremely tight dress, a tambourine and a handkerchief. She does her dancing routine, which includes her sitting next to Judge Claude Frollo, pulling him close with her handkerchief, kissing him on the nose and pushing him away; doing a cartwheel, a split and winking at Quasimodo, and stealing a spear from a soldier and using it to pole dance.

Figure 58. “Screenshots of 00:23:13, 00:23:17, 00:23:29, 00:23:34, 00:23:38, 00:23:41, 00:23:45, and 00:23:49 (left to right, top to bottom),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

She then assists in choosing the King of Fools by pulling Quasimodo on stage and taking off the masks of the candidates until making it to him and realising that it is his actual face.

Figure 59. “Screenshots of 00:24:31, 00:24:41 and 00:24:49 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

Esmeralda exits her tent and finds Quasimodo being harassed by the crowd; she approaches him, apologises to him and wipes him with her clothes. She disobeys Judge Claude Frollo and frees Quasimodo, recriminates him his mistreatment and accuses him of being cruel. She exclaims “justice” with her fist up as he tries to silence her, and calls him a “fool”.

Figure 60. “Screenshots of 00:27:42, 00:27:58 and 00:28:07 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

Figure 61. "Screenshots of 00:28:10 and 00:28:23 (left to right)," Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

As ten soldiers surround her, she pretends to cry, vanishes in a cloud of smoke and reappears in the other end of the square, mocking them. She proceeds to surf the crowd, hit three soldiers by swinging from a cage, roll on said cage, roll on a wheel board, jump and pull the pants of a stilt walker to stop another soldier, bow to the crowd, throw a helmet like a disc to hit some more soldiers, runs away and disappear by wrapping herself in cloth.

Figure 62. "Screenshots of 00:28:44, 00:28:45, 00:28:58, 00:29:11, 00:29:18, 00:29:39, 00:29:43 and 00:30:07 (left to right, top to bottom)," Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

She goes unnoticed again by pretending to be an old beggar and enters Notre Dame. She pulls Phoebus to the floor and threatens him with his own sword. He kicks her to the floor and she insults him, and proceeds to use a metal candleholder to attack him: she mocks him, almost hits his crotch and then hits instead his face.

Figure 63. “Screenshots of 00:31:17, 00:31:51, 00:32:02, 00:32:10, 00:32:29 and 00:33:00 (left to right, top to bottom),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

Esmeralda is surprised that Phoebus is not arresting her, tells him her name and gets closer. Judge Claude Frollo enters to arrest her, but Phoebus claims “sanctuary” for her and the archdeacon intercedes in her favour.

Figure 64. “Screenshots of 00:33:08, 00:33:19 and 00:33:34 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

Judge Claude Frollo sneaks up from behind, twists her arm, speaks with his face next to hers and sniffs her hair. Esmeralda interrogates his action and he caresses her neck while saying that he imagined her hanging. Esmeralda releases herself and counters him.

Figure 65. “Screenshots of 00:34:03, 00:34:14, 00:34:18 and 00:34:30 (left to right),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

Esmeralda is trapped inside of Notre Dame and has a conversation with the archdeacon, protesting the torturing of Quasimodo. She then sings “Gold Help the Outcast”, in which she asks God she selflessly asks for nothing except that he “help the outcasts / hungry from birth”, as well as “(her) people / the poor and down trod”.

Figure 66. “Screenshots of 00:35:01, 00:35:14, 00:35:55, 00:36:40, 00:37:31 and 00:38:13 (left to right, top to bottom),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

Esmeralda follows Quasimodo to apologise to him, finds his handmade miniature Paris and compliments him. She receives a tour though the bells and a view of the sunset. Esmeralda states that she cannot stay there forever, since she does not have freedom and “gypsies don’t do well behind stone walls” (echoing the words of Judge Claude Frollo). Esmeralda reads Quasimodo’s hand as a means of convincing him that he is not a “monster”, and that she is not “evil”.

Figure 67. “Screenshots of 00:39:28, 00:39:50, 00:40:44, 00:41:10, 00:41:20 and 00:41:48 (left to right, top to bottom),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

She agrees to be carried down the wall by Quasimodo while she carries her goat. Esmeralda invites Quasimodo to the “court of miracles” (the hideout of the Romani in the film) and then states that she will visit Quasimodo, kisses him on the cheek, gives him a necklace to find “court of miracles” and leaves.

Figure 68. "Screenshots of 00:43:28, 00:43:44, 00:44:05 and 00:44:09 (left to right)," Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, The Hunchback of Notre Dame, 1996.

Lusting over Esmeralda, Judge Claude Frollo has a vision of her in the fire, first dancing and then being burnt at the stake. He also envisions her as smoke leaving the fireplace, but she vanishes as he embraces her.

Figure 69. "Screenshots of 00:49:00 and 00:50:05 (left to right)," Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, The Hunchback of Notre Dame, 1996.

As the soldiers look for her, Esmeralda is hiding disguised as an old beggar. She seems distressed as Phoebus risks his life to rescue innocent people from being burnt alive, and then saves Phoebus from being executed by using a slingshot. She enters a river to rescue a wounded Phoebus.

Figure 70. "Screenshots of 00:53:27, 00:53:53, 00:54:30 and 00:54:37 (left to right)," Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, The Hunchback of Notre Dame, 1996.

Esmeralda asks Quasimodo for help hiding Phoebus. She then disinfects and sews up his wound while praising him for his courage; Phoebus declares his love for her and they kiss. Esmeralda has to run away but first makes Quasimodo promise that he will take care of Phoebus.

Figure 71. "Screenshots of 00:59:30, 00:59:54 and 01:00:20 (left to right)," Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, The Hunchback of Notre Dame, 1996.

Figure 72. "Screenshots of 01:00:34 and 01:01:32 (left to right)," Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

In the "court of miracles", Esmeralda stops the execution from Quasimodo and Phoebus on account of being spies. When Esmeralda finds out that they came to alert the Romani, she hugs Phoebus in gratitude, but soon the three are surrounded by soldiers and arrested.

Figure 73. "Screenshots of 01:09:39, 01:10:07 and 01:11:31 (left to right)," Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

Esmeralda is tied on the pyre and about to be burnt publicly. Judge Claude Frollo offers her to choose between him and the fire, and she responds by spitting on his face; the pyre is set on fire. Quasimodo rescues an unconscious Esmeralda, takes her to the top of Notre Dame and claims sanctuary. He places her on a bed and tries to have her wake up or drink water, but she does not react and he mourns her.

Figure 74. "Screenshots of 01:12:09, 01:13:17, 01:14:03, 01:14:33, 01:14:41, 01:18:25 and 01:18:43 (left to right, top to bottom)," Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

She does eventually wake up, but she is too weak and Quasimodo has to carry her around to run away from Judge Claude Frollo. At one point, it is Esmeralda's turn to hold onto an

unconscious Quasimodo, while Judge Claude Frollo threatens them both with a sword. She cannot hold Quasimodo any longer and he slips; her last line of dialogue is: “Quasimodo! Quasi! No!”; Quasimodo is however caught by Phoebus.

Figure 75. “Screenshots of 01:19:45, 01:20:10, 01:21:18, 01:21:42 and 01:21:44 (left to right, top to bottom),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

Esmeralda reunites with Quasimodo and Phoebus, hugs the former and kisses the latter. Phoebus and Esmeralda exit Notre Dame hand in hand to a cheering crowd. She invites Quasimodo to go out taking him by the hand and is happy to see that he is accepted by the crowd. The last time she is seen, she is next to Phoebus, holding Djali and cheerfully looking at Quasimodo.

Figure 76. “Screenshots of 01:22:08, 01:22:35, 01:22:44, 01:22:57 and 01:24:15 (left to right, top to bottom),” Gary Trousdale and Kirk Wise, *The Hunchback of Notre Dame*, 1996.

4. *Mulan* from *Mulan* (1998)

“Disguised as a male soldier, a young girl bravely takes her father’s place in the Imperial Army” (Disney+, 2023).

4.1. Background information about *Mulan* (1998) and *Mulan*

Mulan (1998) was directed by Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft. It stars Ming-Na Wen as the protagonist *Mulan* (with a singing voice provided by Lea Salonga), Eddie Murphy as the sidekick dragon Mushu, Miguel Ferrer as the antagonist Shan Yu and B. D. Wong as the love interest Captain Li Shang (with a singing voice provided by Donny Osmond). Two voice actors are of Chinese ancestry: Ming-Na Wen and B. D. Wong are of Chinese descent.

Figure 4. “Original poster,” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, *Mulan*, 1998.

The film is set in Imperial China and is based on the legend of Hua Mulan, which most likely originated in the Northern Wei Period (386-535 CE) of China before it was developed by succeeding authors (Mark, 2020). Although Walt Disney Animation Studios sent a number of artistic supervisors to China to receive artistic and cultural inspiration, *Mulan* (1998) depicts China “stripped of context and embed historical inaccuracies such as the episode with the matchmaker, the presence of the Huns, the presence of the shrine to the ancestors, the clothing, and presenting villains as darker-skinned” (Dundes, 2019, p. 230).

In the film, *Mulan* is a commoner living in a village with her father Fa Zhou, her mother Fa Li and Grandmother Fa. Informal sources (Auger, 2020; Jordan, 2019; Bologna, 2018) attribute to her the age of 16 years. She has the talking dragon Mushu, a cricket called Cri-Kee and a dog called Little Brother as sidekicks.

4.2. Physical appearance of *Mulan*

Mulan is slender and has light skin. She has a mostly straight figure with a waist-to-hip ratio of 0.75 and a relatively flat chest and narrow hips. She has straight black hair with varying length thought the film, from the middle of her back to her shoulders. Her face is oval and she has slanted black eyes with short and thick eyelashes, black arched eyebrows, a broad nose and medium thick peach lips. Her teeth are white and straight and her ears are small and slightly protruding.

Figure 78. "Screenshots of 00:03:27 and 01:14:22 (left to right)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, *Mulan*, 1998.

Throughout the film, Mulan is seen in a variety of different outfits, including her pyjamas, a dress for the matchmaker, an armour, a towel and a concubine dress.

Figure 79. "Screenshots of 00:04:32, 00:08:17, 00:18:53, 00:19:10, 00:35:13, 00:41:03, 00:44:25, 01:00:10, 01:09:30 and 01:13:05 (left to right, top to bottom)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, *Mulan*, 1998.

4.3. Psychological traits of Mulan

Mulan can be described as ingenious and clever. At the very start of the film, she is seen writing notes on her forearm as a means of cheating in the examination of the matchmaker; immediately after, she uses a self-made device to have her dog feed the chicken for her. She is also seen winning at a board game she encountered passing by; using two weights to climb a high pole; strategically using a single rocket to cause a snow avalanche and defeat the Huns; rescuing herself, Captain Li Shang and her horse using a rope and an arrow; disguising three of her fellow soldiers as concubines so as to enter the palace; planning how to defeat the antagonist Shan Yu with a rocket, stealing his sword with a fan and then running away using a lantern as a zip line. In the song “A Girl Worth Fighting For”, Mulan asks her fellow soldiers if they would like “a girl who’s got a brain / Who always speaks her mind”, indicating that intelligence and outspokenness are qualities that she values.

Figure 80. “Screenshots of 00:03:18, 00:03:41, 00:07:05, 00:40:28, 00:49:01, 00:55:53, 00:58:30, 01:09:59, 01:14:10, 01:14:27 and 01:15:01 (left to right, top to bottom),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.

Mulan is also characterised by her difficulty in fitting into the mould of “femininity” required of her at the beginning of the film. She is seen getting off the horse with disarrayed hair, struggling to fit into the dress she wears for the matchmaker’s examination, looking with displeasure at her made-up face and trying to keep up with the poise of other girls. In the song “Reflection”, she wonders when her reflection will show who she is inside. However, she also catastrophically fails at fitting into the mould of “masculinity” when enrolling in the army: she handles her sword clumsily, walks in an uncoordinated manner and tries to unsuccessfully spit.

Figure 81. “Screenshots of 00:05:57, 00:07:17, 00:07:41, 00:08:43, 00:13:09, 00:27:11, 00:29:23 and 00:34:21 (left to right, top to bottom),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.

Mulan is portrayed in a down-to-earth and not very glamorous way, sometimes being the butt of the joke. Right after writing the word “punctual”, Mulan ironically realises that she is being late; she is seen with a full mouth, huge cheeks and food on her chin as Mushu asks to see her “war face”; in the montage that accompanies the song “I’ll Make A Man Out Of You”, she is seen fighting blindly with a dirty bucket on her head, being exhausted with a black eye and having a rocket explode in her arms. Lastly, after bathing with three of her fellow soldiers and stating that she “never want(s) to see a naked man again” (00:44:25), several more naked man run in front of her.

Figure 82. "Screenshots of 00:03:23, 00:35:41, 00:38:56, 00:39:22, 00:39:36 and 00:44:28 (left to right, top to bottom)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, *Mulan*, 1998.

She is also shown to be insecure and fearful, especially at the beginning of the film. Upon seeing Mushu's enlarged shadow, Mulan screams and hides. Before joining the army, she admits to being nervous. Each time that she is faced with physical confrontation, she throws herself to the ground and covers herself or tries to hide behind her hands.

Figure 83. "Screenshots of 00:27:28, 00:28:57, 00:33:08 and 00:36:35 (left to right)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, *Mulan*, 1998.

A core trait of Mulan is her love for her father Fa Zhou. At the beginning of the film, she makes sure that he follows the recommendations of the doctor. When he is called to fight, Mulan comes between the emissary and Fa Zhou and tries to avoid his drafting. She decides to take his place in the army and risk her own life in order to save his. When it is discovered that she is a woman, Mulan explains that she "did it to (save) her father" straight away. At the end of the film, when she goes back to her village, it is presumed that the first thing she does is pay her respects to Fa Zhou.

Figure 84. "Screenshots of 00:04:41, 00:15:22 and 00:19:08 (left to right)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, *Mulan*, 1998.

Figure 85. "Screenshots of 01:00:34 and 01:19:18 (left to right)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, *Mulan*, 1998.

It is also remarkable that Mulan has a strong sense of responsibility and justice, intervening when she sees a situation that she deems unfair although it does not directly concern her. For example, at the beginning of the film, she retrieves a doll that was stolen from a little girl in the street and gives it back to her. When she sees that the Huns have survived the avalanche and are heading towards the Imperial City, she states that she "ha(s) to do something", although she has just been left behind by the army and intended to go back home. In the final battle, instead of saving herself and leaving an unconscious Captain Li Shang behind, she puts her life at risk to save him.

Figure 86. "Screenshots of 00:07:32, 01:05:38 and 01:12:35 (left to right)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, *Mulan*, 1998.

Mulan is also respectful to the deceased and is seen paying her respects to them several times in the film: after failing at the matchmaker's examination, before running away and taking her father's place in the army and after finding a little doll in a village razed to the ground by the Huns.

Figure 87. "Screenshots of 00:13:00, 00:18:31 and 00:52:35 (left to right)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, *Mulan*, 1998.

4.4. Relevant actions of Mulan

The first time Mulan is seen in the film, she is in her pyjamas, eating rice and preparing for the matchmaker's examination by reciting and writing down on her forearm: "Quiet and demure.

Graceful. Polite. Delicate. Refined. Poised. Punctual!"; she immediately realises that she is late. This frames her as being an unconventional girl who is nevertheless trying to fit into what is expected of her.

Figure 88. "Screenshots of 00:03:06, 00:03:10 and 00:03:23 (left to right)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, *Mulan*, 1998.

Mulan sets up a device that has her pet dog feed the chicken for her. She then brings tea to her father, making sure that he is following the doctor's recommendations, and promises him not to disappoint him regarding the matchmaker's examination.

Figure 89. "Screenshots of 00:03:41, 00:04:41 and 00:04:54 (left to right)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, *Mulan*, 1998.

She goes to the city by horse, meeting her mother and grandmother, and arrives in a dishevelled state. During the song "Honor to Us All" she is unpleasantly bathed, combed and made up; in the montage she is seen easily winning at a board game and returning a doll to a girl who had it stolen by other children. Mulan asks her ancestors for help, so that she does not "uproot (her) family tree" and "keep(s) (her) father standing tall".

Figure 90. "Screenshots of 00:05:55, 00:06:20, 00:06:46, 00:07:17, 00:07:40 and 00:08:22 (left to right, top to bottom)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, *Mulan*, 1998.

When meeting the matchmaker, she is admonished for speaking without permission. The matchmaker states that she is too skinny and “not good for bearing sons”. Mulan tries her best reciting the final admonition and serving tea, but ends up setting the matchmaker’s dress on fire and throwing the tea on her face; the matchmaker calls her a disgrace.

Figure 91. “Screenshots of 00:09:28, 00:10:38 and 00:11:04 (left to right),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.

Back home and ashamed, Mulan sings “Reflection”, where she states that she cannot play the part of the perfect bride or daughter; in her family temple, whipping her make-up off and undoing her hair, she asks when her reflection will show who she is inside.

Figure 92. “Screenshots of 00:12:12, 00:13:09 and 00:13:18 (left to right),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.

Her father consoles her; they are interrupted by emperor’s emissaries. Mulan is told to stay inside, but she climbs the wall and sees that her father is being drafted. She runs out and asks for Fa Zhou to be spared, since he has already fought; her father feels dishonoured by her and accepts the scroll. Mulan secretly sees how her father tries to wield his sword and collapses.

Figure 93. “Screenshots of 00:13:47, 00:15:00, 00:15:22 and 00:16:17 (left to right),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.

At dinner table, she protests in front of her family that Fa Zhou should not have to go to war, and he admonishes her. Desolated, she runs to the garden and is soaked by the rain. After visiting the family temple, Mulan steals her father’s scroll, cuts her hair, dresses in soldier armour, grabs the sword and runs away of home on her horse.

Figure 94. "Screenshots of 00:16:58, 00:17:11, 00:17:44, 00:18:58 and 00:19:27 (left to right, top to bottom)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.

Mulan is close to the regiment's camp and rehearsing how to behave manly, with poor results, when Mushu reveals himself to her. She is scared at first, and then disappointed, but she confides her insecurities to him and accepts his help.

Figure 95. "Screenshots of 00:27:11, 00:28:15 and 00:29:20 (left to right)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.

Mulan enters the camp trying to walk "manly" and exclaims that man are "disgusting" upon seeing people picking their nose with the finger or scratching between the toes with chopsticks. Following Mushu's advice, she punches a fellow soldier and inadvertently starts a fight in the whole camp. Captain Li Shang stops the brawl and finds Mulan at the centre of it. She apologises in a "manly" way and lies about her name being Ping.

Figure 96. "Screenshots of 00:29:29, 00:33:05, 00:33:19 and 00:34:05 (left to right)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.

Mulan is woken up and fed breakfast by Mushu, quickly gets dressed and joins the other soldiers. Before she is punched as vengeance for the fight of the day before, Shang starts with

his training. At the beginning, Mulan is being bullied by other soldiers; she is weak and does not know how to fight or shoot arrows or rockets.

Figure 97. “Screenshots of 00:35:35, 00:36:32, 00:38:02, 00:38:43 and 00:40:03 (left to right, top to bottom),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.

She is at one point discharged because she is unsuited, but she figures out a way to climb a high pole using ingenuity instead of pure strength; the other soldiers find her at the top at the break of dawn and applaud her. Mulan starts being faster, stronger, more resistant and better at fighting, as well as getting along with the others.

Figure 98. “Screenshots of 00:40:13, 00:40:28, 00:40:39, 00:40:47 and 00:40:54 (left to right, top to bottom),” Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.

Mulan takes a bath in a lake because “look(ing) like a man doesn’t mean (she) ha(s) to smell like one”. To her surprise, three fellow soldiers join her; she is visibly uncomfortable and leaves as soon as she can. She hears how Shang being scolded by the emperor’s counsel and tries to

cheer him up, to no avail; Mushu accuses her of liking Shang and she denies that, but smiles to herself.

Figure 99. "Screenshots of 00:42:18, 00:43:13, 00:44:16 and 00:45:28 (left to right)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, *Mulan*, 1998.

The regiment marches to the war front singing "A Girl Worth Fighting For"; Mulan feels uncomfortable because of the insinuation that the girls in her hometown might have found her attractive, as well as the attention she receives from female farmers. In shock, they discover that the Huns have defeated the main army (lead by the father of Shang), destroyed a whole village and left no survivors behind. Mulan expresses her condolences to Shang, and pays her respects to the deceased by placing a little doll she found in the destroyed village next to the sword and helmet of the father of Shang.

Figure 100. "Screenshots of 00:48:33, 00:48:50, 00:50:29, 00:51:49 and 00:52:35 (left to right, top to bottom)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, *Mulan*, 1998.

As the regiment marches to the Imperial City to protect the emperor, Mushu lights a rocket by mistake and causes the Huns to attack them. Mulan saves her horse and counterattacks together with the other soldiers; the soldiers are outnumbered by the Huns and will be forced into hand-to-hand combat, but Mulan takes the last rocket and, instead of firing it at leader of the Huns Shan Yu directly, she causes a snow avalanche that buries the Huns. Mulan takes a sword wound to the side by Shan Yu, but she still manages to rescue herself, Shang, her horse, Mushu and her cricket. Just as Shang declares his trust in her, Mulan becomes aware of the bleeding wound and passes out.

Figure 101. "Screenshots of 00:53:37, 00:55:31, 00:56:17, 00:56:38, 00:57:08, 00:58:52 and 00:59:35 (left to right, top to bottom)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, *Mulan*, 1998.

It is discovered that Mulan is a woman and is called a "treacherous snake" by the emperor's counsel. Mulan reveals her real name and explains apologetically that she pretended to be a man and joined the army to save her father. Out of a sense of debt, Shang does not execute her, but instead leaves her behind.

Figure 102. "Screenshots of 01:00:15, 01:00:32, 01:01:05 and 01:01:35 (left to right)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, *Mulan*, 1998.

Mulan regrets leaving home and reflects that her true motive was to prove that she "could do things right" and thus see herself as worthwhile; she cries upon stating that she was wrong. Mushu consoles her, Mulan decides to go back home and they hug. However, she discovers that some Huns have survived and will attack the emperor and rides to the Imperial City.

Figure 103. "Screenshots of 01:02:23, 01:02:56, 01:03:57, 01:04:10 and 01:05:56 (left to right, top to bottom)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, *Mulan*, 1998.

Mulan tries to warn Shang, who does not believe her, and reproaches to him that he would have trusted Ping. Mulan tries to find someone who listens to her, to no avail.

Figure 104. "Screenshots of 01:06:46, 01:06:56 and 01:08:19 (left to right)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.

After the Huns have entered the palace and blocked the entrance, she convinces three befriended soldiers to dress as concubines together with her; Shang joins them and they climb using Mulan's technique. They trick and fight with the Huns and manage to evacuate the emperor, but Shang is rendered unconscious; instead of escaping, Mulan provokes Shan Yu revealing her identity as Ping. She runs away and improvises: she climbs on the roof using a column that Shan Yu cut, calculates the trajectory of the rocket, steals Shan Yu's sword using a fan, makes him fall to the ground and pins him with his sword so that the rocket lighted up by Mushu collides with him. She runs and jumps to get off the roof just on time, ziplines using a lamp and lands on Shang.

Figure 105. "Screenshots of 01:10:14, 01:11:36, 01:12:55, 01:13:07, 01:13:49, 01:14:40 and 01:14:53 (left to right, top to bottom)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, Mulan, 1998.

The emperor's counsel states that Mulan "will never we worth anything" because she is a woman, but the emperor thanks her and bows to her, prompting everybody else to also do so. Mulan is offered to be a member of the emperor's council, but she declines it to go back home. She receives the emperor's crest and Shan Yu's sword as gifts; she hugs the emperor and her soldier friends. Shang compliments her on fighting good; Mulan seems disappointed and rides her horse back home.

Figure 106. "Screenshots of 01:16:35, 01:16:44, 01:17:26, 01:17:45, 01:17:58 and 01:18:12 (left to right, top to bottom)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, *Mulan*, 1998.

At home, Mulan presents the gifts to her father as honour reparations, but he hugs her and states that having her as a daughter is the "greatest gift and honour"; Mulan cries and they hug again, saying how much they have missed each other. Shang shows up to give Mulan her helmet back and Mulan invites him to stay for dinner.

Figure 107. "Screenshots of 01:19:35, 01:19:41, 01:19:47 and 01:20:26 (left to right)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, *Mulan*, 1998.

The last line of dialogue of Mulan is "Thanks, Mushu", followed by a kiss on his forehead. As a callback to the start of the film, the dog and chickens run into the temple, startling Mulan.

Figure 108. "Screenshots of 01:21:14, 01:21:16 and 01:21:23 (left to right)," Barry Cook and Tony Bancroft, *Mulan*, 1998.

5. Tiana from *The Princess and the Frog* (2009)

“A modern twist on a classic tale from Walt Disney Animation Studios features a beautiful girl named Tiana who dreams of owning her own restaurant. When she meets a frog prince who desperately wants to be human again, a fateful kiss leads them both on a hilarious adventure through the mystical bayous of Louisiana” (Disney+, 2023).

5.1. Background information about *The Princess and the Frog* (2009) and Tiana

The Princess and the Frog (2009) was directed by John Musker and Ron Clements. It stars Anika Noni Rose as the protagonist Tiana, Bruno Campos as the love interest Prince Naveen and Keith David as the antagonist Dr. Facilier. Anika Noni Rose and Keith David are African American and Bruno Campos is Brazilian.

The film is set in New Orleans in the 1920s and is based on the German fairy tale of “The Frog Prince” by the Brothers Grimm. Walt Disney Animation Studios consulted with Oprah Winfrey

(and cast her as Tiana’s mother Eudora) and unspecified members of the NAACP (National Association for the Advancement of Colored People) so as to ensure a sensitive portrayal of race (Breaux, 2017, p. 402).

In the film, Tiana is a working-class African American woman. She lives with her mother Eudora, as her father James is deceased. Informal sources (Auger, 2020; Jordan, 2019; Bologna, 2018) attribute to her the age of 19 years. She has the talking trumpet-playing alligator Louis and the talking Cajun firefly Ray as sidekicks.

5.2. Physical appearance of Tiana

Tiana has dark skin and a slender, hourglass figure with a waist-to-hip ratio of 0.5. She has black, curly hair of undetermined length, since she always wears it tied or up. She has an oval face with enormous, round, brown eyes with thick and curved eyelashes, thin black eyebrows, rosy cheeks, a broad nose, thick red lips and dimples. Her teeth are white and straight and her ears are small and slightly protruding.

Figure 5. “Original poster,” John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Figure 110. "Screenshots of 00:25:34, 01:21:16 and 00:11:22 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Throughout the film, Tiana is seen in a variety of different outfits, including her dress and pyjama as a little girl, two different waitress uniforms, two different princess costumes and two different wedding gowns.

Figure 111. "Screenshots of 00:02:22, 00:06:05, 00:06:43, 00:08:16, 00:12:17, 00:23:51, 01:18:16, 01:28:06, 01:28:31, 01:28:58 and 01:29:45 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

5.3. Psychological traits of Tiana

Tiana is shown to be extremely hard-working, even a workaholic. In order to get her own restaurant, she has two jobs as a waitress, working night and day and taking double shifts. When she gets turned into a frog and needs to find a voodoo priestess in the bayou to break the spell, she is the one that keeps the team moving forward, while his love interest Prince Naveen takes on a contemplative role. At the end of the film, she and Naveen are seen renewing an old mill and turning it into a restaurant on their own. Tiana also states her work ethic several times throughout the film.

Figure 112. "Screenshots of 00:06:39, 00:07:18, 00:08:16, 00:09:48, 00:33:05, 00:36:10, 00:40:24, 00:50:20, 01:05:50 and 01:29:09 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Closely related to her strict work ethic is her rejection or outright disdain for things she considers "distractions", such as leisure or entertainment. She is annoyed when she is stopped by a street band on her way to work and is shown scoffing at an ukelele-playing Naveen. She declines her peer's the invitation to dance, later stating to her mother that she has no time for that. She also judgementally side-eyes Naveen when he sings about his partying lifestyle.

Figure 113. "Screenshots of 00:07:50, 00:09:21 and 00:09:58 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Figure 114. "Screenshots of 00:13:37 and 00:39:44 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Tiana is ambitious and dreams big: she wants to open her own restaurant in an old mill. She talks about it throughout the film with several characters, such as her mother Eudora, her friend alligator Louis or her love interest Prince Naveen. The antagonist Dr. Facilier also confirms that when she dreams, she “dreams big”.

Figure 115. "Screenshots of 00:13:01, 00:15:13, 00:42:58, 01:10:28 and 01:18:47 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

She is also shown to be determined to make her dreams come true. She knows what she wants and does not give up, even if she is met with scepticism by other characters. Apart from working tirelessly and saving money, she is even willing to wish upon a star or kiss a frog if that means that she is getting her restaurant.

Figure 116. "Screenshots of 00:13:15, 00:14:01 and 00:24:50 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Figure 117. "Screenshots of 00:26:47 and 00:29:24 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Since childhood, Tiana has a talent for cooking. As a child, she is shown helping her father improve the taste of a gumbo. In a sequence where Tiana imagines herself in her future restaurant, she is seen helping the cooks, micing vegetables and whipping cream. In the bayou, she manages to cook a gumbo using utensils and ingredients she finds around. She also helps the voodoo priestess Mama Odie improve the taste of her gumbo.

Figure 118. "Screenshots of 00:26:47, 00:26:47, 00:26:47, 00:26:47, 00:26:47 and 00:29:24 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Another core trait of Tiana is her love for her deceased father James. As a child, they both dream about opening a restaurant together; when he passes away, she takes up on the mission. The voodoo priestess Mama Odie and the antagonist Dr. Facilier also show Tiana images of James, demonstrating how important her father is to Tiana.

Figure 119. "Screenshots of 00:05:00, 00:07:04 and 00:13:19 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Figure 120. "Screenshots of 01:04:50 and 01:20:01 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Tiana has a sense of humour and is described by her love interest Prince Naveen as being “funny”. This humour is sometimes sarcastic, remarking on the irony of the situation; sometimes it is in form of actual jokes, such as when she states “I’ll talk to the owner”, pause and continues “Owner says yes” indicating that she just talked with herself. She often uses her humour to creatively insult or tease Prince Naveen.

Figure 121. "Screenshots of 00:27:03, 00:33:02, 00:45:58, 00:51:34, 00:54:55, 00:55:45, 01:10:42 and 01:28:18 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Tiana is also shown to be fierce when she gets angry or impatient. Several characters are the objects of her fierceness, such as the realtors who own the old mill she wants to buy, her love interest Prince Naveen, her friend alligator Louis, the voodoo priestess Mama Odie or the

antagonist Dr. Facilier. She is shown being loud or signalling the intention to aggression, but she never physically assaults anyone.

Figure 122. “Screenshots of 00:24:35, 00:28:01, 00:30:05, 00:33:28, 00:46:18, 00:51:20, 01:01:33 and 01:20:28 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Lastly, Tiana is close to her childhood best friend Lottie. Although Lottie comes from a white wealthy family and has been spoiled her whole life, Tiana never displays signs of jealousy or envy towards her, always being understanding and supportive of her.

Figure 123. “Screenshots of 00:02:44, 00:11:22, 00:22:54 and 00:59:58 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

5.4. Relevant actions of Tiana

The first time Tiana is seen in the film, she is a small child listening to the fairy tale “The Frog Prince” being told by her mother Eudora together with her best friend Lottie; although both are dressed up as princesses, her clothes are much simpler. Tiana is disgusted by the description of the princess kissing the frog and states “There is no way in this whole wide world I would ever,

ever, ever... I mean, never kiss a frog. Yuck!”. This establishes her as being from the working class and being dismissive of fairy tale magic.

Figure 124. “Screenshots of 00:01:31, 00:01:54 and 00:02:15 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Tiana and Eudora go back to their house in a poor neighbourhood and Tiana helps her father James cook gumbo, inviting their neighbours to eat. James and Tiana dream about opening a restaurant together; James insists on the importance of hard work, together with “wishing upon a star”, to make dreams come true. Tiana is put to sleep, but wakes up to make a wish on the Evening Star; she is then startled by a frog and runs away.

Figure 125. “Screenshots of 00:03:54, 00:04:24, 00:04:43, 00:05:18 and 00:06:24 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Tiana re-enters the room as a young woman, dressed as a waitress and exhausted. She puts her tips in a jar and drops on the bed before being immediately woken up and going to her next shift with the streetcar.

Figure 126. “Screenshots of 00:06:39, 00:06:49 and 00:07:40 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

She is shown to be a proficient waitress: fast, friendly and attentive. Some peers invite her to dance, but she declines because she has to work. The cook makes fun of her for ever thinking that she will own a restaurant.

Figure 127. “Screenshots of 00:07:58, 00:10:03 and 00:10:22 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Upon hearing that Lottie is hosting a masquerade ball and wants to “catch” Prince Naveen of Maldonia, Tiana advises her to reach his heart “though his stomach”; Lottie hires Tiana for the ball and gives her enough money to get her restaurant.

Figure 128. “Screenshots of 00:10:49, 00:11:28 and 00:11:49 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Tiana closes a deal with the realtors that own the old mill where she wants to open the restaurant. Eudora visits Tiana and brings her James’ gumbo pot; Tiana hugs her and tears up. Eudora is sceptic of the old mill and wants Tiana to work less and meet her “Prince Charming”, but Tiana is convinced of the place’s potential and sings “I’m Almost There”, where she envisions her dream restaurant.

Figure 129. “Screenshots of 00:12:14, 00:12:33 and 00:12:55 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Figure 130. "Screenshots of 00:13:41 and 00:14:07 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Tiana is dressed up as a princess and serving beignets in the masquerade ball. She supports Lottie when she is distressed because Prince Naveen is not showing up, and seems happy when Lottie gets to dance with "him" (actually Naveen's valet). The realtors announce to Tiana that she was outbid and is not getting the old mill, because such business is too big for "a little woman of her background". Tiana falls on the table and gets her costume dirty.

Figure 131. "Screenshots of 00:22:23, 00:23:06, 00:24:43 and 00:24:57 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Lottie lends her another more luxurious princess costume. Tiana is discouraged and starts crying, and reluctantly resorts to making a wish on the evening Star. She gets scared by a talking frog who happens to be Prince Naveen; he offers her "a reward" in exchange for a kiss and Tiana, though disgusted, brings herself to kiss him.

Figure 132. "Screenshots of 00:26:29, 00:26:47, 00:27:14, 00:29:20 and 00:29:31 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

She is transformed into a frog and is disgusted and angry. Tiana and Naveen have to run away from the party, with Prince Naveen lifting her before she gets eaten by a dog. Tiana is furious at Naveen and reveals that she is a waitress, not a princess; they both fall into the bayou and Tiana removes a leech from him. They are almost eaten by several animals but manage to escape; Tiana helps Naveen hide.

Figure 133. "Screenshots of 00:29:53, 00:30:40, 00:31:06, 00:33:40, 00:34:03, 00:34:21 and 00:35:27 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

The next morning, Tiana has built a raft to get them back to New Orleans and break the spell. They meet the trumpet-playing alligator Louis and decide to head to the voodoo priestess Mama Odie to regain their human shapes. As they sing "When We Are Human", Tiana states her strong work ethic. Tiana cannot avoid her tongue following a bug and ends up tangled with Naveen. Louis makes it worse, but a Cajun firefly named Ray unties them and shows them the way to Mama Odie. After Tiana reproaches Naveen how lazy he is and how hard her life has been, three frog hunters attack them and put Tiana in a cage. Naveen helps her out and they both trick the hunters into hurting each other.

Figure 134. "Screenshots of 00:36:01, 00:40:53, 00:43:57, 00:44:26, 00:51:47, 00:52:51 and 00:54:13 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Tiana and Naveen become friendlier; Tiana instructs Naveen how to mince mushrooms as she cooks a gumbo, and in return, Naveen convinces Tiana to dance. They are about to kiss, but Tiana distances herself out of deference to Lottie.

Figure 135. "Screenshots of 00:55:03, 00:56:25, 00:59:02, 00:59:30, 00:59:51 and 00:59:58 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

They find Mama Odie and ask her to turn them back to humans. Tiana helps Mama Odie with her magic gumbo and the voodoo priestess then instructs them in the difference between wanting and needing in the song "Dig a Little Deeper". Tiana concludes that she needs to work even harder to get her restaurant, to everyone's dismay. She learns that Naveen has to kiss Lottie before midnight in order to break the spell.

Figure 136. "Screenshots of 01:00:56, 01:02:43 and 01:05:50 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Tiana and her team board a riverboat to get to New Orleans, accidentally hugging while hiding from humans. Tiana is touched that Naveen has prepared a romantic dinner for them two and finds his nervous clumsiness endearing. She shows Naveen the old mill and tells him about his dream, leaning on him; as he leaves, she is torn apart between Naveen and her restaurant and asks the Evening Star for guidance. When Tiana discovers that Naveen was trying to propose to her, she runs in the crowd to find him; she is devastated to find Lottie and "Naveen" (actually his valet) together and is hurtful to Ray.

Figure 137. "Screenshots of 01:07:58, 01:09:27, 01:10:15, 01:10:48, 01:12:02, 01:13:28, 01:13:57 and 01:14:59 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

The voodoo amulet that gives the valet Naveen's appearance lands on her hands and she has to run away from Dr. Facilier and his shadows. Dr. Facilier transforms her into a human, shows her a vision of her restaurant and tries to convince her to give him the amulet; Tiana realises that her father did not get what he wanted, but what he needed, and that love is what is really important; she attempts to smash the amulet. She is transformed back into a frog and uses her tongue to regain the amulet and break it, defeating Dr. Facilier.

Figure 138. "Screenshots of 01:17:14, 01:18:02, 01:19:11, 01:20:24, 01:20:32, 01:20:50 and 01:20:57 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Tiana stops Lottie and Naveen from kissing, stating that her dream "wouldn't be complete without (Naveen) in it" and declaring her love for him; since it is past midnight, they both stay

frogs. They go to see a fatally wounded Ray and accompany his passing away. They are crying at the funeral, but then they are happy to see that he has ascended become a star and they hug.

Figure 139. "Screenshots of 01:23:16, 01:23:30, 01:25:21, 01:26:27, 01:26:50 and 01:26:59 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Mama Odie marries them in the bayou, they kiss and break the spell; Tiana delivers her last spoken line "You just kissed yourself a princess" and they kiss again. They marry in a sumptuous church and, after Tiana throws her bouquet to Lottie, leave on a luxurious carriage.

Figure 140. "Screenshots of 01:27:24, 01:27:48, 01:28:15, 01:28:22 and 01:28:53 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

Both pay for the old mill, get the key and renew the building together. In the successful restaurant "Tiana's Palace", Tiana reprises "Down in New Orleans" and greets her family and friends; Naveen and her dance, they kiss, she sings her last line "Dreams do come trues / In New Orleans" and they keep dancing as the camera pans out.

Figure 141. "Screenshots of 01:29:03, 01:29:11, 01:29:20, 01:30:09, 01:30:15 and 01:30:19 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, *The Princess and the Frog*, 2009.

6. Moana from *Moana* (2016)

“Moana sets sail on a daring mission to save her people. Along the way, she meets the mighty demigod Maui – together they cross the ocean on a fun-fille, action-packed voyage from Walt Disney Animation Studios” (Disney+, 2023).

6.1. Background information about *Moana* (2016) and Moana

Moana (2016) was directed by John Musker and Ron Clements. It stars Auli‘i Cravalho as the protagonist Moana, Dwayne Johnson as the demigod Maui, Rachel House as the grandmother Tala, Temuera Morrison as the father Tui and Nicole Scherzinger as the mother Sina. Most voice actors are of Polynesian ancestry: Rachel House and Temuera Morrison are of Māori descent and Dwayne Johnson is of Black Nova Scotian and Samoan descent. Auli‘i Cravalho and Nicole Scherzinger are Hawaiian.

Figure 6. “Original poster,” John Musker and Ron Clements, *Moana*, 2016.

The film is set in the fictional island of Motunui (based on Fiji, Samoa and Tonga) and draws elements from Polynesian mythology. Walt Disney Animation Studios created the Oceanic Story Trust, a Pacific Islander advisory board to ensure the cultural accuracy and sensitivity of the film (Herman, 2016).

In the film, Moana is the daughter of Tui and Sina, the chiefs of Motunui. Informal sources (Auger, 2020; Jordan, 2019; Bologna, 2018) attribute to her the age of 16 years. She has a pig called Pua and a rooster called Heihei as sidekicks.

6.2. Physical appearance of Moana

Moana is brown and has a muscular yet slender build. She has an hourglass figure with a waist-to-hip ratio of 0.65 and strong arms and legs. She has curly black hair, long to her waist. Her face is round and she has big brown eyes with straight eyelashes, black thick eyebrows, a broad nose and thick peach lips. Her teeth are white and straight and her ears are small and slightly protruding.

She wears a two-piece outfit consisting of a red crop top decorated with seashells and a layered beige skirt to below her knees with a red scarf wrapped around her waist; all items are made from natural fibres. She is always barefoot and mostly wears her hair loose. For most of the

film, she wears a necklace from her grandmother Tala with a big blue and white gem (containing the heart of Te Fiti) and pearls.

Figure 143. "Screenshots of 01:01:50 and 01:27:50 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

Throughout the film, Moana is seen in a variety of different outfits, including her clothes at different ages while growing up and a disguise to bait a sparkle-hungry monster.

Figure 144. "Screenshots of 00:05:06, 00:09:30, 00:11:33, 00:11:39, 00:13:06, 00:33:08, 00:59:47 and 01:35:58 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

6.3. Psychological traits of Moana

Moana can be described as resourceful, innovative, capable and smart. She is quick to find solutions to the problems of the people in Motunui (such as fixing roofs, saving the coconut plantations and finding new fishing areas); when she gets a foot stuck between corals underwater, she frees herself breaking them with a rock; she escapes from the cave where Maui

trapped her by using his own statue; she rescues the heart of Te Fiti from the coconut pirates Kakamora; she tricks Maui into helping her, and she also tricks the giant treasure-obsessed crab Tamatoa with a fake heart of Te Fiti; she learns quickly how to sail, she repairs her boat and she realises a way to make it around the lava monster Te Kā.

Figure 145. “Screenshots of 00:12:07, 00:13:30, 00:14:26, 00:19:41, 00:41:52, 00:48:35, 00:50:18, 01:04:40, 01:13:00, 01:22:33, 01:22:36 and 01:23:37 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

“Stubbornness and pride”, as stated by her grandmother Tala in the song “Where You Are” (00:09:55), are also Moana’s attributes. She is assertive and persevering, demanding time and time again that the demigod Maui accompany her to restore the heart of Te Fiti. However, her stubbornness and pride also sometimes make her reckless, such as when she mocks Maui by waving the heart of Te Fiti and inadvertently attracts the attack of the Kakamora, or when she disregards the advice of the more experienced Maui and decides to sail in the direction of Te Kā, causing harm to him and her ship.

Figure 146. "Screenshots of 00:36:33, 00:37:51, 00:43:14, 00:44:41 and 01:15:28 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

A core trait of Moana is her love for the ocean and for her island. She starts being divided, feeling that the call of the sea and her compromises as the future leader of her people are irreconcilable. She is ecstatic to discover that she descends from voyagers, meaning that her people and the ocean were once linked. Her eagerness to learn to sail is apparent. At the end of the film, she integrates these two passions, realising that they are not mutually exclusive.

Figure 147. "Screenshots of 00:16:50, 00:17:37, 00:26:07, 00:51:44, 01:20:57 and 01:21:01 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

Moana is athletic, agile and physically strong. Throughout the film she is depicted hanging, running, lifting or pulling heavy objects, contorting to get out a hole, fighting the Kakamora with a paddle, climbing a cliff and even punching Maui by mistake.

Figure 148. "Screenshots of 00:18:00, 00:18:08, 00:31:14, 00:34:19, 00:42:24, 00:46:34, 00:48:05, 00:55:42, 00:59:14, 01:05:07 and 01:24:00 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

She is also compassionate, caring and affectionate. At the beginning of the film, she protects a baby turtle from being eaten by birds on its way to the sea; she saves her rooster pet Heihei countless times, a running gag in the film, and also her pet pig Pua once; she provides emotional support to an islander who is painfully getting a tattoo, and to Maui when he is having self-doubts; she is visibly devastated by the death of her grandmother Tala and when she has to part ways with Maui, and she manages to restore the heart of Te Fiti and save the world thanks to her understanding of Te Kā.

Figure 149. "Screenshots of 00:05:17, 00:09:02 and 00:12:24 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

Figure 150. "Screenshots of 00:19:25, 00:30:12, 00:33:32, 01:10:25, 01:29:43 and 01:33:06 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

Lastly, Moana is courageous: unlike the other children of the island, who cry or faint upon hearing Tala's story about the end of the world, she is visibly delighted. She makes several leaps of faith, jumping off a cliff to catch Maui, who has stolen her boat, or jumping into the realm of monsters Lalotai. She also faces Te Kā completely alone and unarmed.

Figure 151. "Screenshots of 00:03:49, 00:42:32, 00:57:28 and 01:29:31 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

6.4. Relevant actions of Moana

The first time that Moana is seen in the film, she is still an infant. She is listening to the story about the end of the world as told by her grandmother Tala; unlike the other horrified children, she is fascinated by it. Her first word is: "Papa", directed to the chief of Motunui Tui. This establishes her as the daughter of the chief, and also as a curious and fearless child.

Figure 152. "Screenshots of 00:03:26 and 00:04:08 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

Moana goes to the beach, where she helps a little turtle safely get to the water. The ocean then lures her in with conch shells, plays with her, gives her the heart of Te Fiti and returns her to the beach.

Figure 153. "Screenshots of 00:05:31 and 00:06:55 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

Moana spends the next years obsessed with sailing and trying to go back to the sea, while being stopped by her father Tui time and time again. She has a special connection with her grandmother Tala, who is accepting of her love for the ocean.

Figure 154. "Screenshots of 00:08:16, 00:08:42 and 00:10:00 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

Chief Tui takes Moana to the highest peak of Motunui, where all past chiefs have piled stones "rais(ing) this whole island higher", and tells her that she is the future of their people. Moana finishes the song "Where You Are" by deciding to stay on the island and lead her people.

Figure 155. "Screenshots of 00:10:55 and 00:11:39 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

Moana does tasks around the village: fixing a roof, encouraging a man who is getting a tattoo, teaching the children how to dance and providing a solution for the diseased coconut trees. When the fisherman come back empty-handed, she suggests to fish beyond the reef. Chief Tui reprimands her for always wanting to be in the water, and later her mother Sina reveals to her that her father lost his best friend to drowning when he was younger.

Figure 156. "Screenshots of 00:12:33, 00:14:38 and 00:15:21 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

Moana sings "How Far I'll Go", where she reckons with the conflict between the ocean calling her and her role as the leader of Motunui. She boards a boat with her pet pig Pua and ventures beyond the reef, but the waves crash the boat, she nearly drowns and ends up with an injured foot.

Figure 157. "Screenshots of 00:17:44, 00:18:35, 00:19:20 and 00:19:35 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

Tala finds Moana on the beach and takes her to a cave where Moana finds several huge canoes; it is revealed to her that her people descend from voyagers. Tala gives the heart of Te Fiti to Moana and states that "the ocean chose (her)"; the ocean then greets Moana.

Figure 158. "Screenshots of 00:20:18, 00:21:59, 00:26:07 and 00:27:12 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

Moana tries to convince her father to voyage, find Maui, restore the heart of Te Fiti, stop the darkness and save the island, to no avail. Tala passes away after giving Moana her necklace and telling her to go on the mission. Moana reprises "How Far I'll Go", taking a boat and sailing beyond the reef.

Figure 159. "Screenshots of 00:28:37, 00:29:54 and 00:31:50 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

The next morning, Moana discovers her pet rooster Heihei on the boat; she will have to save it several times throughout the film. At night, Moana falls asleep while on course to find Maui, capsizes the boat while correcting the course and is overtaken by a storm.

Figure 160. "Screenshots of 00:33:18, 00:34:23 and 00:35:01 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

She wakes up on a beach, furious at the ocean for not helping her. She finds Maui and tries to convince him to sail with her, but Maui tricks her into a cave and steals her boat. Moana makes it out of the cave using Maui's statue and, with help of the ocean, boards the boat time and time again after Maui throws her overboard.

Figure 161. "Screenshots of 00:35:53, 00:37:59, 00:41:52 and 00:43:03 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

Moana mocks Maui's fear of the heart of Te Fiti by announcing it to the four winds and inadvertently attracting the attack of the coconut pirates Kakamora. They manage to steal the heart, but Moana boards the boat of the Kakamora, fights them with a paddle, retrieves the heart and makes it back to her canoe.

Figure 162. "Screenshots of 00:44:41, 00:48:05 and 00:48:44 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

Moana convinces Maui to help her by using his wish to be a hero. Moana asks Maui to teach her how to sail and, after he calls her a princess and she corrects him, he reluctantly gives in.

Figure 163. "Screenshots of 00:50:18, 00:52:10 and 00:52:42 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

Moana has a nightmare where the darkness destroys her island and family and wakes up screaming. They have arrived at the steep island where the entrance to the realm of monsters Lalotai lies. Maui wants to go alone, but Moana climbs up to the top of the island anyway. She gathers the courage and jumps into the entrance.

Figure 164. "Screenshots of 00:54:05, 00:54:56 and 00:57:28 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

She is immediately almost devoured, runs away and accidentally finds the cave of the giant crab Tamatoa. Moana follows Maui's plan and disguises herself in shiny things to serve as bait. Tamatoa sees through the plan, imprisons Moana and almost devours Maui, but Moana escapes, distracts Tamatoa with a replica of the heart of Te Fiti, gets Maui's hook and brings them both back to the surface.

Figure 165. "Screenshots of 00:58:13, 00:59:54, 01:04:02, 01:04:40 and 01:05:27 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

At night, Moana and Maui have a heart-to-heart, in which Moana admits that she feels unfit for the mission and encourages Maui in his doubts about his identity. With Moana's support, Maui learns to shapeshift again and he teaches her how to navigate.

Figure 166. "Screenshots of 01:08:40 and 01:12:39 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

Moana and Maui make it to Te Fiti's island, guarded by the lava monster Te Kā. Maui realises that they are not going to make it, but Moana stubbornly tries to find a way in and as result Maui's hook and Moana's canoe get damaged. Maui leaves her and Moana asks the ocean to take the heart of Te Fiti back, since she is "not the right person".

Figure 167. "Screenshots of 01:14:20, 01:15:28 and 01:18:16 (left to right)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

Crying desolated, the spirit of Tala appears and reassures her, and Moana reprises the song "How Far I'll Go" to realise her complete identity and the fact that the call is "inside (her)". She retrieves the heart of Te Fiti from the bottom of the ocean, repairs the boat and, with the help of Maui, manages to sail past Te Kā.

Figure 168. "Screenshots of 01:18:36, 01:20:09, 01:22:02, 01:25:49 and 01:26:04 (left to right, top to bottom)," John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

Seeing that that Te Fiti’s island is empty, she realises that the Te Kā is Te Fiti and restores her heart, stopping the darkness and saving the world.

Figure 169. “Screenshots of 01:28:11, 01:29:42 and 01:30:07 (left to right),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

Moana and Maui say goodbye and Moana goes back to Motunui, where she reunites with her family and village. Her last line of dialogue is: “I might have gone a little ways past the reef”, followed by “Pua!” when reuniting with her pet pig. Moana places a conch shell on the piled stones on the peak of Motunui, teaches her people how to sail and in the last frame she is standing on top of the mast and leading several boats to the horizon.

Figure 170. “Screenshots of 01:34:19, 01:34:25, 01:35:41, 01:35:48 and 01:36:11 (left to right, top to bottom),” John Musker and Ron Clements, Moana, 2016.

7. Raya from *Raya and the Last Dragon* (2021)

“Long ago, humans and dragons lived together harmoniously on the world of Kumandra. But when evil threatened the land, the dragons sacrificed themselves to save humanity. Now, 500 years later, lone warrior Raya must track down the legendary last dragon to stop the evil force that has returned... and once again threatens her home world” (Disney+, 2023).

7.1. Background information about *Raya and the Last Dragon* (2021) and Raya

Raya and the Last Dragon (2021) was directed by Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada. It stars Kelly Marie Tran as the protagonist Raya, Awkwafina as the dragon Sisu, Gemma Chan as the antagonist Namaari and Daniel Dae Kim as the father Chief Benja. Only one voice actor is of Southeast Asian ancestry: Kelly Marie Tran, of Vietnamese ancestry. Awkwafina is of Chinese and Korean ancestry, Gemma Chan is Hong-Kong Chinese and Daniel Dae Kim is of Korean ancestry.

The film is set in the fictional land of Kumandra (inspired by the Southeast Asian cultures of Brunei, Singapore, Laos, Thailand, Timor-Leste, Cambodia, Vietnam, Myanmar, Malaysia, Indonesia, and the Philippines). Walt Disney Animation Studios created the Southeast Asia Story Trust, group of cultural consultants (with expertise ranging from music and choreography to architecture and martial arts) to make the film’s details more authentic to Southeast Asia (Moon, 2021).

In the film, Raya is a warrior princess and the daughter of Chief Benja, the leader of the chiefdom of Hearth. Informal sources (Crossley, 2022) attribute to her the age of 18 years. She has a mix of armadillo and pill bug called Tuk Tuk as sidekick.

7.2. Physical appearance of Raya

Raya is tanned and has slender build. She has a mostly straight figure, with a waist-to-hip ratio of 0.7, and a relatively flat chest and narrow hips. She has straight back hair to the middle of her back, always styled with two braids on the top of her head. Her face is oval and she has big black slanted eyes with short eyelashes, a broad nose and medium thick peach lips. Her teeth are white and straight and her ears cannot be seen.

Figure 7. “Original poster,” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

She wears a two-piece outfit consisting of a yellow sleeveless wrapped shirt, a brown vest with pointy shoulders, a brown belt with a metal ring, loose-fitting long green pants and dark brown boots with red accents, as well as several bracelets on her arms. She usually wears a long red cape and a salakot on her head.

Figure 172. "Screenshots of 01:22:49, 01:11:15 and 00:59:36 (left to right)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

Raya is seen in three more outfits as a child, one of them being for training and one of them being formal attire.

Figure 173. "Screenshots of 00:04:57, 00:08:47 and 00:13:20 (left to right)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

7.3. Psychological traits of Raya

Raya is a princess warrior: strong, agile, athletic, flexible, brave and confident. Throughout the film, both as a child and as an adult, she is shown jumping and leaping, dodging traps, lifting or moving heavy objects or people and excelling at fighting with blades or hand-to-hand.

Figure 174. "Screenshots of 00:03:27, 00:04:52, 00:06:19, 00:16:05, 00:16:37 and 00:18:30 (left to right, top to bottom)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

Figure 175. "Screenshots of 00:22:10, 00:30:04, 00:30:26, 00:34:37, 00:47:17, 01:00:00, 01:00:21, 01:00:44, 01:19:28 and 01:20:56 (left to right, top to bottom)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

She is also a quick thinker. She astutely realises when a situation hides danger, finds a way to tricking her father Chief Benja by using his words against him, rapidly sees the association between Sisu touching a piece gem and her newly gained powers, strategically uses elements of her environment to help her escape and, finally, realises that the power of the gem actually comes from trust and not dragon magic, as previously thought.

Figure 176. "Screenshots of 00:05:38, 00:06:52, 00:28:07, 00:32:43, 00:34:54 and 01:24:08 (left to right, top to bottom)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

Another core personality trait of Raya is her distrust. As a child, she is already weary of the people of other chiefdoms. Once she is betrayed by the antagonist Namaari, her distrust only increases and becomes a leitmotiv for her: she is immediately suspicious of anyone she meets (for example, thinking that a child running a restaurant might want to poison her) and she states several times throughout the film: "You can't trust anyone."

Figure 177. "Screenshots of 00:08:54, 00:10:02, 00:38:49, 00:39:20, 00:51:02, 00:54:08, 00:54:37, 01:06:27 and 01:09:40 (left to right, top to bottom)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

Raya is smug and condescending. Her first line in the film is "I know what you're thinking", very much in keeping with a know-it-all attitude. As a child, she displays a patronizing superiority towards her father Chief Benja, although it does not seem to be intended to be hurting. As an adult, she keeps making smug comments to the dragon Sisu and her other travelling companions.

Figure 178. "Screenshots of 00:01:03, 00:04:08, 00:06:00, 00:06:55, 00:08:37, 00:30:08, 00:35:35, 00:50:25 and 00:53:51 (left to right, top to bottom)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

Figure 179. "Screenshots of 00:58:39 and 01:05:38 (left to right)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

Quite in line with her condescending tendencies, she has a hate-mock relationship with the antagonist Namaari. Raya has deep resentment towards her, but expresses it in sarcastic remarks and veiled insults. Raya even admits that "(she) know(s) how to push Namaari's buttons."

Figure 180. "Screenshots of 00:33:30, 00:34:02, 00:37:26, 00:58:35, 00:59:29 and 00:59:39 (left to right, top to bottom)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

However, Raya can also be friendly, caring and empathic. She praises several characters throughout the film, such as her sidekick Tuk Tuk. As a child, she seems to be deeply moved when she hears that the people from the chiefdom of Fang have been having food shortages. She worries about a baby girl who seems to be alone and, even after being conned by her, she welcomes her as part of her team upon discovering that she has no family left. She also shows compassion for a tough-looking villager who also lost his family. Finally, she decides to save several people from Fang instead of getting revenge.

Figure 181. "Screenshots of 00:04:38, 00:13:41 and 00:41:34 (left to right)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

Figure 182. "Screenshots of 00:44:47, 00:47:48, 00:48:07, 00:53:36, 00:57:57, 00:58:11, 01:14:33 and 01:22:36 (left to right, top to bottom)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

Raya feels deep grief and guilt for being the cause of her father Chief Benja turning to stone. She screams in denial right before losing him and spends the next years of her life trying to get him back. She mentions him several times, to talk about the way he was or the things he did, and he is part of her inspiration to start trusting other people at the end of the film.

Figure 183. "Screenshots of 00:19:21, 00:24:17, 00:28:24, 00:54:58, 01:10:14, 01:14:52 and 01:24:19 (left to right, top to bottom)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

Finally, Raya is a self-described “dragon nerd”. This is a trait that she has in common with Namaari, both as a child and as an adult. She is deeply commoved by seeing the dragon Sisu come to life.

Figure 184. "Screenshots of 00:12:49, 00:13:52, 00:30:38 and 01:16:10 (left to right)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

7.4. Relevant actions of Raya

Raya is first seen riding Tuk Tuk through a deserted area, completely covered except for her eyes. Her first line of dialogue is: "I know what you're thinking. A lone rider. A dystopian world." This frames her as being mysterious, severe and adventurous.

Figure 185. "Screenshots of 00:01:03 and 00:01:08 (left to right)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

In a flashback, a young Raya is seen deftly navigating traps to raid the Dragon Gem. She fights Chief Benja, the chief of Heart and her father, using sticks; she defeats him by setting a foot in the "inner circle", earning her right to be a Guardian of the Dragon Gem.

Figure 186. "Screenshots of 00:03:07, 00:04:06, 00:06:04, 00:06:52 and 00:07:22 (left to right, top to bottom)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

When Raya hears that her father Chief Benja has invited the leaders of the other chiefdoms, she plans how to stop them, as she considers her enemies. She is unsure if her father’s plan to reunite the nations into Kumandra is realistic.

Figure 187. “Screenshots of 00:09:52 and 00:10:26 (left to right),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

Raya invites everyone to eat and befriends Namaari, the daughter of the Chief of Fang. They bond over their passion for dragons and, upon receiving a necklace of the dragon Sisu, Raya takes Namaari to visit the Dragon Gem.

Figure 188. “Screenshots of 00:11:14, 00:12:22, 00:14:53 and 00:15:26 (left to right),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

Raya is kicked in the back and fights hand-to-hand to defend the gem; Chief Benja tries to pacify the situation, but the people from the other chiefdoms storm the place and fight over the gem; as it gets broken, it stops keeping the evil Druun at bay. Raya tries to help an injured Chief Benja run away; he gives a crying Raya a piece of the gem and throws her into the river to protect her from the Druun before being turned into stone.

Figure 189. “Screenshots of 00:15:43, 00:16:30, 00:17:39, 00:18:35, 00:19:17 and 00:19:32 (left to right, top to bottom),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

In the present, Raya finds the last possible location for the dragon Sisu. Crying, Raya states that she needs her help to save the world and bring her father back. Thanks to a ritual, she brings Sisu back to life and they decide to collect all the gem pieces, reassemble it and destroy the Druun.

Figure 190. "Screenshots of 00:22:25, 00:24:17, 00:24:44, 00:25:56 and 00:28:22 (left to right, top to bottom)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

Averting traps and dangers, they retrieve the gem piece held by the skeleton of the chief of Tail. Namaari finds them and they run away with the help of Tuk Tuk, landing on a boat owned by an entrepreneur child captain. Raya convinces him to bring them to Talon.

Figure 191. "Screenshots of 00:31:38, 00:32:53, 00:35:45 and 00:36:54 (left to right)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

Raya asks Sisu to hide in human form. On the way to Talon, they encounter several stone people. Raya convinces Sisu to stay on the boat to protect her and ventures into the city to retrieve the gem piece held by the chief of Talon. She is conned by a baby and her half-monkey, half-catfish buddies, but manages to retrieve the gem pieces; Raya offers the baby to “earn some honest loot” by helping her reach the chief of Talon. Raya discovers that the gem piece is with the mother of the chief of Talon and manages to rescue Sisu from her before she is turned to stone.

Figure 192. “Screenshots of 00:38:44, 00:43:32, 00:44:47, 00:45:12, 00:47:35, 00:48:48 and 00:50:23 (left to right, top to bottom),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

On her way to Spine, Raya helps the child captain out by pretending to play hide and seek with the baby and then has a conversation with Sisu where she states her distrustful and pessimistic worldview.

Figure 193. “Screenshots of 00:53:44 and 00:54:07 (left to right),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

Sisu and Raya make it to Spine but are immediately captured by a tough-looking villager; the child captain rescues them. Namaari finds them and Raya asks the tough-looking villager for help. Raya faces Namaari on her own; they fight with swords and hand-to-hand, and Raya is thrown to the ground several times; Sisu and the other rescue her.

Figure 194. “Screenshots of 00:57:57, 00:58:58, 00:59:31, 01:00:08, 01:00:33 and 01:00:44 (left to right, top to bottom),” Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

Figure 195. "Screenshots of 01:01:07 and 01:01:42 (left to right)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

The child captain, the con baby and the tough-looking villager want to help reassemble the Dragon Gem and they all bond thanks to Sisu. They try to devise a plan to retrieve the gem piece from Fang; Sisu takes Raya to Heart and shows her stone siblings to her, trying to convey the importance of trust. Raya visits the statue of her father and decides to follow Sisu's plan and give Namaari a gift, namely her necklace of Sisu, as a sign of goodwill.

Figure 196. "Screenshots of 01:03:02, 01:03:41, 01:06:39, 01:09:31 and 01:11:00 (left to right, top to bottom)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

The whole team is having soup together when they receive Namaari's sign that she accepts a meeting. Raya and Namaari meet; Namaari tries to steal all the gem pieces and Sisu by aiming a crossbow at Raya. Raya tries to disarm Namaari, but causes her to shoot and kill Sisu.

Figure 197. "Screenshots of 01:14:46, 01:15:58, 01:17:27 and 01:17:37 (left to right)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

Raya goes to Fang alone to kill Namaari; she manages to disarm her but at the last second, decides to spare her life. She joins her team into rescuing people from Fang from the Druun; Raya, the child captain, the con baby, the tough-looking villager and Namaari fall into a hole and fight off the Druun with the dying gem pieces.

Figure 198. "Screenshots of 01:18:51, 01:19:24, 01:20:40, 01:21:33, 01:21:52, 01:22:16 and 01:23:03 (left to right, top to bottom)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

Raya realises that trust is the secret of the Dragon Gem and decides to take the first step and give her piece to Namaari; Raya gets turned into stone. The rest of the team reassemble the Dragon Gem before turning into stone and all come back to life. Raya and Sisuu reunite and hug, and the other characters join them.

Figure 199. "Screenshots of 01:23:44, 01:24:37, 01:24:56, 01:27:56, 01:31:15 and 01:31:47 (left to right, top to bottom)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, *Raya and the Last Dragon*, 2021.

Raya goes back to Heart and finds her father alive; she hugs him crying. Raya's last line of dialogue is "Ba? Welcome to Kumandra", as people from all the regions join them. The last time Raya is seen on screen, she is walking while embracing her father next to the other people in direction to Heart.

Figure 200. "Screenshots of 01:33:23, 01:34:21 and 01:34:40 (left to right)," Don Hall and Carlos López Estrada, Raya and the Last Dragon, 2021.

Appendix II. Timeline of white female, non-white male and non-white female Disney main characters

The following timeline was created by the author and includes all white female, non-white male and non-white female Disney main characters (in orange, yellow and green, respectively) identified in the formation of the analysis corpus. On the left side, the conventional classification; on the right side, the phases identified in the discussion.

